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**Platforming Digital Cultural Heritage: History, Curation, and Platform
Governance on Google Arts & Culture**

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**Platforming Digital Cultural Heritage: History, Curation, and Platform
Governance on Google Arts & Culture**

**by
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Abstract

Platforming Digital Cultural Heritage: History, Curation, and Platform Governance on Google Arts & Culture

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This dissertation examines the intersection of cultural institutions and digital platforms, using Google Arts & Culture (GA&C) as a case study of platformization in the cultural sector. Theoretically, it situates GA&C within the intellectual and institutional lineage of the virtual museum, frames the platform as a networked memory institution with risks of digital enclosure and privatization, and unpacks its sociotechnical power through its various governance mechanisms. This study addresses three primary research questions: How did the platform evolve from the original Google Art Project into the current iteration of GA&C? How do the platform's curatorial interventions and interface design shape content presentation? How do cultural institutions use the platform? A mixed-methods approach is adopted, including archival analysis of the platform's website, mobile app, and outreach emails, content analysis of a highly curated section of the platform, visual analysis of the platform's interface architecture, and semi-structured interviews with partner institutions. Key findings reveal a history of convergence among different cultural institutions on the platform but also a divergence from facilitating cultural institutions to engaging audiences through playful experience. The GA&C team plays an essential curatorial and editorial role in deciding project topics and managing featured content, while the platform's interface prescribes a passive mode of user engagement that falls short of the promises of a truly participatory culture. While cultural institutions hoped for an aggregate portal with technological support from Google to expand their digital presence, the alignment between the platform and the partners, often a response to the partner's internal digital strategy or external factors such as the global pandemic, ended up being contingent and experimental due to various issues on both sides. Finally, this dissertation also discusses the implications of GA&C for the participatory culture, the editorial role of digital platforms, and the datafication of arts and culture.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The possibilities of reproducing created colored harmonies: pictures, even in their contemporary form, enable many people to procure stimulating color compositions [...], although the radio picture service as a source of more intensive distribution is probably still to come. (Moholy-Nagy, 1925/1969, p. 25)

We [...] have far more great works available to refresh our memories than those which even the greatest of museums could bring together. For a “Museum without Walls” is coming into being, and (now that the plastic arts have invented their own printing-press) it will carry infinitely farther that revelation of the world of art. (Malraux, 1953/1974, p. 16)

When László Moholy-Nagy, artist and a fervent champion for the integration of technology into the arts, imagined the *domestic pinacotheca* in the 1920s, and when André Malraux, novelist and France’s inaugural Minister of Cultural Affairs, conceived the *imaginary museum* in the 1950s, they would never have foreseen the kind of intensive distribution afforded by what human histories have come to know as the Internet. Decades later, the idea of a virtual museum, Internet “picture service” carrying us “infinitely farther” into the world of art, has become the reality, if not the default and the norm, and unfortunately the only option for many people to access arts and culture during the global pandemic. Despite the museum’s traditional focus on material artifacts, media and communication technologies – from television to the Internet, from video disc to virtual reality – have been an integral part of the museum’s institutional history in the twentieth century, through which artworks have metamorphized through the ages of mechanical reproduction (Benjamin, 1936/2019), digital reproduction (Davis, 1995; Schweibenz, 2018), and what we may as well now call algorithmic reproduction: from the fleeting fervor for digital artworks traded using NFTs (non-fungible tokens) to the meteoric rise of images created by generative AI. At its core, this dissertation is about the intersection between museums and media technologies, focusing on the emergence and dominance of digital platforms as they have transformed and continue to shape all aspects of social life.

When the pandemic abruptly shut down most museums in early 2020, Internet search traffic for “Google Arts & Culture” saw a fivefold increase, as art lovers and cultural institutions flocked to the site hosting digital museum collections and scrambled to keep themselves and their audiences engaged (Gaskin, 2020). Moholy-Nagy and Malraux would have been heartened to see the initiative’s mission “to preserve and bring the world’s art and culture online so it’s

accessible to anyone, anywhere” (Google, 2020), but the idealistic and egalitarian corporate rhetoric obscures as much as it reveals. Google’s expansion into arts and culture, as I argue in this dissertation, deserves our critical attention because the cultural heritage commons is at stake. Digital platforms provided by private technology companies, often disguised in the discourse of democratizing public access, have been accused of facilitating economic processes centered on the collection of user data and the creation of platform-dependent social transactions. Is Google Arts & Culture (GA&C) yet another chapter in this narrative? In this dissertation, I seek to provide a nuanced account of how cultural institutions have responded to Google’s venture into the cultural heritage sector.

This is by no means a deterministic account of how one company single-handedly attempts to disrupt an entire sector, for better or worse. Google is far from the first or only player, public or private, that has attempted to digitize, preserve, and disseminate our collective cultural heritage. Numerous local, national, and supranational efforts have predated or paralleled GA&C (Marcum & Schonfeld, 2021; Valtýsson, 2020a). What makes the emergence of the initiative uniquely emblematic, on top of its global reach and totalizing overtone, is its situation at the convergence of two broader trends: museums have increasingly embraced, or been compelled to rely on, media technologies and platform companies for both their internal functions and external communications, while digital platforms, dominated by U.S.-based technology companies, have increasingly penetrated the cultural sector, both supplementing and substituting the functions of traditional memory institutions. The confluence of museums and platforms perfectly instantiates the process of *platformization*, as the infrastructures, economic processes, and governance frameworks of digital platforms have restructured the organizational practices of cultural institutions (Poell et al., 2019). In this dissertation, I analyze the GA&C platform to understand how this process of platformization has unfolded among cultural institutions, especially the ways in which the platform’s infrastructural services, economic logic, and governance mechanisms have reshaped their everyday operations.

Museums and Platforms

Despite the rise of platformization as a conceptual framework in recent academic discourse, especially in media and communication studies, the intertwining of cultural institutions

and digital platforms has long existed in practice. Many innovative museum initiatives emerging since the 2000s have been gradually outsourced to private digital platforms. For example, The Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) launched its online educational program MoMA Learning in 2006 and a blog site *Inside/Out* in 2009. Both initiatives were hailed as exemplary efforts that extended the museum's educational and communicative functions beyond its physical locations (Bautista, 2014). However, MoMA announced in 2016 that the blog would cease production and be migrated to Medium, a private online publishing platform (Persse, 2016). MoMA Learning was phased out in 2018 and moved to Coursera, a commercial platform that specializes in providing online courses (MoMA, n.d.). In a similar fate, ArtBabble, an award-winning art video hosting service launched in 2009 by the Indianapolis Museum of Art and once dubbed "the YouTube of the arts" (Jamieson, 2009), ceased operation in 2015 and was officially shut down in 2019, citing both unsustainable technology and competitive content hosting services (e.g., YouTube and Vimeo) as reasons for its discontinuation (ArtBabble, n.d.). More recently, museums have increasingly relied on social media platforms to communicate with their audiences (Russo, 2012; Laws, 2015; Wilson-Barnao, 2017; Valtýsson, 2022). Even when they are not intentionally operating on any specific platforms, tracking technologies (e.g., cookies and pixels) that are built into museum websites can still collect, aggregate, and monetize the behavioral data of website visitors, not only making these data "platform ready" (Helmond, 2015) but also rendering cultural institutions unwitting contributors to an enormous ad-based business model widely adopted by platform companies such as Facebook and Google. These cases of platform mechanisms intertwining with institutional practices provide the background against which GA&C emerged as yet another instance of platformization.

The reasons behind the confluence of cultural institutions and digital platforms are multifold. Museums have long sought to redefine their role in society, especially since the emergence of the *new museology* as an intellectual and ideological discourse in the late 1980s. This movement called on museums to prioritize their institutional purposes over technical methods (e.g., curatorial and displaying techniques), challenged the centrality of collections and curatorship, interrogated their cultural authority vis-à-vis the public, and foregrounded their informational base and educational function (Vergo, 1989; Bennett, 1990; Stam, 1993). The

transition to a new museology required museums to transform themselves “from being about something to being for somebody” (Weil, 1999, p. 229). The advent of Web 2.0 technologies in the early 2000s reinforced this institutional reorientation, championing (perhaps too optimistically) the rhetoric of their democratizing potential. Regardless, a *participatory turn* gradually emerged in museum studies around the 2010s and promoted such crowdsourcing and co-creation practices as social tagging and community archiving (Simon, 2010; Giaccardi, 2012; Cook, 2013; Kidd, 2014; Bautista, 2014; Laws, 2015). These internal transformations have motivated museums to increasingly focus on the needs of the audiences and meet them where they are. Ultimately, communicative practices mediated by digital platforms have come to play a constitutive role for the very identity of the museum itself (Drotner et al., 2019).

Externally, the rise of neoliberalism in many western democracies in the latter half of the twentieth century has characterized the broader cultural policy environments in which cultural institutions increasingly have to operate with a market-oriented mentality (Hesmondhalgh et al., 2015; McGuigan, 2005). As a consequence, corporate sponsorship has gradually replaced the funding of arts and culture through direct public subsidy, whereas public-oriented cultural institutions have increasingly been pressured to run as financially self-sustaining private businesses (McGuigan, 2005). In particular, museums were forced to abandon the old *selling* mode, in which they convince the public to accept their cultural offerings, and operate under a new *marketing* mode, in which they are expected to identify and satisfy the public’s needs on its own terms (Weil, 1999). Museums, as entrepreneurial institutions within a nation’s cultural industry, now must collaborate and/or compete with other entertainment and tourist destinations to demonstrate their added value to a public increasingly understood as consumers rather than citizens (Hesmondhalgh & Pratt, 2005; Miller & Yúdice, 2002).

Although the neoliberal marketization of the cultural sector occurred in most West European and North American countries, it is important to emphasize the distinct cultural policy environment in the U.S., which, for historical and political reasons, lacks the sort of centralized public support for the arts by the national government commonly observed in many European countries. Instead, philanthropic and nonprofit organizations, private individuals, and local governments play a primary role in supporting cultural institutions (Wyszomirski, 2004; Mulcahy,

2006; Cherbo et al., 2008). This policy distinction, along with other differences in terms of government regulation, has granted the private sector an outsized influence on the U.S. cultural sector. It is for these reasons that this dissertation will focus primarily on cultural institutions in the U.S. and how they use and interact with GA&C.

Along Came Google

Having established a burgeoning web search business, Google's first major foray into the cultural sector started in 2004 with its announcement of the Google Print project. Later renamed Google Book Search and eventually Google Books, this initiative sought to digitize books from publishers and library partners worldwide and allow the public to search and view a digital copy of the scanned materials, in full-text or preview snippets depending on the book's copyright status. Since its very inception, however, Google Books was criticized on the grounds of copyright infringement, user privacy violations, cultural ethnocentrism, anti-competitive practices, and an overall lack of transparency regarding the scanning of books (Jeanneney, 2007; Levy, 2011; Vaidhyathan, 2011; Thylstrup, 2019; Marcum & Schonfeld, 2021). After a series of lawsuits and negotiations, Google and the publishers reached a settlement in 2011 that would have created a business model to distribute subscription and advertising revenue among all the parties, but this settlement was rejected by a U.S. federal judge (Page, 2011). The scanning operations drastically slowed down afterwards and were all but shut down by 2017 (Somers, 2017).

Describing Google's vision of the universal library as a technocentric approach to an old idea, Marcum and Schonfeld (2021) provided a detailed account of how the company attempted to disrupt the library and publishing communities, "a story about the limitations of disruptive techno-solutionism in the face of well-coordinated incumbent market leaders, and a story in which some librarians have limited the dream because of financial restrictions and failure of will" (p. 10). Taking a more sympathetic view towards the librarians, Thylstrup (2019) considered their responses not so much a failure of will as a form of active resistance that defended a *library ethos* fundamental to state-subsidized cultural institutions that promise to deliver access and transparency to the wider public in exchange for their financial and moral support. Regardless of the role of the libraries in the eventual doom of Google's endeavor, "the clash between the traditional infrastructures of the analog book and the new infrastructures of Google Books was

symptomatic of the underlying radical reorganization of information from a state of trade and exchange to a state of constant transmission and contagion” (p. 46). This radical reorganization, as it turned out, soon crept into the museum sector.

While Google was still mired in lawsuits and settlement negotiations, the Google Cultural Institute – a somewhat opaque internal team whose exact organizational status was never publicly specified – launched the Art Project on February 1 of 2011, with initial contributions from 17 world-renowned museums in nine countries (Sood, 2011). Renamed Google Arts & Culture in 2016 (Osborn, 2016), the platform claims to offer, as of June 2024, more than 3,000 participating cultural institutions free access to digitization services, a collection management system, and an online publishing platform (Google, 2020). For individual users, the platform’s main features include virtual tours of the museum space or heritage site, “in-painting tours” that guide users to zoom in on the artworks to explore hidden details, and camera-based mobile tools using VR, AR, and other AI-enabled functions. A dedicated “Experiments” section also features games and visualization projects by artists and creative coders in collaboration with GA&C.¹

At first glance, Google seemed to have learned its lesson from the Books project: GA&C was designated as a non-profit initiative from the very beginning,² and participating institutions are required to provide only copyright-free or copyright-cleared content. More importantly, despite some initial hesitation among museum professionals, viewing artworks online turned out to supplement rather than substitute for in-person visits, gradually dispelling concerns about possible revenue loss that angered many book publishers and authors in the case of Google Books (Kelly, 2013). Although not without criticism, media coverage and institutional partners have mostly lauded the expanded access and democratizing potential of the platform for students, educators, and art lovers who may otherwise never have the opportunity to visit these museums in person (Berwick, 2011; Pfanner, 2011; Sooke, 2011; Stromberg, 2012; Warman, 2011). What could possibly go wrong?

¹ In December 2023, Google announced that it would gradually phase out the “Experiments with Google” website and transition to Labs.Google, a new site dedicated to AI technologies. See <https://experiments.withgoogle.com>.

² This “non-profit” self-designation was changed to “non-commercial” in May 2022. See Chapter 4, footnote 17.

Enclosure and Platformization

Google's expansion into arts and culture deserves critical interrogation because the digital cultural commons is at stake. Vaidhyanathan (2011) first popularized the phrase "the Googlization of everything" and cautioned against the still rising company as a ubiquitous force permeating our contemporary culture. Vaidhyanathan considered Google Books an attempt to privatize and commercialize libraries and academia, whose core purpose should be "to act as an information commons for the community" (p. 164). Similarly, Pélissier (2021) considered libraries as part of the heritage commons, arguing that Google Books revealed an "intrusion and domination of private companies in a sector hitherto reserved for non-market cultural institutions" (p. 150). The growing danger of the private sector intruding the heritage commons, or "the enclosure of the intangible commons of the mind" (Boyle, 2003, p. 37), is why initiatives such as GA&C deserve more critical scrutiny.

At the heart of the *second enclosure* (Boyle, 2003) is a wide array of legal, managerial, and technological strategies for private corporations to control and commodify data, information, and intellectual property. Pessach (2008), for instance, argued that copyright laws are responsible for not only commodifying both the inputs and the outputs of traditional memory institutions, but also making them more inclined to adopt proprietary practices. Wilson-Barnao (2017) examined how the rhetoric of access transforms the museum from a community space to an advertising resource. In other words, the enclosure of our digital cultural commons, often disguised in the discourse of access, is ultimately designed to facilitate processes of *datafication* as a new form of extraction that transforms hitherto unmeasurable social interactions into massive amounts of behavioral data (Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013; van Dijck, 2014; Mejjas & Couldry, 2019; Zuboff, 2019).

Digital platforms facilitate these processes by bridging interactions between users, third parties, and institutional actors such as libraries and museums. When GA&C offers free tools and resources to institutional partners, it also enables the platform's expansion "by codifying and standardizing infrastructural access and integration" (Poell et al., 2022, p. 67), paving the way for the formalization of platform-dependent cultural heritage reproduction. This dependence, in turn, is maintained through various governance mechanisms, ranging from contracts and access

policies, interface design, content curation, and infrastructural integration. Despite the claims of platform companies, platforms are “neither neutral nor value-free constructs; they come with specific norms and values inscribed in their architectures” (van Dijck et al., 2018, p. 3). The ideological dimension of platforms, if not digital technologies at large, has a long intellectual history, from the classic aphorism “code is law” (Lessig, 1999), to understanding new media as a language with its distinct governing principles (Manovich, 2002), default settings as behavioral nudges expressive of an ideology (Vaidhyathan, 2011), and the interface as an enveloping discourse with unique effects (Galloway, 2012; Ash, 2015; Stanfill, 2015). Platforms, in short, “don’t just mediate public discourse, they constitute it” (Gillespie, 2018, p. 22).

From terms of service to interface architecture, many governance mechanisms are present on GA&C, but content curation, given the term’s original use in the museum context, deserves some special attention. Although institutional partners can curate online exhibits, many of them have in fact been created by GA&C itself, which already refutes any claim of the platform as a mere facilitator. In addition to deciding what content appears on its front page and what trending topics to promote on a regular basis, GA&C literalized its editorial role in August 2020 when the platform added a new section called “Today’s top picks,” showcasing five stories every day usually located at the top of the site’s homepage. Since these picks are not personalized based on user profiles, what has been the basis for the selection? These perhaps incidental acts of cultural canonization became problematic when a special project about Egypt was introduced on August 21, 2021. Titled *Ancient Egypt: Mummies and Mysteries*, this project featured collections exclusively from 14 European and American museums, and not a single Egyptian institution was included. Another incident happened on August 22, 2022, when the “Museum Explorer” section at the top of the homepage featured the National Palace Museum in Taipei, but following the link would somehow lead users to the landing page of The Palace Museum in Beijing. Was the *Ancient Egypt* project an example of digital cultural colonialism (Kizhner et al., 2020) that continues the exploitation and misrepresentation of non-western cultural heritage in the digital space? Did the mix-up between the two Palace Museums not reflect the platform’s embedded lack of cultural sensitivity towards historical conflicts and contemporary geopolitics? We may never have the answers, but these questions are precisely why Google’s editorial interventions in

the cultural sector need to be critically interrogated, especially when these deeply political interventions are being delivered through platforms that are too often veneered with an “aura of truth, objectivity, and accuracy” (boyd & Crawford, 2012, p. 663).

Organization of the Dissertation

From the enclosure of cultural commons, to the platformization of museum collections, and to the creation of a new curatorial regime, Google’s continuing venture into the cultural sector involves more than what its idealistic corporate mission claims. This dissertation revolves around the notion of platformization as it unfolds in the cultural sector through the ongoing expansion of the GA&C platform, which itself has undergone significant changes in the past 13 years. Just as Poell et al. (2019) dissected the concept of platformization as the mutual articulation between institutional changes and cultural practices, so too this dissertation approaches the platformization of museum collections from the perspective of both the platform and the participating institutions. This two-pronged approach is based on the understanding that platform governance is “multiple, contingent and contested” (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019, p. 9). Although GA&C imposes institutional and productive power through myriad governance mechanisms, these power dynamics are not unconditional or uncontested, as cultural institutions may strive to retain their agency and autonomy by selectively accepting what Google has to offer based on their own needs. This dissertation therefore investigates what the platform affords its partner institutions and how they in turn use the platform. Specifically, in this dissertation I seek to address three primary research questions:

- RQ1: How did the initiative evolve from the original Google Art Project into the current iteration of Google Arts & Culture?
- RQ2: How does Google Arts & Culture present cultural content on the platform?
 - RQ2a: What types of curatorial interventions does the platform perform?
 - RQ2b: How does the platform’s interface design condition the presentation of individual cultural objects?
- RQ3: How do cultural institutions use Google Arts & Culture?
 - RQ3a: Why did institutions decide (not) to join the platform?

- RQ3b: How do institutions utilize the platform's tools and resources?
- RQ3c: How is the use of the platform influenced by its governance mechanisms?

The remainder of the dissertation is organized as follows: in Chapter 2, I begin with a description of the platform's current operations, before presenting a literature review of existing research to contextualize the discussion of GA&C. In particular, I focus on 1) the concept of the virtual museum, emphasizing the role of audiences as active participants, 2) the emergence of networked memory institutions and the implications of datafication and digital enclosure, and 3) the process of platformization, with an emphasis on the platform's governance mechanisms. In Chapter 3, I present my analytical methods and empirical data used to address not only what the platform does but also how its institutional partners use the platform. I adopted a mixed-methods approach that includes archival analysis, content analysis, discursive interface analysis, and in-depth interviews. In Chapters 4-6, I present the findings of my empirical research and situate these findings within the theoretical framework established in Chapter 2. Chapter 4 addresses RQ1 by reconstructing a historical timeline of the platform, highlighting the trend of convergence on the platform and the divergence of the mobile app into elements of gamification. Chapter 5 addresses RQ2 by shedding light on the decision-making processes of the GA&C team and foregrounding the normative nature of the platform's interface architecture. Chapter 6 addresses RQ3 by identifying the motivations of cultural institutions to work with Google, perceived benefits and concerns, and how, if at all, the collaboration has changed the institution's internal practices. Ultimately, as Google continues to structure and order access to our collective knowledge and culture, I seek to unveil what the company's foray into arts and culture truly means for cultural institutions beyond the glorified rhetoric of preservation and universal access.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

In this chapter, I describe the Google Arts & Culture platform in more detail and discuss existing research related to the virtual museum, digital enclosure, and platform governance to contextualize the analysis of the platform. These concepts situate GA&C within broader scholarly discourses about the intersection between cultural institutions and media technologies. As I seek to demonstrate in this chapter, the historical vision of the virtual museum, from avant-garde artists in the 1920s to museum practitioners in the 1990s, emphasized the value of experimenting with media technologies to expand access to museum collections, highlighted the importance of interactivity in exhibition design, and sought to engage the audiences as active participants rather than passive spectators. The GA&C platform, while implementing many aspects of this concept, has not always lived up to the full potential of the participatory culture. Instead of engaging users as active, co-creating participants, the platform's main features – from virtual tours to interactive games – equate active participation with, if not reducing it to, mere interactivity, thus perpetuating a passive mode of cultural consumption. Moreover, the rhetoric of democratizing access through new technologies belies the invisible processes of datafication, enclosing traditional memory institutions inside new economic and cultural infrastructures controlled by private corporations. For GA&C, this control is realized and reinforced through a series of governance mechanisms and ultimately serves to produce new forms of digital cultural heritage that are decidedly platform dependent.

Far from being placed on a pedestal, the museum as a social institution also wields tremendous power in representing or repressing the collective cultural memories of our contemporary societies. Storytelling with decontextualized artifacts is inherently political, and curation is an interpretative process literally combining selective inclusion and (more often than not) systematic exclusion. The western art canon established over the past few centuries by the museum is more than an aesthetic assertion, “not simply a designation by category, but a performative act that exalts one thing over another” (Hein, 1993, p. 556), “a structure of power, a criterion of authority, and a legitimizing argument” (Rodríguez-Ortega, 2018. p. 3). Digital platforms inherit and amplify the power of storytelling and canonization and continue to, selectively and systematically, exalt and legitimize one thing over another. The difference, at least

in the case of GA&C, is that private companies, algorithms, and users have in part usurped the position of power long held by curators, historians, and sometimes politicians. The increasing dependence on platforms challenges the authority and even legitimacy of traditional cultural institutions. This dissertation analyzes the kind of platform power Google wields over the cultural sector and unpacks its control based on the concepts of virtual museum, digital enclosure, and platform governance.

This chapter is organized into four sections. First, I provide a brief summary of the initiative's official origin story and early development based on press coverage at the time, as well as a description of the platform in its current edition, including the conditions under which cultural institutions can join the platform, the tools and services it provides for partner institutions, and the types of content and activities offered to users. In the next section, I trace the intellectual origin and institutional history of the virtual museum, as avant-garde artists in the 1920s and museum practitioners in the 1990s experimented with new technologies to expand public access to museum collections beyond their physical walls. In the third section, I examine the emergence of networked memory institutions and the digital enclosure of the cultural heritage commons, which transform public cultural resources into private economic assets through datafication. In the final section, I present the platform as a new form of economic structure, social paradigm, and productive power, highlighting the ways in which it has reshaped various social spheres with infrastructural services and governance frameworks through the process of platformization. These four sections combine to provide the historical background and theoretical framework of the dissertation and set up the next chapter in which I introduce the analytical methods and empirical data used for the analyses.

From the Art Project to Google Arts & Culture

The Official Origin Story

“In the beginning, there was Google Books.” This is how the official Google Books website introduces the project (Google Books, 2012). The biblical overtone ties the conception of Google Books to the original vision of the company's cofounders Sergey Brin and Larry Page, when they were still graduate students working on a project funded by the Stanford Digital Library Project in

1996. Both in terms of the intended goal (to build a universally accessible digital library) and the underlying technology (a crawler called BackRub, the basis of the PageRank algorithms), Google Books was *the* prototypical Google. Fast forward to February 2011: Google's universal digital museum ambition had a much humbler beginning. In an official blog post, the Head of then Google Art Project Amit Sood announced:

It started when a small group of us who were passionate about art got together to think about how we might use our technology to help museums make their art more accessible – not just to regular museum-goers or those fortunate to have great galleries on their doorsteps, but to a whole new set of people who might otherwise never get to see the real thing up close.

We're also lucky here to have access to technology like Picasa and App Engine and to have colleagues who love a challenge – like building brand-new technology to enable Street View to go indoors! Thanks to this, and our unique collaboration with museums around the world, we were able to turn our 20% project into something you can try out for yourself today at www.googleartproject.com. (Sood, 2011)

The 20% project refers to the company's "20% rule" that encourages employees, "in addition to their regular projects, to spend 20% of their time working on what they think will most benefit Google" (Page & Brin, 2004). The beginning of the Art Project was thus a side project for art-loving employees who sought to utilize Google's existing technologies – Picasa (a retired image viewing and organizing system), App Engine (a cloud computing platform for developing and hosting web applications), and Street View – to give users "a fun and unusual way to interact with art – and hopefully [inspire them] to visit the real thing" (Sood, 2011). The features highlighted in the blog post showcased exactly what these technologies were capable of: zooming into the artworks in greater detail, exploring the museum space in virtual tours, and building one's own personalized collection to share online.

Not unlike Google's early book digitization efforts, the operation of the Art Project was shrouded in secrecy, except for a handful of official blog posts and media interviews with team members over the years that occasionally shed light on its otherwise obscure development. An *Art in America* article revealed that Google executives began reaching out to museum partners in mid-2009 (Berwick, 2011). In a 2013 interview with *The Guardian*, Sood suggested that he started working on the Art Project full time since mid-2012 and that the project was part of the Google

Cultural Institute (Caines, 2013). However, most news media, scholars, and even some Google employees would simply use “Art Project” and “Cultural Institute” interchangeably. A 2011 *New York Times* article commented that “the activities of the Cultural Institute differ from some other Google initiatives in that there are few outward signs of the company’s involvement” (Pfanner, 2011), attesting to the lack of clarity and transparency regarding the role of the Cultural Institute within the company’s overall organizational structure. Indeed, the limited press releases and news articles over the years have painted a rather fragmented picture of the initiative’s early development. Its official origin story is incomplete and conveniently sanitized at best, obscuring, as I demonstrate in Chapters 4 and 5, the essential editorial and curatorial functions it fulfills.

The Transition to GA&C Now

The Art Project’s initial 17 partners included some of the world’s most popular museums: The Metropolitan Museum of Art and MoMA in New York City, the State Hermitage Museum in St. Petersburg, Tate Britain and The National Gallery in London, the Museo Nacional Centro de Arte Reina Sofía in Madrid, the Uffizi Gallery in Florence, and the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam (Sood, 2011). As of June 2024, the number of GA&C’s partner institutions worldwide has reached over 3,000. Every partner institution has a home page on the platform, typically including a short description with links to its social media profiles, stories curated by the institution, a preview of the entire collection based on art medium, style, or topic, a strip of thumbnails showing all uploaded items sorted by popularity, time, or color, a list of available virtual tours, and an embedded Google Maps interface followed by practical information such as opening times and current exhibitions.

While Google reached out to its earliest museum partners, the initiative underwent major expansions in 2012, when it began allowing institutions to self-nominate through a signup form that gathers preliminary information about the potential partners (Google, 2020). To this day, however, the platform still describes itself as “accessible by invitation only” (Google, 2015a), and it is unclear what eligibility requirements Google takes into account when reviewing partner applications. Regardless, as more institutions have joined the initiative, what used to be a process of collaboration and negotiation – in which cultural institutions and Google acknowledged and therefore legitimized each other – has been replaced by a lopsided power structure in which,

especially for smaller institutions, simply being approved and featured on the platform has become a factor that in itself adds value to their collections (Rodríguez-Ortega, 2018).

Despite the platform's mission statement that focuses on "cultural institutions and artists" and an FAQ stipulating that the platform is only "open to non-profit institutions, museums, galleries, and archives" (Google, 2015a), GA&C now also hosts entities that are not exactly cultural institutions, including national and local tourism agencies such as the Federal Agency for Tourism in Russia, South African Tourism, Tour Nigeria, Quang Binh Tourism Department in Vietnam, as well as the City of Takasaki and City of Gastronomy Niigata in Japan. These agencies may be public or private, but they all aim to promote the local tourist industry, a commercial endeavor, therefore contradicting the platform's own content guidelines that it "should not be used for any commercial activity" (Google, 2018).

The Partner tab on GA&C's About page describes the list of tools and services it provides for institutional partners, including digitization, collection management, online publishing, and The Lab (Google, 2020). Digitization is implemented using Art Camera (a custom-built imaging device that produces high-resolution images and allows advanced zoom functionality), Museum View (a series of portable imaging stations that create Street View-style virtual tours), and traditional tabletop scanners for two-dimensional objects. The collection management tools include a step-by-step tutorial on item management, exhibit curation, publishing options, account management, content translation, with a resource document titled "Connected to Culture" – published on the 2020 International Museum Day in collaboration with the International Council of Museums – that aimed to help organizations create online cultural programs at the beginning of the pandemic (Kobyakova, 2020). Not only are these technologies available to institutional partners on the platform, but GA&C also promotes the adoption of these proprietary tools inside the partner institution's own digital infrastructure. For instance, GA&C encourages partners to use the "in-painting tours" feature (formally named Embed), which allows users to zoom in on an object to see extremely fine details, on their own website as an interactive displaying tool. Finally, The Lab, first unveiled as a physical space in Google's Paris headquarters in December 2013 (Willsher, 2013), is where the GA&C team works with engineers, artists, curators, and creative coders to design new art experiments that increasingly use machine learning and artificial intelligence.

On top of the resources offered to institutional partners, I have recreated the menu structure of the GA&C website below to demonstrate what an average user may encounter when exploring the platform (Figure 1). This menu structure has remained stable (as of April 2024) since the platform update in April 2020, and only the homepage includes regular changes on a daily basis, where featured content – artworks, exhibits, and projects – is presented sometimes in conjunction with (mostly U.S.) holidays and global events, such as Black History Month, Women’s History Month, Valentine’s Day, Pi Day, St. Patrick’s Day, Christmas, and the death of Queen Elizabeth II, just to name a few. In addition to temporary content, the homepage also consistently includes the following sections:

- Today’s top picks: five featured stories, items, games, or videos
- Games: including puzzle, crossword, coloring, trivia, and other audiovisual projects
- Explore in high definition: artworks that allow detailed zooming
- Museum explorer: virtual tours using Street View technologies
- Discover by color: sorting and grouping collection images by color palette

The current version of the GA&C mobile app provides users with access to the same collection content, but it also promotes a growing set of playful experiences and camera-based features using VR, AR, and AI-enabled functions, including the (in)famous Art Selfie feature that matches a selfie provided by the user with a portrait in the GA&C database based on (problematic) visual similarities (Chen, 2018; Shu, 2018). I provide a detailed account of the GA&C app in Chapter 4.

It is important to note that despite the structural updates of the platform over the years, what individual users can do on the platform has not changed significantly and is still rather limited compared to other types of digital platforms. Users do not have to login to their Google account to access the platform, and most content is not personalized based on either user profile or geolocation, except for the Nearby tab that asks for a user’s device location and a small section on the homepage “Recommended for you” showing certain artworks “Because [...] is in your favorites.” When users are not logged into their Google account, this becomes a generic message, “Discover popular artworks and hidden gems from around the world.” Logged in users can add individual objects, stories, projects, and collections to their “favorites” and group their favorited items into galleries. They can share content on social media, but only six options are available:

Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, Email, Tumblr, and Google Classroom. Users can also play games, and an Achievements tab keeps track of their progress and badges (e.g., an Adventurer badge is granted when a user takes a virtual tour using Street View).

Both the website and the mobile app have an Experiments section that redirects users to “Experiments with Google,” a website outside GA&C that showcases a collection of experimental projects created by various Google teams in collaboration with different partners, including artists in residence at The Lab, using Chrome, Android, AI, VR, AR, and other technologies (Google, 2014). Arts & Culture is a subsection of the website that first started in 2016. Early experiments included Curator Table³ and Free Fall,⁴ two interactive data visualization projects used by the Director in a 2016 Ted Talk to promote the then new GA&C platform (TED, 2016). In contrast to these early projects that visually epitomized the platform’s totalizing approach to arts and culture, some of the recent experiments have taken a more playful turn to create gaming or game-like experiences based on cultural elements, including Blob Opera (based on a machine learning model trained on the voices of four opera singers to create opera-like vocal tunes), 3D Pottery (to recreate the look of an original artifact), and Baguette Sprint (a 3D endless running game that celebrates the French baguette receiving UNESCO World Heritage status in late 2022).

Summary

This section provides a brief account of the GA&C initiative’s official origin story, in which it emerged as a side project for some enthusiastic employees who sought to expand the company’s overall mission with existing technologies. The limited number of press releases and interviews about the project failed to paint a complete picture of its early development, especially how the scale of participation and availability of features have expanded over the years, or how the two interchangeably used labels – Art Project and Cultural Institute – eventually converged to become the Google Arts & Culture it is today. Although GA&C does not keep a public record of its own development, researchers and archivists have created and maintained an extensive web archive of how the platform’s presence on the web has changed over the years. I therefore adopt a web

³ See <https://experiments.withgoogle.com/curator-table>.

⁴ See <https://experiments.withgoogle.com/free-fall>.

archival and media archaeological approach to examine this ever-expanding web archive and seek to reconstruct a more complete timeline of GA&C's institutional history.

This section also offers a descriptive account of the platform's features and tools. The recently developed Experiments are particularly worth mentioning in part because they connect GA&C to Google's broader efforts to create, if not exploit and monetize, new technologies. More importantly, these experiments and their underlying technologies were made possible and continue to improve because of the massive amounts of cultural datasets provided by GA&C's partner institutions. If cultural institutions are not paying for the platform, are they the product? On the platform's FAQ, Google claims that it "will not show ads on the website" and "will neither *directly* monetize the content nor charge users a fee to access the content" (Google, 2015, emphasis added). Then, is collecting data about cultural objects and platform users how Google *indirectly* monetizes the initiative? The 2011 *New York Times* article mentioned earlier also included an interview with former director of the Cultural Institute, Steve Crossan, who, stopping short of using the word data, acknowledged that philanthropy and public relations were not the initiative's only goals:

There's certainly an investment logic to this. Having good content on the Web, in open standards, is good for the Web, is good for the users. If you invest in what's good for the Web and the users, that will bear fruit. (Crossan, as cited in Pfanner, 2011)

The ultimate (and ulterior) motive behind the platform, as I demonstrate in Chapter 6, is a recurring point of tension and distrust for many institutional partners. I will return to the topics of datafication and commercialization in a later section, but it is imperative that the investigation of the GA&C platform challenge its purported and preferred rhetoric of access and preservation, focusing instead on the issues of power and control. Considering the intellectual lineage of a universally accessible catalogue of arts and culture, the risks of privatization posed by technology companies controlling otherwise public resources, and the dominance of digital platforms as a sociotechnical force in contemporary society, the following three sections will unpack the GA&C platform from the perspectives of the virtual museum, digital enclosure, and platform governance.

Figure 1. The menu structure of GA&C's current website (as of April 2024).

The History of the Virtual Museum

Whether it is the stated purpose of access, preservation, and democratization, or the unstated function of power, control, and canonization, what Google is trying to achieve in the cultural sector through GA&C is anything but new, at least not on a conceptual level. Throughout the twentieth century, many artists, intellectuals, and museum practitioners have envisioned and experimented with the idea of a universally accessible virtual museum that brings museum collections beyond the institution's physical walls to the wider public. The expanded access was especially predicated upon the transformation of artworks through the ages of mechanical and digital reproduction. In this section, I trace the intellectual underpinnings and institutional experimentations of the virtual museum, highlighting the importance of interactive media technologies in exhibition design and the role of the audiences as active participants rather than passive spectators. Although GA&C implements some aspects of the virtual museum and underscores access and preservation in its mission statement, the reconceptualization of the users as more than passive spectators has yet to be realized on the platform. This section provides the theoretical framework and (art) historical context to understand the aspirations and limitations of GA&C as a contemporary iteration of the virtual museum.

From Domestic Pinacotheca to the Imaginary Museum

Huhtamo (2010) historicized the virtual museum and traced its origins to the early twentieth century, when exhibition design began to emerge as a new medium among the avant-garde artists. The use of emerging technological media by these artists created new radical aesthetic forms (e.g., ready-made, non-narrative film, and photomontage) that were deeply incompatible with established cultural institutions of the time. In searching for new ways of displaying art, Huhtamo argued that many artists sought to expose the ideological roots of the modernist exhibition space and reconfigure the gallery to integrate new media technologies and create “a total environment that envelops the visitors and encourages them into dynamic relationship with the space and all its dimensions and elements” (p. 125). In this immersive new space, artists such as El Lissitzky, Frederick Kiesler, and László Moholy-Nagy deployed different strategies to encourage visitors to move around inside the gallery space and interact with the exhibits. Although dismissed by some critics as “penny arcade without the pennies,” these radical

exhibition practices anticipated a culture of interactivity that used technology “*against* collective consumption typical of mass media and *for* individualized and customized experiences” (p. 127, emphasis in original). For Huhtamo, the reconfiguration of the gallery as a navigable non-linear database, the convergence of different media, and the visitor’s interactive relationship with the exhibits all paved the way for the future virtual museum.

In addition to the integration of media technologies in the gallery space, Huhtamo suggested that the same artists and designers also attempted to facilitate the domestic consumption of art. In particular, Huhtamo noted the increased visuality of the domestic interior as an essential feature of nineteenth-century bourgeois culture, citing the filing cabinet for stereoscopic photographs as the archetypical “database furniture” designed for armchair travelling, with hundreds of images “retrieved from the logically arranged databank only when needed” (pp. 129-130). For Huhtamo, the increased domestic visuality in the early twentieth century was the sociocultural background in which Moholy-Nagy envisioned his pinacotheca in 1925, which inspired Kiesler’s conception of the *Telemuseum* in 1926, a home space with “walls for sensitized panels that would act as receiving surfaces for broadcasted pictures” as well as “built-in shrines for original masterpieces that will be concealed behind walls and revealed occasionally” (Kiesler, 1930, as cited in Huhtamo, 2010, p. 129). All in all, Huhtamo argued that these avant-garde experiments, along with other lesser-known efforts, to introduce interactive art experiences to the home space since the 1920s have long envisioned the contours and characteristics of the virtual museum.

Whether it is Moholy-Nagy’s pinacotheca or Kiesler’s *Telemuseum*, these new configurations for art consumption are predicated upon the reproducibility of the original artworks. Walter Benjamin’s (1936/2019) seminal essay discussed the aesthetic, social, and political implications of art being mass reproduced through mechanical means. What he did not discuss was how the museum would be implicated in this process. In his three-part volume originally published in 1951, André Malraux (1974) conceived his “museums without wall” (or “imaginary museums” as translated from the French title *le musée imaginaire*) and discussed how photographic reproduction had changed both the role of the museum and the way the public engages with reproduced artworks outside the museum space:

[...] in our Museum without Walls, picture, fresco, miniature and stained-glass window seem of one and the same family. For all alike [...] have become “colorplates.” In the process they have lost their properties as *objects*; but, by the same token, they have gained something: the utmost significance as to *style* that they can possibly acquire. (Malraux, 1953/1974, p. 44, emphasis in original)

Malraux’s central argument, echoing and expanding on Benjamin’s idea, is that the process of photographic reproduction deprived objects of their specificity and scale but conferred upon them a common style, a “specious unity” that renders otherwise unconnected objects related when they are reproduced on the same page, allowing new relationships between artworks to be established. The photo album, as Malraux put it, “isolates both to metamorphose [...] and for discovery” (p. 16).

The imposition of a common style and the resulting discovery of new relationships between artworks is what connects the imaginary museum and the virtual museum. For instance, Battro (2010) considered the various forms of virtual museums emerging in the 1990s as “the product of the prodigious evolution” of Malraux’s imaginary museum, focusing particularly on their common capacity for serendipitous discovery (p. 137). Just as the imaginary museum transcends the confines of the museum walls, “the virtual museum has ceased to be a simple reflection of the real one; it has developed a life of its own, no longer satisfied with informing and exhibiting but challenging to action and discovery” (p. 146).

Implementing the Virtual Museum

While avant-garde artists and scholars had established the intellectual foundation for envisioning the virtual museum, it was not until the 1960s when the invention of hypertext finally paved the way for museums to build non-linear data architectures for information management. The use of hypertext for the purpose of information organization was rooted in pioneering ideas such as Ted Nelson’s Project Xanadu in 1960, Vannevar Bush’s hypothetical device Memex in 1945, as well as the Mundaneum as the “city of knowledge” conceived by Paul Otlet and Henri La Fontaine in the early twentieth century (Huhtamo, 2010; Schweibenz, 2019; Perkowitz, 2016). Hypertext-based application programs such as HyperCard allowed the museum to organize and cross-reference collection information in a non-linear fashion and provided museum professionals with access to massive multimedia files with a user-friendly interface (Schweibenz,

2019). As for public access, Huhtamo (2010) mentioned two exhibitions organized by the Japanese telecom company NTT's InterCommunication Center, "The Museum Inside the Telephone Network" in 1991 and "The Museum Inside the Network" in 1995, which allowed users to access the exhibition at home using telephone, fax, and the Internet.

In the early 1990s, stand-alone information kiosks and CD-ROM-based virtual museums became increasingly popular. One of the earliest virtual museum applications was Micro Gallery, introduced at the National Gallery in London in 1991 and later adopted by the National Gallery of Art in Washington, D.C., which allowed visitors to browse individual objects and print a personalized tour guide (Rubinstein, 1992; Ziska, 1999). Huhtamo (2010) also described some of the earliest CD-ROM-based virtual museum applications, including Apple's "Virtual Museum" presented at a computer graphics conference in 1992, demonstrating its Quick Time VR software that allowed users to explore 3D simulations of interactive museum spaces. Importantly, Huhtamo noted that these early commercial CD-ROM products deliberately limited their scope and rarely attempted to recreate (and therefore substitute for a visit to) the actual museum space. Rather, they served as promotional supplements often sold as souvenirs in museum shops or bookstores and "did little to question the legitimacy of the traditional museum institution" (p. 122). Eventually, as the emergence of the Internet allowed museums to build their own websites that fulfil the same informational and promotional functions with more efficiency and fewer limitations, these CD-ROM experiments, along with the medium itself, gradually became obsolete (Bearman & Trant, 2018).

Computerization and networked communications first became available for the museum community on a smaller scale in the 1960s, but the systems were expensive to build and maintain, limited to text files only, and therefore primarily served institutional functions rather than public needs (Parry, 2007; Williams, 2010; Navarrete, 2014; Marty, 2018). Bearman and Trant (2018) offered a comprehensive account of how museums began to experiment with the Web in the 1990s, including online exhibitions that accompanied on-site shows (e.g., the Smithsonian Institution and MoMA), virtual experiences such as 3D models of artifacts and tours of the museum space (e.g., University of California Museum of Paleontology), community outreach events such as livestreaming (e.g., Exploratorium), social tagging (e.g., Powerhouse

Museum), volunteer cataloging (e.g., Fine Arts Museum of San Francisco), and serious games (e.g., Science Museum of London). Overall, the museum community's early experiments with the web were "programmatically driven, emphasizing exhibitions and events, rather than collections databases and privileging browsing over site-searching" (p. 3222). Museum websites, like CD-ROM-based virtual museums and Web 1.0 technologies in general, cultivated a cyclical relationship with the museums and were intended to complement rather than replace visits to the physical museum (Marty, 2007). In addition to these institutional efforts that sought to establish a virtual extension of the physical museum, individual enthusiasts also created many prototypical virtual museum projects featuring images from multiple collections, such as WebLouvre (created by French student Nicolas Pioch in 1994 and later renamed as WebMuseum as per the request of the Louvre Museum) and Artchive (created by virtual curator Mark Harden in 1998 as a mix of collection images and art history resources).

Schweibenz (2019) described how the term "virtual museum" came to be established in the museum studies discourse through conference presentations and publications since the 1990s. Because of the term's eclectic disciplinary origins, however, there was never a commonly accepted definition. Instead, the meaning of the term virtual museum "remains under practical construction" (Besser et al., 2004, p. 21, as cited in Schweibenz, 2019), and it referred to "almost any kind of collection of material (supposedly of 'historical' or at least 'cultural' value) put on general display on the Internet" (Huhtamo, 2010, p. 121). The phrase gained some official recognition in 1996 when Britannica Online added a reference entry for virtual museum, defined (still in 2024) as:

[...] a collection of digitally recorded images, sound files, text documents, and other data of historical, scientific, or cultural interest that are accessed through electronic media. A virtual museum does not house actual objects and therefore lacks the permanence and unique qualities of a museum in the institutional definition of the term. (Britannica, 2017)

Andrews and Schweibenz (1998) provided a similar but more nuanced working definition:

[...] the virtual museum is a logically related collection of elements composed in a variety of media, and, because of its capacity to provide connectedness and various points of access, lends itself to transcending traditional methods of communicating with the user; it has no real place or space, and dissemination of its contents is theoretically unbounded. (p. 24)

Schweibenz (2004) unpacked this definition and identified different types of virtual museums emerging in the early 2000s, including *brochure museum* with a museum's basic information, *content museum* presenting a museum's collections online, *learning museum* that focused on contexts instead of objects and provided additional educational resources, and finally *virtual museum* that not only showcased a museum's digital collections but also linked to the collections of other institutions. While this typology seems to present a steady progression of the various forms of the virtual museum, Bearman and Trant (2018) argued that the virtual museum did not evolve in a linear fashion, but rather started as a highly experimental space featuring both online exhibitions and educational interactives, and only added basic brochure information later when the Internet became more readily available among the public.

GA&C as Virtual Museum

To some extent, GA&C is a combination of Schweibenz's brochure museum, content museum, learning museum, and virtual museum all at once. Like Malraux's imaginary museum, GA&C also produces a similar stylistic unity that, thanks in part to the uniform design language and interface architecture, connects otherwise unrelated objects and therefore allows new relationships between artworks to be established. This is especially the case with interactive experiments. For example, Curator Table and Free Fall (see footnotes 3 and 4) demonstrate this logic by depriving the digital objects of their scale and specificity and presenting them in a totalizing fashion. Another experiment launched in 2016, X Degrees of Separation,⁵ pushed this logic even further and literalized the imaginary museum's capacity for serendipitous discovery. This experiment uses machine learning algorithms to create a visual pathway between two works chosen by the user through a chain of visually similar images (Figure 2). The description of the experiment sounds eerily familiar to the promises of Malraux's imaginary museum:

This network of connected artworks allows X Degrees of Separation to take us on the scenic route where serendipity is waiting at every step: surprising connections, masterful works by unknown artists or the hidden beauty of mundane objects. (Klingemann & Doury, 2016)

⁵ See <https://experiments.withgoogle.com/x-degrees-of-separation>.

Figure 2. The result page of X Degrees of Separation.⁶

In the meantime, the definitions of the virtual museum, the museum sector's experiments with the Web in the 1990s, and even the exhibition design philosophy of the avant-garde artists all foregrounded the use of interactive media technologies and the role of the audiences as active participants instead of passive spectators. However, other than consuming cultural content in the form of objects, stories, and exhibits, the types of activities GA&C affords its users are limited to adding to favorites, sharing to social media, and playing interactive games. Valtýsson (2020) commented on this limited user maneuverability and the broad cultural politics of participation on GA&C, arguing that it falls short of the promises of the participatory culture mobilizing user-generated content, exemplified by concepts such as *creative audience* and *users-turned-producers* (Castells, 2009), *interactive audience* (Jenkins, 2006), *producers* (Bruns, 2008), and *productive enthusiasts* (Gauntlett, 2011). Instead of transitioning to a *read-write* and *making-and-doing* culture that encourages and supports the active participation of the users, the GA&C platform, Valtýsson argued, is still perpetuating the *read-only* and *sit-back-and-be-told* culture (Lessig, 2008; Gauntlett, 2011) that imagines users as primarily passive spectators. On the GA&C mobile app, this read-only form of cultural consumption doubles down on the logic of passivity by

⁶ Unless otherwise stated, all screenshots in the dissertation were captured on July 29 of 2024.

fully adopting the social media format of infinite scrolling, turning the promised serendipitous discovery into yet another avenue of endlessly streaming culture (Arditi, 2021).

It is important to recognize that GA&C always has elements of interactivity built into the platform, and with the introduction of games in recent years, it may have literally become an art-based “penny arcade without the pennies.” However, user participation in the sense of creative remix championed by scholars mentioned above should not be equated with, or reduced to, mere interactivity facilitated by the use of digital technologies. Responding to the buzz of interactive media art in the 1990s, Sarkis (1993) critiqued the promotional rhetoric surrounding interactivity, arguing that it created an illusion of engagement when the users were simply responding to pre-programmed scenarios, thus perpetuating a passive mode of interaction, or what Sarkis termed “interpassivity.” Furthermore, Witcomb (2006) cautioned against the confusion of interactivity as a pedagogical ideal with the mere equipment of interactives in the exhibition space, advocating instead an understanding of interactivity that foregrounds the process of dialogue. Finally, from a sociopolitical perspective, Barry (1998) attributed the obsession with interactivity in the museum space to the neoliberal reimagining of the citizen as an actively self-governing agent capable of individual choice and market-driven participation. For Barry, interactivity disguised as such often reinforced consumerist behaviors in the cultural sector while promoting a superficial sense of agency rather than fostering genuine democratic participation. This kind of rhetorical slippage that reduces dialogue-based engagement to technologically enabled interactivity, often through the increasing gamification on GA&C, is discussed in Chapter 5.

Summary

This section traces the intellectual origin and institutional history of the virtual museum. Both avant-garde artists in the 1920s and museum practitioners in the 1990s strove to use new media technologies to expand access to museum collections beyond the institutional walls and communicate with the wider public in their home space. From the reconfiguration of the gallery space as a navigable database, the convergence of multiple media, to the user’s interactive relationship with the exhibits, these practices not only envision the historical contours of the virtual museum throughout the twentieth century but also provide the theoretical framework and historical context to understand the aspirations and limitations of GA&C as a contemporary

incarnation of the virtual museum. As a private initiative, however, GA&C's intellectual lineage is often overshadowed by the role it plays in the privatization of the cultural sector. The next section focuses on the rise of networked memory institutions, especially how they have facilitated the processes of digital convergence, datafication, and ultimately the digital enclosure of the cultural commons.

From Digital Convergence to Digital Enclosure

Despite the grand vision of avant-garde artists in the 1920s and the novel experiments of museum practitioners in the 1990s, the capacity for serendipitous discovery enabled by digital platforms such as GA&C ultimately depends on the continuing collection of data, both from individual users and institutional partners, in exchange for its “free” services. In the meantime, even the most fervent advocates of the participatory culture have come to acknowledge the exploitive nature of how platforms engage with the users (Jenkins, 2009), a process similarly based on the generation, collection, and monetization of massive behavioral data. In other words, the rhetoric of democratizing access in GA&C's mission statements belies the invisible yet incessant processes of datafication, a broader economic and ideological trend that encloses traditional memory institutions inside new forms of economic relationships and cultural infrastructures controlled by powerful corporations. In this section, I interrogate the privatization of the cultural sector through the notion of networked memory institutions, beginning with the institutional background of digital convergence and then focusing on the corporate enclosure of the digital commons as well as the issue of datafication.

Digital Convergence in Memory Institutions

The definitions of the virtual museum outlined in the previous section emphasize the absence of object materiality and institutional permanence. However, other museum scholars have attempted to reconcile the digital and the virtual with the material and the real. Müller (2002) considered the dichotomy between real and virtual to be misleading, oversimplifying the multiplicity of meanings bestowed upon objects. Insofar as artifacts tell a story within the curatorial and architectural framework of the museum display, virtuality remains a “fundamental exhibiting practice” that offers another frame of reference that contextualizes objects through

narratives and connections (p. 21). Similarly, Parry (2007) underlined the museum's informational nature and coined the term *e-tangible* to characterize objects that are created, altered, and managed through the intervention of a computer. For Parry, museums have always performed the functions of computers, and the notions of digitality and virtuality only served to synchronize with "existing curatorial discourses that had valued information, liminality and mimesis" (p. 81). Likewise, Geismar (2018) proposed an alternative trajectory of materiality that reconciles the digital with the analogue, information with material, and knowledge with form, considering the digital to simply be "the latest in a string of interpretive and imaging technologies devised to copy, distribute and presence [*sic*] collections" (p. 106). Pushing the conceptual boundaries even further, Dziekan and Proctor (2019) invoked the concept of the *post-digital* to suggest the convergence between spatial practices and digital mediation, in which digitality has become a normative condition of human existence (see also Parry, 2013).

While these scholars considered the ontological and philosophical implications of digitality on museum objects, memory institutions at large, along with the social functions they fulfill, have also undergone significant changes because of new powerful entities in the digital realm. Pessach (2008) defined memory institutions as "social entities that select, document, contextualize, preserve, index, and thus canonize elements of humanity's culture, historical narratives, individual, and collective memories" (p. 73). Considering LAM institutions (libraries, archives, and museums) as paradigmatic examples of *traditional* memory institutions, Pessach observed that new types of collaborative platforms for the production and distribution of cultural works (e.g., content-sharing infrastructures, social networking sites, digital images agencies, and online music stores) perform a "derivative ancillary function of [...] constructing and preserving cultural representations of social remembering" and thus serve a de facto function as *networked* memory institutions (p. 106). For Pessach (writing before the launch of GA&C), prominent examples of networked memory institutions included Getty Images (a commercial supplier of stock photographs, videos, and music), iTunes Music Store and Rhapsody (a music streaming service that later became Napster), and the Google Books project. As media companies became increasingly involved in collective social remembering, "[t]he power to remember, as well as the

power to forget, are thus gradually being concentrated in clusters of commercial enterprises with very particular interests, beliefs, ideologies, and preferences” (p. 74).

Not only does the term *networked memory institution* foreground the convergence between spatial practices (i.e., museums) and digital mediation (i.e., platforms), but it also signals the functional and organizational integration – a digital convergence – between different types of memory institutions in the past three decades. Rayward (1998) argued that the emergence of an electronic information system would “require a major redefinition and integration of the role of archives, museums and research libraries” (p. 207). Likewise, Schweibenz (2004) argued that the trends of digitization and increased public access would “blur the differences between cultural heritage institutions, and in the long run these institutions will merge into one memory institution” (p. 3). For those working in the cultural sector, Marty (2014) emphasized the importance for “cultural heritage information professionals to transcend the traditional boundaries between libraries, archives, and museums to meet information needs in the digital age” (p. 613). More recently, Hvenegaard Rasmussen et al. (2022) discussed a similar convergence among LAM institutions in the Scandinavian context, highlighting their common intellectual ancestry, cultural policy goals, new user-driven institutional missions, structural proximity inside the government administration, collaboration across different LAM institutions, and shared cultural imperatives and professional practices. However, focusing on Australia and New Zealand, Robinson (2018) cautioned against the danger of administrative convergence in museums at the expense of effective interpretive practices, which may end up limiting public access to the museum collection. Regardless of the benefits or dangers, the overall trend of digital convergence among cultural institutions serves as the backdrop against which different types of memory institutions began to use or collaborate with digital platforms.

Enclosure of the Cultural Commons

Against the institutional backdrop of digital convergence, many traditional memory institutions have increasingly integrated their operations with private platform companies (i.e., networked memory institutions) actively involved in the cultural sector. As a consequence, civic and political institutions have partly relegated the role of constructing and preserving cultural

memories to commercial forces, with powerful corporations now relentlessly pursuing the privatization of otherwise public cultural resources.

Pessach (2008) argued that the transformation from preserving tangible cultural artifacts to distributing digital cultural information has resulted in a gradual privatization of traditional memory institutions. In this process, copyright laws play an instrumental role, especially in the U.S., by commodifying the inputs and outputs of networked memory institutions, “transforming the cultural DNA” of traditional memory institutions,” and making them more inclined to adopt “proprietary restrictive policies toward third parties” (p. 97). For Pessach, this transformation is achieved through the combination of coercion and evolution: *coercion* refers to the prevalence of intellectual property laws, contractual obligations, and technological protection measures (e.g., licensing agreements, terms of service, and digital rights management measures) that memory institutions are compelled to follow in networked domains; *evolution* refers to the fact that copyright laws incentivize traditional memory institutions to voluntarily implement proprietary practices, creating new *evolutionary dynamics* that make public-oriented institutions behave like commercial entities. As a result, networked memory institutions have created or leveraged external legal pressures and internal operational dynamics that facilitate the gradual privatization of traditional memory institutions.

Regarding these evolutionary dynamics, Pessach discussed several examples, including Smithsonian Networks (a collaboration between the Smithsonian Institution and a commercial cable company to develop television programming using the Smithsonian’s collections), ARTstor (a non-profit initiative that provides digital images for educational and scholarly use), and again, the Google Books project. According to Pessach, what these initiatives had in common was the adoption of proprietary practices on the part of public institutions, imposed and enforced by their commercial partners. For example, the Smithsonian was obliged to limit access to its collections by other film creators interested in using these materials; Google’s library partners must prevent users from downloading the digitized books and other search engines from automatedly scanning these digitized copies; and by limiting the use of its image collections exclusively to non-profit institutional users, ARTstor was “a paradigmatic example for a public-oriented not-for-profit

institution that implements licensing schemes and technological protection measures as part of its networked presence” (p. 103).

If the privatization of memory institutions signals a shift from political and civic spheres to commercial forces in the construction of cultural memories, it also underscores the peril inflicted on the cultural commons by corporate forces relentlessly attempting to enclose a growing share of supposedly public resources. Historically, the commons referred to communal fields and arable lands that, starting in twelfth-century England, gradually became consolidated into privately owned farm properties through the process of enclosure (Wordie, 1983). Scholarly interest in the commons saw an increase since the 1980s, especially following Ostrom’s (1990) seminal work refuting Hardin’s (1968) essay “The Tragedy of the Commons,” demonstrating that properly governed commons can function as economic institutions that provide sustainable and effective alternatives to market-centered and state-oriented approaches to manage natural and cultural resources. In the mid-1990s, the rise of the Internet created new virtual communities and online communications in cyberspace, and the commons as a conceptual framework helped legal, economic, and information scholars (e.g., Boyle, 2008; Lessig, 2001) make sense of newly developed social dilemmas, as new technologies gradually captured and enclosed resources that were previously unowned and unprotected (Hess & Ostrom, 2007). Bollier and Helfrich (2012) elevated the idea of commons to something akin to a political ideology beyond the symbiotic duopoly of market and state, as “a paradigm that embodies its own logic and patterns of behavior, functioning as a different kind of operating system for society” (p. 2).

Derived from this academic discourse were new concepts such as information commons, knowledge commons, digital commons, and cultural commons (Christen, 2012), conceived in different contexts but all intended to address what Boyle (2003) considered to be the second enclosure movement targeting “the intangible commons of the mind” (p. 37). Recently, Dulong de Rosnay and Stalder (2020) defined digital commons as holistic social institutions that govern the (re)production of data, information, culture, and knowledge as shared resources, and highlighted the role of cultural institutions in preserving, digitizing, and disseminating public domain works without imposing excessive legal, economic, or technical restrictions to public access and reuse. Scholars examining the Google Books project have made explicit references to the erosion of the

information commons by the company's proposed proprietary digital library regime. On top of copyright infringement and anti-competitive practices that eventually doomed the project, Vaidhyanathan (2011) argued that participating libraries prioritized expediency over concerns of image quality, user confidentiality, metadata standards, and long-term preservation, and were therefore "complicit in centralizing and commercializing access to knowledge under a single corporate umbrella" (p. 164). Similarly, Pélissier (2021) examined the emerging cultural heritage commons economy against "the force of capitalism's vague 'proprietarist' tendencies" (p. xii), regarding Google Books and the ensuing legal settlement as a prime example of "the intrusion and domination of private companies in a sector hitherto reserved for non-market cultural institutions" (p. 150). Based on Ostrom's previous work, Pélissier considered the cultural heritage commons to be a manifestation of the knowledge commons, whose social value depends on its dissemination among and use by the public, and it should follow such principles as "shared ownership of cultural resources, social value generated by voluntary contributors, and governance oriented towards the continuous enrichment of cultural resources" (p. 196).

However, this commons-based approach to digital cultural heritage is far from the reality. Building on the work of Boyle (2003), Benkler (2006), and Schiller (2007) that interrogated corporate strategies that construct a restrictive legal regime to control, privatize, and commodify previously non-proprietary information, Andrejevic (2007) proposed the term *digital enclosure* to conceptualize new forms of productivity and monitoring facilitated by ubiquitous interactivity. The resulting *interactive enclosure* is "fantastically productive in terms of its ability to generate, capture, and store personal information" (p. 298) and "facilitates control over resources so as to structure the terms of access" (p. 307).

Ultimately, the enclosure of the cultural commons, just like the historical land enclosure, is about extracting and transfiguring aspects of human life, whether it is arable lands, personal behaviors, or cultural collections, into elements used for the creation of economic value. Underlying the dialectics of digital commons and digital enclosure is the process of *datafication*, the transformation of hitherto unquantified human actions and social phenomena into quantified formats in order to be tabulated and analyzed (Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013; van Dijck, 2014; Mejjias & Couldry, 2019; Zuboff, 2019). Not only is datafication a discernable economic

process, but as van Dijck (2014) noted, it also represents an ideological dimension, a form of *dataism* beneath the normalization of datafication as a new paradigm that betrays “a widespread *belief* in the objective quantification and potential tracking of all kinds of human behavior and sociality” and “*trust* in the (institutional) agents that collect, interpret, and share (meta)data” (p. 198, emphasis in original). The analytical value of the term thus lies in its ability to “name the processes and the frameworks by which a new form of extractivism is unfolding in our times,” especially the processes of value generation and the external infrastructures for collecting, processing, and storing data (Mejias & Couldry, 2019, p. 7).

GA&C as Networked Memory Institution

Exploiting networked communication technologies (like media companies operating in commercial markets) as well as fulfilling the roles of selection, preservation, and canonization (like the cultural institutions hosted on its platform), GA&C is a paradigmatic networked memory institution, providing institutional partners with proprietary technologies and tools that tend to restrict access to cultural content that may otherwise be freely available to the public. For instance, when GA&C encourages partners to use the Embed feature (i.e., in-painting tours) on their own website as an interactive displaying tool, it in effect replaces a downloadable image file in a widely accessible format on a web page with a piece of the company’s proprietary technology that restrictively affords its users nothing but passive viewing and zooming. This is precisely the kind of evolutionary dynamics that, as Pessach argued, incentivize public memory institutions to voluntarily adopt proprietary practices and in so doing transforming their cultural DNA to behave more like commercial entities.

Capturing this symbiotic relationship between access and control, Wilson-Barnao (2017) applied Andrejevic’s notion of digital enclosure in the museum context, arguing that, despite the rhetoric of access promoted by Google, the GA&C platform has transformed the museum from a community space to an advertising resource, bridging “a commercial enclosure with the cultural collections of public institutions, enclosing those institutions within the architecture of networked capitalism” (p. 562). As a result, “the historical, aesthetic and pedagogical attributes of the objects are regarded as less important than stimulating forms of engagement that generate attention and data online that shape users’ attention” (p. 569). Despite this critical commentary

on the invisible process of digital enclosure, Wilson-Barnao considered the platform's visible infrastructure to be "appealingly neutral" and suggested that "Google seems not to express any authority over the environment" (p. 567). On the contrary, I argue that even "appealingly neutral" digital interfaces are normative statements embedded with social logics and cultural norms – about the platform's intended use and the idealized user profile – and are therefore an important part of the digital enclosure process. I will elaborate on the normative nature of digital interfaces in the next section.

Summary

This section examines the rise of networked memory institutions against the background of digital convergence among traditional memory institutions. Controlled by powerful actors in the private sector, these networked memory institutions have leveraged external legal pressures and induced internal operational dynamics that bring about the privatization and commodification of previously non-proprietary cultural information. These new forms of digital enclosure center on the process of datafication, transforming commons-based cultural resources into elements used for the generation of economic value. This is the sociopolitical backdrop that contextualizes and is in turn reinforced by the emergence of private platform such as GA&C. The next section focuses on the wide array of governance mechanisms, from interface design to infrastructural services, employed by digital platforms to exert invisible control while appearing to be "appealingly neutral."

Platforms and Digital Cultural Heritage

The previous two sections examined how GA&C implements some aspects of the virtual museum ideal but falls short of achieving its full participatory potential, as well as how this networked memory institution seeks to privatize and enclose the cultural commons through the process of datafication. Underlying both processes is the rise of the platform as a form of sociotechnical power, realized and reinforced through different governance mechanisms including interface architecture, terms of service, and the distribution of boundary resources. This section focuses on the issue of platform governance as the process of platformization unfolds in the cultural sector in order to interrogate how GA&C facilitates new forms of platform-dependent content creation that restructure the partner institution's own organizational practices.

The Rise of the Platform

The concept of platform has an eclectic intellectual origin. From a historical and political economic perspective, Srnicek (2017) associated the rise of the data-centric form of advanced capitalism – what he called *platform capitalism* – with the decline of the manufacturing industries since the 1970s, which paved the way for the platform to emerge as a new business model better equipped to extract and monetize data. In economics and business studies, Rochet and Tirole (2003) presented a model of platform competition in two- or multi-sided markets with strong network externalities. These markets are multi-sided because they mediate the transactions between two or more groups, and network externalities are commonly referred to as network effects whereby a platform becomes more valuable as the number of users increases. Social media platforms are prototypical multi-sided markets as they facilitate the interaction between users, advertisers, content creators, and sometimes third-party developers. From a software studies perspective, Andreessen (2007) considered the use of the term around mid-2000s as “a swirling vortex of confusion” and asserted, “whenever anyone uses the word ‘platform,’ ask: ‘Can it be programmed?’ [...] If not, it’s not a platform.” Similarly, Baldwin and Woodard (2009) proposed an *architecture of platforms* that centers on the notion of modularity. Bogost and Montfort (2009) addressed some of the common misconceptions about what they called platform studies, which “may emphasize different technical or cultural aspects and draw on different critical and theoretical approaches, but they will be united in being technically rigorous and in deeply investigating computing systems in their interactions with creativity, expression, and culture.”

Commenting on how YouTube adopted the term platform – instead of website, company, service, forum, or community – to characterize itself in several press releases in 2007, Gillespie (2010) provided a comprehensive analysis of the term’s semantic richness:

This more conceptual use of “platform” leans on all of the term’s connotations: *computational*, something to build upon and innovate from; *political*, a place from which to speak and be heard; *figurative*, in that the opportunity is an abstract promise as much as a practical one; and *architectural*, in that YouTube is designed as an open-armed, egalitarian facilitation of expression, not an elitist gatekeeper with normative and technical restrictions. (p. 352, emphasis added)

Not only do these four connotations constitute the politics of platforms, but Gillespie also argued that adopting the term platform was an act of discursive positioning on the part of content intermediaries to tap into the rhetoric of democratization and the enthusiasm for user-generated content, to evade the tensions among different constituencies, and to minimize legal liability for what users distribute on the platform in the eyes of the regulators.

For Gillespie, this discursive work was facilitated by the uptake of the term both in the industry and in common parlance, where, thanks to public figures such as Tim O'Reilly (2005), it became detached from the strict computational meaning. Later, Gillespie (2017) revisited the platform metaphor, "which lent social media services a particular form, highlighted certain features, naturalized certain presumed relations, and set expectations for their use, impact, and responsibility." Importantly, Gillespie highlighted what the metaphor seeks to hide: platforms are intricate and multi-layered structures, inhabited by diverse and sometimes contentious communities, equipped with complex content moderation, and necessitating a massive yet invisible labor force to operate and maintain. Regarding these invisible aspects, Gillespie (2018) offered a book-length treatment of the topic, arguing that content moderation "is not an ancillary aspect of what platforms do. It is essential, constitutional, definitional" (p. 21).

Since the mid-2010s, the platform as a media concept and a business model has extended beyond the provision of networked sociality to broker the transaction of news, housing, transport, gaming, labor, and more, all in the name of sharing or gig economy. Srnicek (2017) discussed several different types of platform companies, including *advertising platform* (e.g., Google and Facebook), *cloud platform* (e.g., Amazon Web Services as a *cloud computing* service), *industrial platform* (e.g., GE and Siemens as traditional manufacturers), *product platform* (e.g., Zipcar and Spotify as subscription-based and goods-as-a-service platforms), and *lean platform* (e.g., Airbnb and Uber as outsourcing-dependent and "assetless" platforms). These categories present a useful typology but are by no means exhaustive or mutually exclusive. Specifically related to cultural institutions, Roued-Cunliffe et al. (2022) identified three types of platforms used for digital communication purposes: *internal* platforms, typically developed in-house or for a specific institution (e.g., a museum website), *external* platforms (e.g., social media platforms or content-sharing sites such as Flickr and Wikipedia), and *cross-institutional*

platforms designed for cultural institutions (e.g., Europeana or national initiatives created for the cultural sector).

While recognizing the diverse disciplinary origins and practical applications of the term, scholars in media and communication studies have reached some common ground on the conceptual definition of and analytical approach to the platform as a social phenomenon. For example, van Dijck (2013) acknowledged the four semantic connotations mentioned by Gillespie (2010), considered platforms as techno-cultural and socioeconomic constructs, analyzed five platforms – Facebook, Twitter, Flickr, YouTube, and Wikipedia – and highlighted the algorithmic basis of platformed sociality increasingly supported by vertical integration and scalable interoperability. Later, van Dijck et al. (2018) proposed an anatomy of the platform:

a platform is fueled by *data*, automated and organized through *algorithms* and *interfaces*, formalized through *ownership* relations driven by *business models*, and governed through *user agreements*. (p. 9, emphasis in original)

This anatomy provides the theoretical and methodological foundation of what the authors called *platform society*, a society in which “social and economic traffic is increasingly channeled by an (overwhelmingly corporate) global online platform ecosystem that is driven by algorithms and fueled by data” (p. 4). This (western) platform ecosystem consists of core infrastructural services operated by U.S.-based technology companies and an array of *sectoral platforms* that seamlessly integrate with the infrastructural core, governed by three primary mechanisms, including datafication, commodification, and selection. I have explained the processes of datafication, commodification, and privatization in the previous section. The mechanism of selection is similar to that of content curation, but the authors emphasized a mutual shaping between users and content, namely, “the ability of platforms to trigger and filter user activity through interfaces and algorithms, while users, through their interaction with these coded environments, influence the online visibility and availability of particular content, services, and people” (pp. 40-41).

Taking into account how the term has been used in software studies, business studies and economics, critical political economy, and cultural studies, Poell et al. (2019) defined platforms as “(re-)programmable digital infrastructures that facilitate and shape personalized interactions

among end-users and complementors, organized through the systematic collection, algorithmic processing, monetization, and circulation of data” (p. 3). In this definition, *complementors* refer to “the independent providers of complementary products to mutual customers” (McIntyre & Srinivasan, 2017, p. 143), which often include content creators, intermediaries, and advertisers (I will discuss cultural institutions as platform complementors in a later section). Furthermore, Poell et al. (2019) also defined *platformization* as “the penetration of the infrastructures, economic processes, and governmental frameworks of platforms in different economic sectors and spheres of life,” and “the reorganization of cultural practices and imaginations around platforms” (pp. 5-6; see also Nieborg & Poell, 2018; Poell et al., 2022; Helmond, 2015). Similar to platform capitalism and platform society, the concept of platformization captures the outsized power of the platform as a technological, economic, and cultural phenomenon, rendering all aspects of contemporary social life increasingly precarious and contingent on its interface architectures and infrastructural operations.

Platform Governance: From Infrastructure to Interface

Whether it is platform capitalism, platform society, or platformization as a process of social and cultural transformation, the dominant power of the platform is realized and reinforced through various governance mechanisms. Platform scholars mentioned above all emphasize the “leanness” of digital platforms in that they typically do not own the products or services provided on the platform. Instead, they position themselves as intermediaries and provide tools and resources for complementors (and sometimes end-users) to create and publish their own content. The focus on the social, material, and political dimensions of infrastructures has led Plantin and Punathambekar (2019) to note an emerging *infrastructural turn* in media and communication studies, influenced by both science and technology studies and cultural anthropology. As platforms acquire the characteristics of infrastructures, Plantin et al. (2018) argued that infrastructures also begin to be built or reorganized on the logic of platforms, leading to the convergence between what they called the *infrastructuralization of platforms* and the *platformization of infrastructures*.

This is the broader disciplinary background in which Poell et al. (2022) borrowed the term *boundary resources* from software development (Ghazawneh & Henfridsson, 2013) to describe

the tools and resources that platforms offer to their complementors and end-users. Defined as “a platform’s infrastructural gateways and associated informational resources that enable and control the computational and institutional interactions with complementors” (Poell et al., 2022, p. 66), these boundary resources may include Software Development Kits (SDKs), Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), documentations, programming languages, community guidelines, and terms of service. Using the game industry, podcast, music and book publishing, social media entertainment, and journalism as case studies, Poell et al. (2022) demonstrated how boundary resources “delineate platform boundaries by codifying and standardizing infrastructural access and integration” and “provide platform companies with decisive mechanisms to govern transactions and interactions” (p. 67). As the platform’s infrastructural services “partly replace the legacy infrastructures of the cultural industries and partly replace public or commons-based infrastructures” (p. 75), the result is the formalization of platform-dependent cultural production.

While infrastructural services such as SDKs and APIs are specialized resources that only developers may encounter, terms of service and community guidelines are more commonly used and (mis)understood means of platform governance that affect every platform user, regardless of whether they have read the texts or simply checked a box willy-nilly. Tan (2018) examined how the terms of service may shed light on the regulation of content generation by social media users from a copyright perspective. Following a thorough analysis of the terms of service of five major platforms – Facebook, Pinterest, YouTube, Twitter, and Wikipedia – Tan argued that the inconsistencies between the terms of service and the copyright regimes may “compromise the effectiveness of [copyright] laws in regulating the content-generative behaviors of social media users” (p. 99). Gillespie (2018) highlighted the differences between terms of service, a legally binding agreement aimed at “indemnifying the company as broadly as possible against any liability for users’ actions,” and community guidelines, typically written in “deliberately plainspoken language [that] lays out the platform’s expectations of what is appropriate and what is not” (p. 46). Gillespie considered community guidelines to be discursive performances, intended primarily as a gesture rather than for arbitration, making legible “the anxieties and assumptions of the platform providers, and the challenges they face as they find themselves becoming curators of (often contentious) public speech” (p. 47). Ultimately, Gillespie argued that

these guidelines matter because they reveal the platform's values and the underlying theories of governance and rights.

Finally, the most visible yet taken-for-granted part of the platform's governance apparatus is its interface architecture. Media and communication scholars have long stressed the material and political aspects of the interface. In a way similar to how Lessig (1999) perceived the legal, technological, and political implications of the code, Manovich (2002) argued that the interface "acts as a code that carries cultural messages" and may "provide its own model of the world, its own logical system, or ideology" (p. 64). Similarly, Galloway (2012) provided a philosophical take on the interface as a site of mediation and highlighted its inherently political and ideological nature, or what he called the *interface effect*. Ash (2015) proposed a *transductive* understanding of the interface to "account for how non-human processes come to have tangibly human effects on the user of that interface" (p. 31). Stanfill (2015) made these goals and effects more explicit, arguing that the design of the web interface is embedded with, reflects, and reinforces social logics and cultural norms. In a Foucauldian sense, Stanfill argued that the power of web interface is necessarily productive, providing users with "the normative or 'correct' or path of least resistance" (p. 1060).

Understanding the interface as a normative statement about the intended use of the web page highlights what user activities are allowed on a particular website. This is exactly what the concept of *affordance* captures. Originating from the field of ecological psychology, the concept was conceived by Gibson (1986) as "what [the environment] *offers* the animal, what it *provides* or *furnishes*, either for good or ill" (p. 127, emphasis in original). Later adopted in design studies and human-computer-interaction, Norman (1988) defined affordances as "the perceived and actual properties of the thing, primarily those fundamental properties that determine just how the thing could possibly be used" (p. 9). Emphasizing the dimension of user perception, Hartson (2003) further divided the term into four categories: cognitive affordances, physical affordances, sensory affordances, and functional affordances to refer to design features that allow users to, respectively, know something, perform a physical action, sense something, and accomplish some goal. In media and communication research, Davis and Chouinard (2016) focused on the diverse subject-artifact relations and proposed six *mechanisms* of affordance – request, demand,

allow, encourage, discourage, and refuse – which take shape through three interconnected *conditions* – perception (i.e., whether users are aware of the affordances), dexterity (i.e., whether users have the know-how to exploit the affordances), and cultural and institutional legitimacy (i.e., whether certain affordances are deemed socially acceptable). “Together, the mechanisms and conditions constitute a dynamic and structurally situated model that addresses *how* artifacts afford, *for whom* and *under what circumstances*” (p. 241, emphasis in original). In order to clarify the ambiguity and confusion between “true” affordances and features of a site or outcomes of an affordance, Evans et al. (2017) proposed several threshold criteria for substantiating the use of the term, highlighting concepts such as anonymity, persistence, and visibility as robust examples for affordance-related terminology. These concepts, and other affordance-based conceptual variations (Bucher & Helmond, 2018), help demonstrate how the platform’s interface design functions as important governance mechanisms to shape user activities “with specific norms and values inscribed in their architectures” (van Dijck et al., 2018, p. 3).

Cultural Institutions as Platform Complementors

As cultural institutions started to establish their presence on social media, content sharing, and aggregation platforms, they became platform complementors and began to integrate the platform’s boundary resources into their content creation. While Poell et al. (2022) demonstrated how the adoption of boundary resources reshaped the practices of platform complementors in different communities – from game developers to podcasters, from music and book publishing to online journalism – traditional memory institutions as platform complementors are faced with unique challenges not least because of their public orientation, organizational complexity, and historically slow adoption of new technologies.

Parry (2007) recounted the sluggish adoption of computers in the museum sector since the 1960s and highlighted a fundamental disconnect and incompatibility between museums as social institutions and computers as an emerging technology, especially how automation and standardization in the 1970s “contorted curatorial practice” by imposing a new epistemological structure and “the tyranny of the classifying code” on the perception and management of museum collections (pp. 49-50). For Parry, this incompatibility was not a historical legacy. Rather, museums in the early twenty-first century seemed to have the same debates about digital

technologies that started back in the late 1960s. The use of external platforms, along with their boundary resources, is one of the current challenges that continues to contort curatorial practices by imposing yet another epistemological structure on museum collections.

Museum scholars have also emphasized the role played by organizational dynamics and internal hierarchies in shaping the adoption and integration of new technologies into content management and curatorial practices (Anderson, 1999; Bautista, 2014; Hvenegaard Rasmussen et al., 2022). Debate about institutional priorities with regard to information management, for instance, “often exposes fundamentally different perspectives within organizations. Established practices reflect and reinforce entrenched beliefs, customs and power relations” (Peacock, 2007, p. 62). Many scholars in science and technology studies use the social construction of technology (SCOT) framework to understand how different social groups can interpret new artifacts – from household appliances to transportation systems – in vastly different ways (Hughes, 2012; Klein & Kleinman, 2002; Kline & Pinch, 1996; Pinch & Bijker, 2012). In this sense, digital platforms may function as what Star and Griesemer (1989) termed “boundary objects,” adaptable enough to meet the specific needs of multiple groups while maintaining a consistent identity across different contexts, therefore playing the role of translation within a heterogeneous organization. Applying the SCOT framework in the museum context, I have elsewhere demonstrated that non-curatorial employees such as educators and researchers may shape how museums understand and pursue open-related practices depending on social values institutionalized by these staff members (Cao, 2024).

Emphasizing the heterogeneity of museum professionals and their social values resonates with previous research on the discourse of new museology, which, as I argued in the Introduction, not only challenged the centrality of curators and highlighted the museum’s information and educational functions (Bennett, 1990; Stam, 1993; Vergo, 1989; Weil, 1999), but also served as the philosophical foundation, along with the impetus of neoliberal cultural policy, for cultural institutions to increasingly use and collaborate with external platforms in order to better address the needs of the broader public. In other words, “for [museum] content to be truly accessible, it needs to be where the users are, embedded in their daily networked lives” (Waibel & Erway,

quoted in Baltussen et al., 2013), and our daily networked lives, as it happens, have long been embedded in various digital platforms.

The platform metaphor, as Gillespie (2017) argued, tends to obscure its intricate and multi-layered structure as well as the diverse and sometimes conflicting communities that inhabit the platform space. As platform complementors, cultural institutions therefore add to the intricacy and potential contention of platform governance, as different internal groups – curators, educators, marketing, and digital teams – may have competing internal priorities and interpret the intended use of the platform in entirely different manners. It is also for this reason that case studies of museum digital initiatives consistently emphasized the importance of communication and collaboration between different internal functional groups within the organization (Cachia, 2014; Petrelli et al., 2016; Pietroni, 2019).

GA&C as Platform Provider

Despite the semantic richness and occasional “swirling vortex of confusion” with respect to the exact characteristics of platforms, this dissertation follows the definitions provided by Poell et al. (2019) and van Dijck et al. (2018) to unpack the governance mechanisms of GA&C and the process of platformization as it unfolds in the cultural sector. As a sectoral platform, GA&C integrates its institutional partners with the company’s core infrastructural services (e.g., Search, Maps, Street View, Experiments) by providing them with a variety of boundary resources (e.g., digitization services, content management systems, content guidelines, and help resources) they can use both on the platform and in their own organizational infrastructures. As the platform’s free but proprietary infrastructural services gradually replace the legacy infrastructures of the cultural sector, the result would be the standardization of cultural heritage reproduction that becomes increasingly platform-dependent.

In the meantime, the platform presents a two-sided market (as it currently does not run ads) mediating the interactions, however limited, between institutional partners and end-users, regulated by the company’s general terms of service and the platform’s contractual agreements. The extremely limited user affordances are both a part and the result of the platform’s interface architectures, which present a normative statement about how the platform is intended to be used. More importantly, GA&C’s interface architectures also reveal the values underlying its

design choices and, to borrow Manovich's (2002) words, Google's "own model of the world, its own logical system, or ideology" (p .64).

However, the question remains how, if at all, GA&C's institutional partners use these tools and resources as intended in their daily operations. For Poell et al. (2019), platformization is as much about the changes in infrastructures, market relations, and governance frameworks as it is about the resulting cultural practices. While analyzing the platform itself may address the former, understanding the changing cultural practices as platformization unfolds within the cultural sector necessitates an empirically grounded approach that takes into account both the ways in which GA&C's institutional partners adopt, negotiate, or resist these boundary resources on the ground, as well as the extent to which these resources have restructured their organizational practices.

Summary

This section describes the rise of the platform as a dominant form of economic structure, social paradigm, discursive positioning, and productive power. Through the process of platformization, digital platforms have penetrated different economic sectors and spheres of life with their infrastructures, economic logic, and governance frameworks. This process and the resulting institutional practices are reinforced through a variety of governance mechanisms, including the distribution of boundary resources, the imposition of community guidelines and terms and service, as well as the creation of an interface architecture that affords users different kinds of activities. With an established tradition of public service, a complex organizational structure, and slow adoption of new technologies in the past, cultural institutions as platform complementors present additional challenges as they adopt the platform's boundary resources. In the next chapter, I outline the data collection and analytical methods I adopted to address the three primary research questions raised at the end of the Introduction.

Chapter 3: Methods

In the previous chapter, I outlined the theoretical framework of the dissertation by unpacking the concepts of virtual museum, digital enclosure, and platform governance. These concepts highlight the tension between the rhetoric of access and the reality of control and situate the Google Arts & Culture platform within broader scholarly discourses about the intersection between cultural institutions and media technologies. In this chapter, I introduce the methodological approaches taken to investigate not only what the platform does but also how its institutional partners use the platform in practice. As a reminder, the research questions of the dissertation are:

- RQ1: How did the initiative evolve from the original Google Art Project into the current iteration of Google Arts & Culture?
- RQ2: How does Google Arts & Culture present cultural content on the platform?
 - RQ2a: What types of curatorial interventions does the platform perform?
 - RQ2b: How does the platform's interface design condition the presentation of individual cultural objects?
- RQ3: How do cultural institutions use Google Arts & Culture?
 - RQ3a: Why did institutions decide (not) to join the platform?
 - RQ3b: How do institutions utilize the platform's tools and resources?
 - RQ3c: How is the use of the platform influenced by its governance mechanisms?

These questions not only address the role played by GA&C but also focus on the practices and responses of its institutional partners, highlighting the importance of investigating the mutual articulation between institutional changes and cultural practices in the process of platformization (Poell et al., 2019), as well as the contingent and contested nature of platform governance (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019). In order to address these research questions, I adopted a mixed-methods approach that combines archival analysis, content analysis, discursive interface analysis, and in-depth interviews.

RQ1: Reconstructing Platform Timeline

RQ1 examines how the platform has positioned and presented itself to the public and its institutional partners as it transitioned from the Art Project to the current iteration of GA&C. This question is a direct response to the platform’s abbreviated, if not mythologized, official origin story and the lack of transparency in how the platform operated in its early years and developed over time. I addressed the questions of self-presentation, both indirectly through the design and functions of the platform’s website and mobile app interfaces, and directly through its mission statements and communications with partner institutions. Specifically, I reconstructed a more nuanced platform timeline using archival analysis based on archived webpages of the platform’s previous iterations, earlier versions of the mobile app, and archived email communications between GA&C and its institutional partners. The findings of these analyses are discussed in Chapter 4.

Archival Analysis

The current GA&C website has undergone extensive changes, both in terms of style and structure, since its initial launch in 2011. While the platform does not have an official timeline of its own development, researchers and archivists have maintained an extensive dataset of how the platform’s web presence has changed over the years using the Wayback Machine, a web archiving tool that allows users to save web pages and view archived versions of websites from the past.⁷ In order to reconstruct a more complete timeline of the platform, I first used the Wayback Machine and Link Grabber (a browser extension that extracts outgoing links on a webpage) to analyze previous versions of the GA&C website, focusing in particular on the structure of the homepage, as well as the positioning of the platform and its mission statements. The rationale for this media archaeological approach is the understanding of the website as an “archived object in a historiographical tradition akin to the biographical” (Rogers, 2013, p. 65). In other words, the biographical information of a website, including its design and structure – internal

⁷ The tool is free to use, but the archiving of web pages is not automatic, and a user has to choose to “save page now” on any given day. The display of the original page layout is not perfect either: most interactive components may not work anymore, and different web elements (e.g., images, text boxes) sometimes overlap on top of one another.

components as well as links to external websites – all reflect both design and organizational considerations that went into the creation of the website.

In addition to the website, GA&C also launched a mobile app in late 2015. Although early versions of the app closely resembled the design principles and content strategies of the website – versions 1.0 of the app simply redirected users to the website – the app has drastically pivoted since 2019, increasingly highlighting camera-based features that are only supported on mobile devices, playful experiences based on a growing collection of games, and most recently an “Inspire” section that mimics the “snap scrolling” style of content navigation now commonly seen on social media platforms. Similar to the website, the app is another important aspect of the platform’s biography, and tracing its changing design and functions is therefore another essential part of reconstructing the platform’s historical timeline. While the Wayback Machine only saves webpages, Google’s own Android mobile operating system allows users to install current or previous versions of an app using APK (Android Package Kit) files, which are available on many APK archiving websites. To access these previous versions, I used the website APKMirror, which offers access to the app’s more than 60 APK files and keeps a record of its release notes as they originally appeared in the app store, detailing changes made to each version of the app.⁸ In addition to comparing the official release notes, I also examined how the app has evolved by installing and using, through an abbreviated walkthrough method (Light et al., 2018), previous versions of the app to understand how it has gradually diverged from the website by highlighting a different set of content and features for the users.

Finally, the GA&C team has been reaching out to partner institutions through emails on a regular basis, calling for participation in upcoming projects, showcasing and promoting new tools and features, as well as recapping seasonal highlights and annual achievements. Not only are these email communications part of the platform’s outreach and engagement efforts, but they also constitute an important aspect of its value propositions in that they directly convey a message to the partners about the platform’s most important functions and how they, according to the platform, may help to achieve their mission statements. A copy of these email records between 2016 and 2023 was provided by one of the cultural institutions that I interviewed (more

⁸ See <https://www.apkmirror.com/apk/google-inc/arts-culture>.

on the interviews in the section about RQ3). Although not all partners received the same emails throughout the years – as coordinators from the GA&C team may have sent out customized messages every now and then – this email archive contains bulk messages intended for all U.S.-based partners, including messages regarding “Year in Review,” “Seasons Greetings,” and updates and reminders about new tools and features. I analyzed these emails to understand how the platform has been trying to stay connected with its institutional partners and how it has presented and positioned the initiative as the platform itself was going through regular changes over the years.

RQ2: Analyzing Content Presentation

RQ2 investigates content presentation on GA&C, including how the platform’s curatorial and editorial interventions have affected the prioritization of select partners and topics on an aggregate level (RQ2a) and how the platform’s interface design conditions content presentation on an individual level (RQ2b). While RQ2a is based on the argument that content curation has always been an essential part of GA&C and presents a deep dive into one particular editorialized section on the platform, RQ2b analyzes the platform’s various affordances and how its interface design shapes the presentation of individual objects and in so doing constructs an idealized user with a particular mode of engagement. I used a combination of qualitative content analysis and discursive interface analysis, supplemented by interviews with the partners and the GA&C Program Manager (see next section on RQ3). These findings are discussed in Chapter 5.

Content Analysis

For RQ2a, I conducted a qualitative content analysis of the “Today’s top picks” (TTP) section on GA&C to highlight the platform’s curatorial and editorial role. As an essential governance mechanism, digital platforms utilize content curation to structure content (in)visibility through interface design and algorithmic sorting. GA&C has always played a curatorial and editorial role since the platform’s inception, from inviting select institutions to become its initial partners to featuring select artworks and artists on the homepage. In recent years, these curatorial interventions have become routinized on the platform with recurring sections such as “Today’s top picks” and “Weekly highlights.”

I chose TTP as the data source for the content analysis for several reasons. First, since its introduction in August 2020, TTP has always been featured on the platform’s homepage. For over two years, it was consistently placed at the top of the homepage and the mobile app, occupying the “first-page real estate” and attracting more user attention than content elsewhere located (Rogers, 2019). The “Weekly highlights” section, by contrast, is placed on the Explore page at a much lower position unless a user opts in to receive weekly newsletter emails. Second, while Weekly highlights include 10 to 12 recommended stories, TTP includes five different stories and is updated almost on a daily basis, providing a more extensive source of data for analysis. Most importantly, I argue that using the words “top” and “pick” is a deliberate design and semantic choice that epitomizes and literalizes the platform’s curatorial functions. Finally, using the Wayback Machine, I was able to trace and collect almost all of the “top picks” between August 2020 and December 2021, whereas the URL for the Weekly highlights page has only been archived infrequently.

Through content analysis of the TTP section, I identified the overall trends of the featured content – including content types (e.g., stories, projects, artworks, or games) frequently featured on the home page and the institutions that created the content (especially their country of origin) – in order to offer a systematic and historical account of the editorial and curatorial role played by the GA&C team.

Discursive Interface Analysis

For RQ2b, I focused on GA&C’s interface architecture, which, as the platform’s most visible governance mechanism, provides users with some actions while prohibiting others, and in so doing conditions the participatory potential of the platform regardless of the content being presented. The process of digital enclosure also depends on what users are allowed to do with cultural resources presented on the platform, which in turn depends not only on the legal code of copyright law but also on the computational code of interface architecture (Lessig, 2006). In other words, GA&C’s interface architecture presents a normative statement about the platform’s intended use, both in relation to the users it serves and the cultural commons it supposedly encloses.

Advancing an understanding of the productive power, in a Foucauldian sense, of the web interface, which reflects and reinforces social logics and cultural norms, Stanfill (2015) proposed what is called *discursive interface analysis* (DIA) to interrogate a web page's intended use, or "the assumptions built into interfaces as the normative or 'correct' or path of least resistance" (p. 1060). Stanfill's analytical framework is based on Hartson's (2003) classification of affordances into four groups: sensory affordances support the operations of cognitive and physical affordances, which in turn serve the realization of functional affordances. For Stanfill, cognitive affordances (e.g., names, labels, and taglines) facilitate information processing and are thus "closely tied to the social act of meaning-making" (p. 1063), while sensory affordances can be analyzed through the visibility, legibility, and audibility of certain web elements.

I adopted DIA to address how GA&C's interface architecture imagines users as passive viewers and encloses cultural resources in the public domain behind the platform's proprietary technologies. For instance, does the interface allow users to download an image for creative reuse, or does it limit the mode of engagement to viewing and sharing? What types of visual or textual information (e.g., icons and labels) does the interface provide to facilitate users' cognitive and meaning-making processes? The DIA approach considers answers to these questions as "productive" because they produce a normative statement about a platform's intended use and therefore the ideal role users should assume accordingly.

Specifically, I used one artwork, *The Milkmaid* (1658) by Dutch painter Johannes Vermeer, as an example to demonstrate how its digital copy is presented on three websites with vastly different interface design: GA&C, Europeana (a digital cultural heritage platform supported by the EU), and Rijksmuseum (where the physical painting is located). I chose *The Milkmaid* in part because the painting has long been in the public domain and is therefore copyright-free. Its European hosting institutions also allow the comparison of its display between two ideologically different platform environments, one supported by a private U.S.-based technology company and the other funded in part by the EU, which openly champions a commons-based approach to preserving and disseminating public cultural resources (Edwards, 2015).

RQ3: Unveiling Platform Use

RQ3 examines the use of the GA&C platform by cultural institutions, including the rationales for joining (or rejecting) the platform (RQ3a), the actual use of the platform's tools and resources (RQ3b), and the influence of the platform's governance mechanisms on this process (RQ3c). Although the platform's governance framework imposes a variety of mechanisms that shape the practices of its institutional partners, these power dynamics are by no means unconditional or uncontested. Institutions and staff members may choose to adopt some of what the platform has to offer while rejecting others. Most importantly, existing studies on GA&C have primarily focused on the platform itself, rather than how, if at all, it is used by partner institutions or how internal dynamics within these institutions may influence the adoption of external tools. I addressed this research gap by offering empirical evidence about the use of the platform through semi-structured, in-depth interviews.

In addition, I also referred to GA&C's content guidelines and partner agreements to provide contextual information about the use of the platform and the overall partnership with cultural institutions. Content guidelines are publicly available on the Help Center. Although partnership agreements signed between GA&C and its institutional partners are typically unavailable to the general public, I obtained three copies of the agreements. One of them was obtained from the University of Texas at Austin (a public institution) through the Texas Public Information Act, which grants the public the right to inspect and obtain copies of government records (Office of the Attorney General, 2018). Two institutions that I interviewed agreed to provide a redacted version of their agreement but wished to remain anonymous for the purpose of this study. The findings of these analyses are discussed in Chapter 6.

Semi-Structured Interviews

As I mentioned in the Introduction, this dissertation examines cultural institutions based in the U.S. due to its unique cultural policy environment in which the private sector has an outsized influence on traditional memory institutions, which would presumably rely more on collaborating with initiatives such as GA&C to fulfill some of its institutional functions. I therefore focused on recruiting individuals from U.S.-based institutions, which are either currently hosted on GA&C or have considered joining the platform, as the potential interviewees. As of August 2023, there are

673 U.S.-based cultural institutions hosted on the platform, each with a landing page showing the number of items they have uploaded and the number of stories they have created.

Four institutions located in the city of Austin were first recruited as part of a pilot interview. Subsequently, I reached out to users of the MCN (Museum Computer Network) Forum and attendees of the MCN 2023 Annual Conference. Dating from 1967, MCN is a U.S.-based non-profit organization aimed at supporting the integration of technology within the museum community, and the MCN annual conference is one of the largest museum technology conferences worldwide attended by both museum practitioners and scholars (Marty & Kim, 2020). In addition, MCN Forum is an online discussion board and email listserv for cultural sector professionals to exchange information on resources, jobs, and events, and engage in discussions about current trends and challenges.⁹ I first posted a recruitment message on MCN Forum and then used the public attendee list of the annual conference to reach out to attendees whose institutions are hosted on GA&C. A total of 13 interviews were scheduled through this recruitment process. Three additional interviews were scheduled after several individuals recommended their counterparts from another institution to share their experience.

A total of 20 interviews were conducted with 26 individuals from 23 cultural institutions between September 2023 and March 2024. Four interviews were group sessions, while three individuals have worked with GA&C at multiple institutions. Three interviews were conducted in person, while the others were conducted remotely on Zoom. The interviews were transcribed and then analyzed with a combination of open and axial coding (Corbin & Strauss, 2015) – using the software ATLAS.ti 24 – to identify recurring themes based on the interviewees’ personal accounts. This iterative coding process was based on the narrative analysis (Riessman, 2008) and thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022) approaches and aims to demonstrate how individuals from the partner institutions experienced, contextualized, and recalled the process of discussing and using the platform internally, as well as to identify overarching patterns that emerge by comparing and contrasting these personal accounts.

These 23 mostly U.S.-based institutions, including the numbers of items and stories they contributed to the platform, are listed in Table 1. The position of individual interviewees was

⁹ See <https://groups.io/g/mcn>.

omitted to ensure their anonymity, but their job titles are primarily related to the institution's use of technologies or work in the digital space, such as chief digital officer, director of technology, curator of digital experience, social media & digital content manager, manager of digital records, and web manager. Several institutions require a special note:

- Royal Ontario Museum (#8) and Münchner Stadtmuseum (Munich City Museum) (#17) are the only two institutions not based in the U.S.
- Harry Ransom Center (#18) and The Mesoamerica Center (#19), both affiliated with the University of Texas at Austin, have considered but ultimately decided not to join the platform.
- Institutions #20 and #21 are currently in the process of establishing a partnership with GA&C and have requested to remain anonymous for the purpose of the study.
- Cultural Heritage Imaging (#22) is a non-profit organization that specializes in creating digital capture and documentation tools and practices for the preservation of cultural and historical heritage.
- Curationist (#23) is a non-profit project of the MHz Foundation that hosts public domain images of works from 13 museums at the moment of the interview.

Individuals from institutions #8, #18, #22, and #23 responded to my recruitment message in the MCN Forum and kindly offered to share their experiences with GA&C. Although these institutions are not the platform's existing partners, they nonetheless offered great insights into the operation and perception of GA&C within the broader cultural sector. Finally, several interviewees facilitated an introduction and then one additional interview with a Program Manager from the Google Arts & Culture team. This interview helped clarify some of the ambiguities and (mis)perceptions about the platform's operations and will be used to address RQ1 and RQ2 as well. A list of all interview questions is included in Appendix A.

Table 1. Interviewed institutions with the number of items and stories.

#	Institution	Objects	Stories
1	The Metropolitan Museum of Art	201,174	39
2	The J. Paul Getty Museum	71,358	52
3	National Gallery of Art	42,488	3
4	Dallas Museum of Art	15,177	3
5	Indianapolis Museum of Art at Newfields	6,056	5
6	Walters Art Museum	1,838	1
7	Harvard Art Museums	1,133	4
8	Royal Ontario Museum (Canada)	763	6
9	Philadelphia Museum of Art	231	0
10	Texas Archive of the Moving Image	204	2
11	Denver Art Museum	171	1
12	Getty Research Institute	150	4
13	Georgia O’Keeffe Museum	92	2
14	Blanton Museum of Art	77	1
15	Voces Oral History Project	71	1
16	Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute	68	4
17	Münchner Stadtmuseum (Germany)	52	1
18	Harry Ransom Center	-	-
19	The Mesoamerica Center	-	-
20	[anonymized]	-	-
21	[anonymized]	-	-
22	Cultural Heritage Imaging	-	-
23	Curationist	-	-

Finally, it is worth noting the degree to which this conveniently and purposively assembled sample represents the overall U.S.-based institutional partners, especially in terms of how actively they make use of the platform. For all 673 U.S.-based institutions, I gathered the numbers of their items and stories and presented a summary plot in Figure 3. The average number of items uploaded is 8,011 (indicated by the × sign), heavily skewed by active partners on the platform, whereas the number of items for the middle %50 of the institutions ranges from 83 (Q1) to 256

(Q3). Similarly, but to a lesser extent, the average number of stories is 5.6 (indicated by the × sign), with the middle 50% ranging from 1 (Q1) to 6 (Q3). Outliers are omitted from Figure 3 since showing the highest story count of 220 would render the remaining data points too closely clustered for the figure to be legible. Figure 4 compares the distribution of the two numbers of the entire population (i.e., 673 institutions, shown in blue) and the sample (i.e., 17 institutions that are currently hosted on the platform, shown in orange). Outliers are included in Figure 4, but the numbers are log-transformed to normalize the distribution and minimize the impact of outliers while maintaining the legibility of the graphs. It is also for this reason that a y-axis is not included. In any case, Figure 4 demonstrates the representativeness of the sample relative to the entire population. Perhaps unsurprisingly, the sampled institutions are skewed towards active users of the platform, contributing more items on average than the population and including some top contributors in terms of uploading items. In the meanwhile, the sample can be seen as a fair representation of the population in terms of how many stories have been created.

Figure 3. The distribution of item (left) and story (right) numbers among U.S.-based institutions. Outliers are excluded from display to increase legibility.

Figure 4. The distribution of item (left) and story (right) numbers for population and sample. Outliers are included, but the numbers are log-transformed to increase legibility.

Chapter 4: Reconstructing Platform Timeline: A Story of Convergence and Divergence

In this chapter, I discuss how the Google Arts & Culture platform has presented itself to both individual users and institutional partners, as it evolved from the original Art Project to its current incarnation as of January 2024 (QR1). This analysis is based on the examination of archived materials from several sources, including webpages of the platform retrieved using the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine, update logs and screenshots of the platform's mobile app obtained by installing its previous versions, as well as email records sent from the platform team to one of the U.S. institutional partners. The analysis is supplemented by interviews conducted with the GA&C Program Manager (PM), who shared some of the rationale for how the platform was designed and implemented, as well as institutional partners, who occasionally made references to features of the platform's previous versions. By reconstructing a more complete timeline and platform biography, this chapter sheds light on the evolution of the GA&C, both aesthetically and functionally, in the past 13 years. In so doing, it also highlights the changing roles the platform claimed to play both for the public and its institutional partners.

Google Cultural Institute? A Story of Convergence

The current GA&C website has changed extensively since the launch of the Google Art Project in 2011. Unless otherwise stated, all dates and screenshots presented in this section are based on the archived pages retrieved using the Wayback Machine.¹⁰ The Art Project website¹¹ has been archived regularly since its launch on February 1 of 2011. The original website included a homepage that listed the 17 initial institutional partners and an FAQ page with a link to the project's YouTube Channel (Figure 5). This minimal web interface received an update on April 3 of 2012, when the initiative announced its first major expansion, now hosting 151 museums from 40 countries and adding new tools and social media integration (Sood, 2012). This update marked an important step-up of the platform's editorial and curatorial role, however rudimentary, as it started

¹⁰ Between December 2015 and April 2020, the platform's About page included a timeline for its development between January 2011 to April 2016. My analysis referenced some of the activities mentioned in this official timeline. Valtýsson (2020) provided a detailed analysis of this timeline.

¹¹ See http://web.archive.org/web/20230000000000*/www.googleartproject.com.

to showcase one artwork and later a “Featured” section on its homepage (Figure 6). In October 2012, another 29 institutions joined the initiative, making the total number of partners reach 180 (Adamczyk, 2012).

As the Art Project continued to grow, the occasionally mentioned Cultural Institute was also expanding. The earliest available Cultural Institute website (archived on March 28 of 2012) consisted of two sections – Home and About (Figure 7) – with links to six different projects: the Art Project, three digitization projects in collaboration with Nelson Mandela Centre of Memory, The Israel Museum in Jerusalem, and Yad Vashem – The World Holocaust Remembrance Center, and two 3D modelling projects using Google Earth technologies in partnership with Paris Center for Architecture and Urbanism and the Maison de l’Histoire de France (a stillborn museum project abandoned in December 2012). Google’s plans for the Cultural Institute in fact grew out of the two pilot projects with The Israel Museum and Yad Vashem, which predated the launch of the Art Project (Pfanner, 2011). At that point, the Art Project and the Cultural Institute were hosted on two different web addresses, and the other five projects were hosted on the respective institutional partners’ own websites, making the Cultural Institute website more of an informational portal and aggregator that directed user attention to its institutional partners, rather than attracting web traffic to the Cultural Institute as a content-hosting platform itself.

Figure 5. Google Art Project homepage (archived February 1, 2011).

Figure 6. Google Art Project homepage (archived April 4, 2012).

Figure 7. Google Cultural Institute homepage (archived March 28, 2012).

This portal configuration began to change on May 31 of 2012, when the Cultural Institute launched the World Wonders Project on its own website, featuring 132 heritage sites from 18 countries using virtual tours, 3D models, and YouTube videos, supplemented with information provided by partner institutions such as UNESCO, World Monuments Fund, and Getty Images, as well as downloadable educational materials for classroom use (Blaschke, 2012). On June 5 of 2013, the previously separate Art Project site was migrated to the Cultural Institute site, becoming one of its permanent and primary sections. Along with the integration came another new interface design that remained stable for over three years until the platform was renamed Google Arts & Culture in 2016. This iteration of the homepage (Figure 8) included three featured projects (Art Project, Historical Moments, and World Wonders), a growing list of other projects shown in the dropdown menu, and other content such as collections (from partner institutions), exhibits (curated by partner institutions), and Gigapixels (individual objects with advanced zoom functions). This integration, unannounced on any official channel, also increased the Cultural Institute's total number of institutional partners to more than 400.

Figure 8. Google Art Project homepage (archived May 31, 2016).

Before Google formally introduced the revamped GA&C on July 19 of 2016, a beta version of the new website¹² had been running for more than a month. In terms of interface design and website functionality, this new edition was very close to GA&C's current form as of June 2024. The revamp also came with a new mobile app (more on the app in the next section), first released on November 30, 2015 (Google, 2015b).

The most recent major update to the platform arrived on April 24 of 2020, when the homepage became visually identical to how the platform appears as of June 2024. With the name change, the platform also began to remove all traces of the Cultural Institute label and streamline its name under the new Google Arts & Culture brand: old URLs of the Art Project and Cultural Institute were redirected to GA&C; information about the Cultural Institute's former presence was removed from the platform, from the About page to the Terms of Service, including the only official timeline of the Cultural Institute for its activities between February 2011 and April 2016; the Cultural Institute's official YouTube channel, verified with a checkmark even to this day, was vacated and content migrated. Finally, to put a visual nail in the Institute's design coffin, GA&C

¹² See http://web.archive.org/web/20160315000000*/www.google.com/culturalinstitute/beta/project/art-project.

debuted a new logo in January 2023, replacing the old design that resembles the façade of a Doric temple with one that is the amalgamation of the letters G, A, and C, stylized with the company logo's prime colors and in the shape of an ampersand (Perrigo, 2023).¹³ The last visual semblance of an physical institute was thus replaced by a constant reminder of the company's corporate brand. Nonetheless, the Cultural Institute's former and current employees continue to use the two names interchangeably on sites such as LinkedIn, and if one stumbles upon the signup page for potential new partners, (for now) the welcome message still says, "Google Cultural Institute – Join Us!" As was later confirmed in the interview with the GA&C PM, the Cultural Institute label is a legacy term that the team no longer uses to describe the initiative. For all intents and purposes, the Google Cultural Institute label serves as a vestige of the Art Project's eclectic origin and an emblem and reminder of the divergent, if not haphazard, nature of Google's early venture into the domain of arts and culture.

The media archaeological exercise presented here uncovers a more nuanced story of the initiative's origin and evolution. The early history of the initiative was itself a process of platformization in that the integration of the Art Project into the Cultural Institute served to centralize the organization and display of institutional collections, aggregating both web traffic and user attention to one totalized destination managed and controlled by one team of the company. Despite the uniform design of the GA&C site today, its short history was full of trials and experiments. Notably, the initial separation of art, historical, and heritage projects with the Cultural Institute was later replaced with a disciplinary and organizational consolidation under the "Arts & Culture" label, something decidedly, if not accidentally, symptomatic of the broader digital convergence among memory institutions at large. This convergence, as I address in Chapter 6, is not without tension and cracks.

Appnography and the Gamification of User Experience¹⁴

¹³ In July 2023, the logo's color palette was again replaced with the most recent black and white design.

¹⁴ The term "appnography" was first coined by Cousineau et al. (2019) and later revisited by Johnson et al. (2023) for the study of dating apps. It highlights three methodological considerations: design, user, and researcher. I borrowed the term to highlight design considerations of the GA&C app, including its technological architecture and temporality, while acknowledging that my analysis does not have an ethnographic element that would otherwise focus on users and researchers.

If the web history of GA&C is a story of convergence, the history of the mobile app painted a picture of gradual divergence, not only from the aesthetics and functions of the website, but also from facilitating institutional partners to entertaining individual users. Before formally launching its own mobile app in 2015, the Cultural Institute had provided free tools and technologies for interested institutions partners to build their own mobile apps (Tansley, 2014). This type of dispersed infrastructural support was soon replaced by a unified mobile access point in late 2015, reversing and redirecting the flow of web traffic and user attention to the platform itself rather than its institutional partners.

Between November 30 of 2015 and March 1 of 2024, a total of 61 versions of the Google Arts & Culture apps have been released with APK files archived and available for download. Between the initial release of version 1.0.1 and version 3.0.9 – released 10 days before the initiative’s rename into Google Arts & Culture on July 19 of 2016 – the app was simply called Arts & Culture. Each release came with an update note, including a What’s New section and an overall Description section for the app. Table 2 lists select versions with new information added to the What’s New section, while Description texts, to which I will return later in this section, are not included due to their extensive length.

Table 2. The official update log of the app. Versions with no new information provided are omitted.

Version	Date	What's New
1.0.1	2015-11-30	Initial version
1.0.6	2016-03-18	Add splash screen.
2.0.5	2016-06-16	New: Save your favorites, plus organize them into Collections for easy viewing and sharing; other bug fixes and improvements.
3.0.9	2016-07-19	New: Improved share dialog.
...		
4.1.2	2016-12-03	Design improvements and bug fixes.
4.2.2	2017-01-17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Localization improvements • Bug fixes
...		
6.0.5	2017-12-13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take a selfie and discover if your portrait is in a museum (Select locations only). • Bug fixes and minor improvements.
6.1.9	2018-03-14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search with your selfie: Now available in Australia, Canada, India, New Zealand and parts of the U.S. Stay tuned as we try to improve and expand.
6.2.0	2018-04-16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add stories and themes to your Favorites. • Search with your selfie: Now available in Australia, Canada, India, New Zealand, Singapore and parts of the U.S. Stay tuned as we try to improve and expand this experiment. • Bug fixes and minor improvements.
6.3.12	2018-06-20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Browse local landmarks in paintings & photos using the Nearby map. • Improvements for TalkBack support • Search with your selfie: Now available in Australia, Canada, India, New Zealand, Singapore and parts of the U.S. Stay tuned as we try to improve and expand this experiment.
6.4.17	2018-08-31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • View paintings in AR: Use augmented reality to see real-size artworks in front of you. • Search with your selfie: Now available in Australia, Brazil, Canada, India, Japan, Korea, New Zealand, Singapore and parts of the U.S. Stay tuned as we try to improve and expand this experiment.
...		
6.4.19	2018-10-03	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art Selfie - A playful way to discover art. Now available globally.
...		
7.0.11	2019-01-23	Dive into an immersive gallery with all of Vermeer's artworks, brought together for the first time
...		
7.5.21	2020-04-01	Art Transfer – Can you recognize the artists behind iconic styles? (Re)discover artworks from famous artists like Frida Kahlo, Keith Haring or Katsushika Hokusai. Tap the camera icon and get inspired by Art Transfer.
...		

Table 2 (continued)

8.0.19	2020-12-02	Art Filter — The most famous pearl earring, a Samurai helmet, an iconic Van Gogh self-portrait and more: try on new filters based on artifacts from museums by tapping the camera icon.
8.1.8	2021-03-30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel the globe with 3 new Pocket Gallery virtual exhibitions. Tap the camera button to get started. • Brushes with the World: The first Pocket Gallery with guided audio narration, taking you around the world through art and sound • Better Together: Explore social gatherings in art through works by Renoir, Manet, Rousseau, and more from the Getty’s collection • From Africa to Japan: Contemporary Japanese and African artworks from the Jean Pigozzi Collection
...		
8.4.8	2021-09-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New style sets in Art Transfer to transform your photos using iconic artworks, from contemporary art to classic portraits • Unlock badge achievements by exploring interactive camera features
...		
9.5.1	2023-01-11	Bring artworks to your home screen with the new Artist of the Day widget. See a new artwork every morning, from an artist born on this day.
9.6.12	2023-05-23	We’ve given our icon a fresh new design.
...		
10.2.3	2023-07-24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We’ve consolidated our navigation bar into three items - ‘Inspire’, ‘Play’ and ‘Explore’. • Design improvements to the ‘Inspire’ feed make it easier to like, share and find related content. • Find our Camera features and other cultural playables in the ‘Play’ tab. • Use the new ‘Explore’ tab to browse our partners’ wide corpus of cultural content through topics such as Fashion, Food and Visual arts.
...		

It was not until version 6.3.12 (released on June 20 of 2018) that the installation and use of the app’s previous editions became possible. The earliest versions (from 1.0.1 to 4.0.3) would simply redirect users to the platform’s website using a browser; when Internet access is disabled, one would instead receive an error message. Versions 4.1.2 to 6.2.0 were presumably built with obsolete technical or security parameters, and the app, rather than redirecting users to the website, would require an update (Figure 9). As screenshots of these earlier versions were not available through other sources, the analysis presented in this section was based on versions 6.3.12 and later. Although the interface structure has changed throughout the versions, all the screenshots used in the following analysis show the same content that was being promoted on the day (July 29 of 2024) these screenshots were captured. Although this analytical approach

was very useful in revealing the app’s previous menu structures, labels, and taglines (i.e., cognitive affordances) and their relative visibility, legibility, and audibility (i.e., sensory affordances), the resulting screenshots sometimes turned out to be anachronistically jarring with some recently added features somehow superimposed onto a previous version of the app’s design framework.

Figure 9. Earlier app versions that cannot be retrieved: 1.0.1 (left), 3.0.9 (middle), 4.1.2 (right).

The earliest available version (6.3.12) of the GA&C app closely resembles the design aesthetics and functional layouts of the initiative’s website, including four main tabs when launched: Home, Explore, Nearby, and Profile (Figure 10). All four tabs, as well as the sidebar menu accessed by tapping the top left corner, include identical sections presented on the website, slightly reformatted in a mobile friendly layout. One of the anachronisms mentioned earlier is the “swipe up” feature in the Explore tab. This snap scrolling style of navigation resembles those commonly used on social media platforms, but this feature was in fact not introduced until much later in version 10.2.3 (released in July 2023). This interface structure featuring four primary tabs remained in place until version 6.5.13 (released on November 28 of 2018).

Figure 10. The earliest version (6.3.12) of the app that can be retrieved.

The mobile app's first major departure from the website was introduced in version 7.0.11 (released on January 23 of 2019), when a camera icon was added to the center of the navigation bar, with subsequent versions making the icon larger and more prominent (version 7.5.21) and stylized with Google's primary colors (version 8.0.16) (Figure 11). This tab gives users direct access to camera-based, XR-enabled features, such as Art Selfie (discover portraits that look like you), Color Palette (find art by using the colors of your photo), Art Projector (see how artworks

look in real size), and Pocket Gallery (wander through immersive galleries and get up close to art). Before the addition of this dedicated tab, users had to either scroll down the homepage or use the search bar to locate one of these features. This addition was probably and understandably in response to the viral popularity of Art Selfie on social media, which, however flawed it may have been, temporarily made the app the most downloaded “free education application” in the Google Play Store (Duino, 2018). In subsequent versions, more camera-based features were added to this section, including Art Transfer (take a photo and transform it with classic artworks), Art Filter (try filters based on artifacts from museums), Pet Portraits, and most recently, the second edition of Art Selfie now enabled by generative AI (Shepherd, 2024). Additionally, a Cast function was added in version 8.0.16 (later removed in version 10.2.3) that allowed users to project an image onto a second screen in the same Internet environment, while a Favorite tab with a heart icon replaced the Profile tab, which never included a customizable user profile, except for one’s Google account, to begin with.

Figure 11. The addition of a new tab for camera-based features: version 7.0.11 (left), 7.5.21 (middle), 8.0.16 (right).

In version 8.0.19 (released on December 2 of 2020), an Achievement section was added to the sidebar menu, which allows users to see the Badges they earn based on the progression of their in-app activities, such as using a specific feature or creating one’s own galleries (Figure 12).

While playful experiences have always been an important part of the app’s camera-based features, adopting ludological terms such as “achievements” and “badges” was a clear, if not precursory, sign of the broader gamification trend soon to be embraced by the platform. This trend became more explicit on June 30 of 2021, when the GA&C website added a Play tab to its homepage navigation bar. Later, version 8.4.8 (released on September 15 of 2021) also came with a reworked navigation bar: the Nearby tab was moved to the sidebar menu, whereas a Play tab with a game controller icon was added (the icon was later changed into a more identifiable controller shape presumably to avoid confusion) (Figure 13).

Figure 12. The addition of an Achievements section: version 8.0.19.

Figure 13. The addition of a dedicated Play tab: version 8.4.8 (left, middle), 9.0.27 (right).

Finally, version 10.2.3 (released on July 24 of 2023) completely revamped the design aesthetics and functional layouts of the app by consolidating the navigation bar into three tabs: Explore, Play, and Inspire (Figure 14). Instead of replicating different sections on the homepage of the website in a mobile-friendly layout, the new Explore tab highlights six pieces of featured content, followed by a series of different art mediums (e.g., visual arts and crafts), topics (e.g., nature, fashion, and food), and ways of browsing (e.g., collections, themes, and Street View). The Play tab includes camera-based features, a growing list of interactive games, and a Lab section that, according to the PM, will gradually replace the Experiments website that is currently not part of the platform. The most radical departure in this current version is perhaps the Inspire tab, which now fully embraces the snap scrolling way of user navigation, jumping from one “post” to the next with full screen display and sometimes ready-to-play videos.

Figure 14. The revamp of the app on July 24 of 2023: version 10.2.3.

Although the complete history of the GA&C mobile app cannot be retrieved due to technical limitations preventing the use of its earliest versions, the app’s discrete version numbers, along with detailed update documentation, make it possible to identify incremental changes that shed light on the larger trend gradually embraced by the app, whereas the updates made to the website often happened on a continuous basis and thus often flew under the radar.

Based on the analysis presented in this section, the evolution of the app between June 2018 and early 2024 can be divided into three phases:

- Versions 1 – 6: creation of the web experience in mobile friendly formats.
- Versions 7 – 9: experimentation with camera-based features and game experiences.
- Versions 10 – present: prioritization of playful experiences.

When asked to confirm whether the highlighting of games and playful experiences was a deliberate strategy, the PM commented:

Yes, definitely! People love interactive experiences. [...] One of the things that we can offer our partners are new ways of interacting with your content and making it fun and exciting and delightful. If we say that we're about education and accessibility, what does that actually mean? Often times people think art is out of their reach, they think it's not for them, they weren't raised going to museums, or whatever it is. But if you approach it in a playful and engaging way, maybe then eventually those people will go see that artwork in the museum themselves. I think "play" is only a good thing in that regard.¹⁵

Therefore, the trend of gamification did not result from the whim of some developers, but rather reflects an intentional effort on the part of the GA&C team to try to engage with the segment of the public that may not be the cultural sector's primary audiences. If the development of the GA&C website is a story of convergence, then the evolution of the app is perhaps one of divergence, not only from the design aesthetics and functional layouts of the website, but also from a focus on the needs of partner institutions to the wants of the platform's individual users. This, as I demonstrate in Chapter 6, turned out to be a point of tension for many institutional partners.

Mission Statements, Greetings, and Updates

The changes noted above reflect the tensions and dilemmas faced by many institutional partners. On the one hand, the platform provides tools for institutions to reach new audiences who may be otherwise uninterested in or even intimidated by arts and culture; on the other hand, the constant introduction of new features made some partners wonder who this platform is truly

¹⁵ Unless otherwise stated, all direct quotes included in the dissertation are based on personal communications with the interviewees, as described in Chapter 3.

intended to serve. The latter became especially poignant when many of these features were not communicated to the partners before they were rolled out. In this section, I address how the platform presented and positioned itself through an evolving mission statement, as well as how the GA&C team communicated with its value to the institutional partners on a regular basis.

GA&C's mission statement, available on the platform's About page, has undergone several iterations over the past 13 years:

- “The Google Cultural Institute helps preserve and promote culture online.” (March 2012 – July 2013)
- “Google has partnered with hundreds of museums, cultural institutions, and archives to host the world’s cultural treasures online. With a team of dedicated Googlers, we are building tools that allow the cultural sector to display more of its diverse heritage online, making it accessible to all.” (July 2013 – April 2015)
- “Founded in 2011, the Google Cultural Institute is a not-for-profit initiative that partners with cultural organizations to bring the world’s cultural heritage online. We build free tools and technologies for the cultural sector to showcase and share its riches, making them more widely accessible to a global audience.”¹⁶ (April 2015 – April 2020)
- “Google Arts & Culture is a non-profit initiative. We work with cultural institutions and artists around the world. Together, our mission is to preserve and bring the world’s art and culture online so it’s accessible to anyone, anywhere.” (April 2020 – May 2022)
- “Google Arts & Culture is a non-commercial initiative. We work with cultural institutions and artists around the world. Together, our mission is to preserve and bring the world’s art and culture online so it’s accessible to anyone, anywhere.”¹⁷ (May 2022 – present, as of June 2024)

What do these changes over time suggest? Not only was the reference to museums and archives replaced by the umbrella term “cultural institutions,” another sign of the trend of digital

¹⁶ The phrase “its riches” was later changed to “their gems.”

¹⁷ On May 18 of 2022 (based on the Wayback Machine), the term “non-profit” was changed to “non-commercial” without any public announcement from Google. The GA&C Program Manager, admitting they do not know the context of the change, speculated that it was to clarify that GA&C is not a 501(c)(3) organization and not a different entity than Google.

convergence, but the current statement has also removed the emphasis on “free tools and technologies.” Yet, despite the changes in terms and emphasis, access and preservation have undoubtedly been the two constantly proclaimed foci of the initiative. However, the issue of preservation was rarely mentioned in the archived web and mobile histories, nor were the tools and features on the platform intended for preservation purposes. In fact, when referring to the mission of GA&C, the PM emphasized education and accessibility on several occasions but never directly mentioned preservation at all. The apparent discrepancy was also mentioned by another interviewee, an imaging expert, who repeatedly and vehemently challenged Google’s alleged commitment to cultural heritage preservation:

As entertainment, as a game, as something for fun, I don’t see anything wrong with it. The concern is that people start presenting things like this as actual examples of preservation, and it’s going to start confusing people. [...] Particularly for small museums, historic sites, underfunded cultural heritage organizations, [Google is] harming and not helping, because they believe that their site is being preserved and documented, and what [Google is] doing is not preservation or documentation by any measure.

The disparity between the mission statement’s claims and the platform’s actual offerings can also be seen in the email communications from the GA&C team to partner institutions. The email records analyzed in this section were generously provided by one institution, which joined the platform in late 2016. The records included 12 emails that spanned from January 2017 to December 2023. The dates and subject lines of these emails are listed in Table 3. Among other things, these emails serve as another reminder of the legacy status of the Google Cultural Institute label. Not only was the GA&C team still addressing itself as Google Cultural Institute in April 2017, but most emails were in fact sent from an address that includes “cipartners” in the local part. The subject line slipup (i.e., “US Bulk”) on December 19 of 2018 more than likely indicated that at least some of these emails were meant only for U.S.-based institutional partners. The GA&C team probably reached out to institutional partners more often than these 12 emails would otherwise indicate, but these emails nonetheless reveal how the initiative positions itself as a whole and conveys its value through direct communications with its institutional partners.

Table 3. The dates and subject lines of all 12 emails shared by one institution.

Date	Subject Line
January 16, 2017	Google Arts & Culture: 2016 Year in Review Newsletter
April 27, 2017	Updates from the Google Cultural Institute
March 1, 2018	Google Arts & Culture: 2017 Year in Review Newsletter
December 19, 2018	US Bulk
June 3, 2019	Artists Grant x Google Arts and Culture
April 21, 2020	Connected to Culture: an update from Google Arts & Culture
March 2, 2021	Google Arts & Culture's update 10 years on
August 26, 2021	Google Arts & Culture Storytelling Update
December 13, 2021	Reminder: Google Arts & Culture legacy exhibit tool deprecation & transition to Story Editor
December 20, 2021	Google Arts & Culture (and the blobs) wish you happy 2022
October 1, 2023	The latest Google Arts & Culture features and news for your cultural organization
December 15, 2023	Season's Greetings from Google Arts & Culture

In terms of content, the 12 emails can be grouped into three categories: greetings (2), reviews and highlights (3), and project and feature updates (7). The greeting emails are simply that, annual greetings and check-ins with little substance, only to perhaps remind the partner institutions of the initiative's existence. For instance, apart from an animated greeting card with a link to the Blob Opera game, the email sent on December 20 of 2021 simply said, "Google Arts & Culture wishes you a happy 2022 in music. Thank you to all our partners in over 80 countries for continuing to partner with us." Similarly, the one sent on December 15 of 2023 said:

Wishing each of our partners around the globe a happy holiday season. Here's to the art that has connected us, the cultures that have enriched us, and the stories that were brought to life. Thank you for your continued collaboration and partnership. Explore the collections from all partners at g.co/arts or via the Android or iOS app.

The three reviews and highlights emails were "Year in Review Newsletter 2016," "Year in Review Newsletter 2017," and "Google Arts & Culture's update 10 years on." The 2016 newsletter included project highlights organized by theme (e.g., Honoring Cultural Contributions and Traditions) and for each quarter; the 2017 review discussed new tools and features added to the platform, events and activities organized by the Lab, and project highlights organized by theme

and for each continent. The 10-year anniversary email¹⁸ provided a much more detailed review of the initiative's first decade. After reiterating the initiative's "20% project" origin story, the email first listed tools and services provided for cultural institutions and highlighted a few featured projects. It then listed the initiative's innovative aspects, including the creation of "playful, educational, and discoverable" cultural experience through games and camera-enabled features, as well as the work by the Lab in "bringing the tech and creative communities together." Finally, the email had a "Beyond Google Arts & Culture" section that talked about the integration of GA&C with Google Search, Google Assistant (virtual voice assistant), and YouTube.

The remaining emails were about updates to specific features (e.g., how to use Pocket Gallery or the new Story Editor) or calls for participation in upcoming projects. The latter is worth mentioning in that it highlights the editorial role played by the platform. For instance, the email sent on April 27 of 2017 mentioned two theme projects:

At the moment, we are preparing two new theme projects - Latino Culture for Hispanic Heritage Month and Inventions & Discoveries.

- Our **Hispanic Heritage Month** project is scheduled to launch in September and will highlight the diverse stories, artworks, images and historic objects that reflect the background, experiences and impact of Latinos in the U.S. June 15th is the content preparation deadline.
- **Inventions & Discoveries** is scheduled for the end of the year; we aim to collaborate with cultural organizations around the world that are on the forefront of science and technology and will share the stories of the world's greatest inventions and discoveries in engaging new ways.

Please let us know by Friday, May 5th, 2017 if you would like to participate in either of the launches, or would like to know more.

Similarly, the inaptly titled "US Bulk" email sent on December 19 of 2018 said:

As you may know, Black History Month is coming up in February. As we do every year, we are looking to refresh our Black History and Culture page. We are wondering if you have any stories you would like to contribute this year from your archive. Let us know if you have anything in mind. It would be great to include you in our efforts!

¹⁸ See also <https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/google-arts-culture-turns-10>.

These calls for participation were also unique in that they were all sent from individual Project Managers instead of the generic “cipartners” email address. As the PM confirmed in the interview, “Oftentimes we’ll reach out to an organization if they’re connected to a project that we’re working on.” Therefore, the two emails shown above were likely targeted communications sent to cultural institutions that the GA&C team considered to be a potential fit for the respective project.

Despite the small number of emails analyzed in this section, these communication records highlight the types of messages the GA&C team conveyed to its partners. These messages included calls for participation in upcoming projects, description and promotion of new tools and features, highlights of previous projects, as well as occasional greetings and check-ins. On the one hand, the messages are consistent with how GA&C positions itself in relation to the institutional partners. According to the PM:

Our goal is to be a tech partner to the cultural ecosystem. That means many different things, and sometimes that means amplification. [...] I would often describe us as a toolbox because I find that’s the easiest way for people to understand what we do. It helps explain that we wear a lot of different hats and support in a lot of different ways.

On the other hand, from deciding the topic of the projects to inviting cultural institutions to participate, the metaphors of “amplification” and “toolbox” belied the editorial and curatorial functions played by the GA&C team, especially those individual Project Managers who reached out to select cultural institutions they considered to be ideal contributors of upcoming projects. For the participating institutions, the condition of visibility, in other words, takes place long before anything concrete is implemented on the platform.

Summary

What exactly does this reconstructed institutional timeline, however piecemeal and incomplete, mean for GA&C as a sociotechnical platform? Based on archival analysis of the platform’s web histories, app histories, and communication histories with its institutional partners, this chapter has demonstrated: 1) the convergence of a variety of initiatives in collaboration with the cultural sector into one unified corporate brand of Google Arts & Culture, as well as the convergence of different types of cultural institutions into one networked environment controlled by an integrated governance regime; 2) the divergence of the GA&C mobile app, and to

some extend the platform itself, from the initial focus on curating an aggregated collection catalogue to the promotion of interactive and playful experiences for individual users; and 3) the purported commitment to facilitating access to and preservation of institutional collections by providing an ever-expanding set of tools and channels of amplification.

The confluence of convergence and divergence, however, sometimes means it is not always clear who the platform is truly intended to serve. When asked about the platform's primary users – institutional partners or individual users – the PM commented:

I would say the challenging thing about this team is that there's a lot of ambiguity. In a sense, it's both. Our partners are a top priority for us, but then obviously users are a priority for us too, not only because we want to provide a great user experience, but also because users are a priority for our partners. That's one of the offerings that we bring. So, really it's both, which I know is not a very satisfactory answer.

This ambiguity partly explains the disparity between the aspiration of the mission statement and the reality of the platform's implementation, which, as I discuss in Chapter 6, was a consistent source of tension and frustration for many partners. Nonetheless, what remains decidedly unambiguous is the editorial and curatorial role played by the GA&C team. By describing what the platform offers as building tools *for* cultural institutions to showcase *their* content, GA&C perfectly embraces the platform metaphor that imagines itself as a neutral facilitator (Gillespie, 2017). Therefore, the mission statements sidestep and overlook the initiative's fundamental role as a cultural mediator since its conception, performing important editorial and curatorial interventions by inviting some institutions (over others) to be its initial partners, featuring some artworks, projects, and institutions (over others) on its front page, and recommending some content (over others) in a variety of curated sections. These interventions, regardless of the platform imaginary as a mere intermediary, negate any claim of neutral facilitation. In the next chapter, I offer a deep dive into the platform's editorial and curatorial functions, the conditioning effect of the interface design on the presentation of individual objects, and the resulting conception of an idealized user profile.

Chapter 5: Dissecting Content Presentation: From Editorial Intervention to Interface Design

In this chapter, I analyze content presentation on the Google Arts & Culture platform (RQ2), including how the platform's editorial and curatorial interventions prioritize certain types of content from certain institutions on an aggregate level (RQ2a) and how its interface regime conditions the presentation of individual objects (RQ2b). This chapter builds upon the argument presented in the previous chapters that content curation – from inviting select cultural institutions to highlighting select project topics – has always been an essential part of the platform's editorial functions, which belies the alleged neutrality often associated with the platform metaphor (Gillespie, 2010, 2017).

This chapter is based on a qualitative content analysis of one particular section on the platform – “Today's top picks” – focusing primarily on content sources and types instead of specifics of the content itself. This chapter also analyzes how the GA&C platform presents and showcases objects contributed by the institutional partners, highlighting the platform's various affordances and examining how its interface design – which affords rather limited user interactions – constructs an idealized user with a particular mode of cultural engagement. I investigate GA&C's platform affordances by comparing how one artwork is being presented in three different platform environments. Throughout the chapter, I use information gathered from the interview with the Program Manager (PM) to contextualize the discussion of these questions.

The Curatorial Function of the Platform

Chapter 4 analyzed the history of the GA&C platform – both the website and the mobile app – and identified evidence underscoring its editorial functions since its origin, from inviting select cultural institutions to participate in the initiative to choosing certain topics as featured projects. While it is often unclear from the platform itself how the GA&C team is internally structured or how some of the content decisions were made behind the scenes, the interview with the PM provided important insights into the initiative's organizational structure and decision-making processes.

In addition to the Director, the GA&C team includes several functional teams. The Content team includes Program Managers who often serve as country/region managers, Coordinators who manage the day-to-day partner relationships on the ground and are typically contractors rather than Google employees, and an editorial team that works (with partner institutions) on content creation. The Engineering team includes Product Managers that focus on specific features or functions of the platform (e.g., games or the mobile app), often in collaboration with Developers and Engineers, who are Google employees but may not work 100% for the Arts & Culture team. There is also a Marketing team in charge of outreach efforts, including managing the initiative's social media accounts. Finally, the Paris-based Lab is a place for the technology and creative communities to work together on solutions for cultural institutions or playful experiences for the users.

In addition to the initial 17 partners that were exclusively invited by Google to join the Art Project, there are currently two ways for cultural institutions to join the platform. Since late 2012 (a date confirmed using the Wayback Machine), non-profit cultural institutions can sign up to become a partner through an application form that collects (increasingly) detailed information about the organization (Google, 2020). When asked what eligibility criteria the GA&C team takes into account when reviewing these applications, the PM responded:

We don't discriminate on who can join the platform. If you are a cultural nonprofit with stories to tell and a collection to share, then you're welcome to join. We *do* only work with not-for-profit institutions, but it's a very visual platform, so a children's museum, for example, is a not-for-profit institution, but they might not be the best fit for the platform because they don't necessarily have images. It's not necessarily that you have to be a collecting institution, but there does need to be some form of images.

Central to our [review] process is that they're nonprofit, that they do have that collection to share, and that they understand this can't be all about sponsors, shouting out, or things like that. We don't want super foul language and offensive things. We try to keep it neutral and educational. For example, there was a museum of cannabis that we're not quite sure about. We reached out to learn more, but they never got back to us.

Additionally, the PM confirmed that they do work with government agencies, including the U.S. Department of State on preservation projects overseas, as well as for-profit galleries if they have a

non-profit branch (e.g., Hauser & Wirth Contemporary & Modern Art Gallery) that does not include merchandise or sponsorship information in their contribution to the platform.

Two content preferences emphasized by the PM are worth mentioning. First, the focus on visual images echoes the experience, sometimes a gradual realization, of several interviewees that their institution, whose collection mostly contains archival documents or amateur footage, may not be the ideal candidate for the platform because they do not necessarily have the kind of images expected by the platform. In other words, despite the convergence of different types of cultural institutions on GA&C, the platform still has a clear and perhaps lingering preference for still images typically found in art museums and cultural heritage sites. Second, despite the claim of neutrality, the PM used the museum of cannabis as an example of “offensive things.” This comment tracks with the play-it-safe curatorial strategy of the platform that usually prioritizes celebratory over provocative content. For example, in the week following the death of former Queen Elizabeth II, GA&C’s entire homepage featured a decidedly glorious portrayal of the queen and the royal family,¹⁹ with no reference whatsoever to all the controversies surrounding the British monarchy that one might expect from a more self-reflective exhibition curated by a history museum.

As each country/region lead (again, usually a PM), along with the coordinators they manage, reviews applications only from within that particular country/region, the amount of time it takes for the GA&C team to review partner applications can vary from country to country. According to the PM, most of the GA&C team is split between London (where the Director is based) and Paris (where the Lab is located), whereas the U.S. satellite team only has one full-time employee and a small team of three coordinators. As a result, it would often take a very long time for a U.S.-based institution to hear back from the GA&C team after submitting an application. While not one of the individuals interviewed for the study, a staff member from one U.S.-based non-profit organization focusing on American history reached out to me and suggested that they had submitted an application but had been waiting for a response for more than eight weeks. When asked about the review process, the PM admitted:

¹⁹ See <https://web.archive.org/web/20220910135231/https://artsandculture.google.com>.

I'm going to be transparent that it's long, and that's because we are such, such, such a small team. I cannot exaggerate the number of projects and competing priorities that we have going on, and unfortunately reviewing new applicants is not always the top priority. If we have a project launch, we need to make sure that that launches smoothly. I would love to have a team member dedicated solely to reviewing the applicants and getting back to them within a few weeks, a few days even! But yes, it can take a long time, especially during the pandemic!²⁰

According to the PM, cultural institutions that actively sought to join the platform are internally referred to as “long-tail partners,” as opposed to “project partners,” which were initially invited by the GA&C team to join the platform because they may be a good fit for a special project that the team is working on.²¹ The PM provided one specific example for an upcoming project:

For example, we are launching in May a project celebrating America's Chinatowns. We are working with the National Trust for Historic Preservation and 15 or 16 local Chinatown organizations on the ground, such as the Museum of Chinese in America and the Center for Asian American Media [CAAM] in San Francisco. We reached out to CAAM because they seem like a great fit. They're not a partner, but they would be an amazing contributor to this Chinatown project. Once you're a partner, you can continue using the platform as little or as much as you want. There's really no expectation on our end.

When asked about the internal decision-making process for coming up with project topics, especially the role played by GA&C team members, the PM continued:

Ultimately, it's our director, but also every country manager, [who are] in constant conversation with our partners, always doing research on what's happening in the [arts and culture] ecosystem and trying to understand what would be relevant and impactful, what is something that would both align with ecosystem priorities and Google priorities, what are ways that we can uniquely be helpful, because we don't do everything.

For example, the National Trust for Historic Preservation was the one who brought this topic to us and said, “We think this is important, gentrification is happening everywhere, these Chinatowns are being lost, and it's an important preservation project to talk about how important they are to immigrant culture and American culture.” We always

²⁰ The platform's FAQ page for institutional partners includes the question, “How quickly could our content become published on the Google Arts & Culture website?” Since as early as 2015, the answer had always been “as quick as 1-2 months,” but it was changed to “as quick as a few months” sometime between July 2021 and January 2022, based on the limited pages archived by the Wayback Machine.

²¹ These special projects are called Themes. As of April 2024, there are 200 themes featured on the platform. See <https://artsandculture.google.com/project>.

have these big projects for heritage months, so it made a lot of sense for us. We're able to also align it with a big cultural moment, Asian-American Heritage month in May.

In that case, a lot of it really comes from conversations with our partners. Or, if I come up with an idea about, say, a retrospective on a certain artist, I talk to someone who's an expert on the artist. If they say this is not that relevant right now, or it's already been done, or people aren't interested, then we'll move on to something else.

In essence, what the PM described is a two-pronged approach to decide the topic of upcoming projects. Institutional partners may reach out to the GA&C team and suggest a topic, or GA&C director and managers may suggest topics and (ideally) discuss them with experts from partner institutions. On the one hand, this decision-making process does demonstrate certain degree of respect for domain expertise, as well as the mechanisms for communication and collaboration between the platform and its complementors when it comes to content creation. It is, apparently and fortunately, not based on what is popular in terms of engagement metrics and could draw the attention of users (and therefore advertisers), as is the case with so many digital platforms. On the other hand, as the interviews with institutional partners confirmed (in the next chapter), this communication process could be uneven, often unilateral, and heavily contingent on the availability and resources of specific coordinators on the ground, as well as personal or professional networks that could help partners deliver their message to the GA&C team's decision makers.

What the PM did not quite clarify was the supposed alignment between "ecosystem priorities" and "Google priorities." On a macro level, it might be useful to mention that, on the official Google blog site, Arts & Culture is listed on the Outreach and Initiatives page, along with 14 other topics such as Digital Wellbeing, Small Business, and Sustainability,²² which can be regarded as some of Google's publicly proclaimed priorities. On the content level, the featured project placed at the top of the Themes page is called "Virtual Museum Day Out," highlighting the Pocket Gallery feature with navigable tours in 3D virtual spaces. Another example would be Play with Google Arts & Culture, which started as just another project (as noted in Chapter 4) and was later promoted as a dedicated section of the platform that features games and playful experiences. Showcasing proprietary technologies developed by the wider company that are

²² See <https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives>.

applied to the arts and culture context, these technology-oriented, as opposed to content-driven, projects also indicate the priorities that the GA&C team has to take into account when deciding the topic of special projects.

Today's Top Picks: The Platform as Content Creator

Despite the rhetoric and self-proclamation of digital platforms as a mere facilitator for individual and institutional users to create and share their own content, the decision-making process on the part of the GA&C team goes beyond mere facilitation. Rather, they actively review partner applications and, more pertinent to the platform's curatorial function, choose topics for upcoming special projects. Although various members of the GA&C team have played an important part in this project development process, they typically do not create any content in a direct or authorial manner. In this section, I examine the "Today's top picks" (TTP) section of the platform to demonstrate the ways in which the GA&C team engages in the content creation process on a much more direct and granular level.

The TTP section was first introduced in August 2020 and consistently placed at the very top of the homepage of the GA&C website for almost two years. As its name suggests, the section is updated on a nearly daily basis and usually includes five title-card style images linked to individual items, stories, projects, games, or embedded YouTube videos. As I argued in the Methods chapter, using such words as "top" and "pick" is a deliberate design and semantic choice by the GA&C team that epitomizes and literalizes the platform's curatorial and editorial functions. The PM confirmed that:

We have an editorial team that builds those pages, and they're not built by an algorithm or anything. I'm not sure exactly what their background is, but they're based in the UK. The team is very close to all the new content that's coming out, like new experiments and games, and they try to showcase a diversity of content, they try to pull stuff from around the world, including natural history, street art, food, dance, things that are not just painting or sculptures. The same goes for other sections on the homepage, like "Today in history" and "Collection of the day."

Without direct access to the decision-making processes of this editorial team, I instead focused on the result of its editorial interventions by analyzing these "top picks" on an aggregate level. For this section, I collected these (mostly) five daily URLs using the Wayback Machine for

the period between August 11 of 2020 to December 31 of 2021, with a total number of 2,485 links.²³ For each linked page, I first collected the information about the content creator, defined as below depending on the content type:

- Items: the collecting or exhibiting institution
- Stories: the institution listed in the byline
- Projects: excluded from analysis due to its collaborative nature
- Games: the GA&C platform itself
- YouTube videos: the channel owner

Then, I gathered information about the country in which each creator, as defined above, is located and tallied the total number both over the entire 17-month period and by month to demonstrate which types of content and creators from which countries have been most frequently promoted on the platform's front page.

The breakdown of the 2,485 pages in terms of content type is as follows (Figure 15): 1,248 stories (blue), 503 games and experiments (red), 387 YouTube videos (green), 168 individual items (brown), 141 projects (yellow), 27 search by color or time (gray), 7 Street Views, and 4 artists.²⁴ The overall dominance of the "story" format suggests that the TTP section has been used by the GA&C's editorial team to highlight the platform's storytelling features, which are online exhibitions that allow, ideally and supposedly, institutional partners to deep dive into particular topics using the platform's various features. The centrality of storytelling is followed by the promotion of engaging content formats such as interactive games, playful experiences, and (short) videos, which has been a rising trend especially on the GA&C mobile app. In contrast, individual items and special projects – the bulk of what partners have contributed – have only occasionally been promoted in the TTP section.

²³ Data from the following dates are missing because no webpages were archived using the Wayback Machine: August 7, August 11, and December 8 of 2021.

²⁴ Promoted on the same day (October 27 of 2021), the four artists were Andy Warhol, Jean-Michel Basquiat, Keith Haring, and Salvador Dalí.

Figure 15. Breakdown of TTP by content type.

It may be useful to mention that for an interested institution to join the platform, it now needs to have at least one story ready to publish before the launch of its landing page. It is unclear when exactly this requirement started, but based on the interviews with the 20 partners, it was more than likely in the late 2010s since institutions that joined the platform in the initial rounds were not required to create any story before the partnership began. This transition from objects to storytelling was confirmed by another interviewee, who recalled their communication with the GA&C team between late 2016 and early 2017:

The wording in the emails started to be about [stories]. They started to use the word “exhibitions,” which they hadn’t at the beginning. The beginning was focused more on objects, and then it transitioned to the idea of exhibitions. The last few emails were mentioning the topic of exhibitions, but nothing was ever explained. You had to extract this information and pay attention to the terminologies.

Regardless of the exact timing, the current minimum requirements to upload 50 items and create one story at the beginning of the partnership corroborates the argument that the platform has

increasingly been intended by the GA&C team to be used as a storytelling tool, among other things.

Who then has been telling the stories featured in the TTP section? The 2,485 picks were authored by 273 creators from 38 countries. First of all, these 273 institutions only accounted for about 10% of the platform's total partners worldwide. Not including GA&C itself, the 10 most frequently featured institutional creators, mostly large and state-funded institutions, were:

- State Darwin Museum (Russia, 1.73%)
- National Park Service (U.S., 1.33%)
- CyArk (U.S., 1.29%)
- NASA (U.S., 1.18%)
- UNESCO (1.10%)
- The National Gallery, London (UK, 0.71%)
- CAAC - The Jean Pigozzi Collection (N/A, 0.63%)
- National Air and Space Museum (U.S., 0.59%)
- Sydney Opera House (Australia, 0.55%)
- Centre Pompidou (France, 0.55%)

More importantly, belying the rhetoric that the GA&C platform is simply providing tools for its institutional partners to use and share their own collections, many stories were in fact created, as the byline indicates, "By Google Arts & Culture" using content uploaded by partner institutions (Figure 16). The complete breakdown of the top creators is shown in Figure 17. Notably, the platform itself directly authored 38% of the content in the TTP section, which included stories and videos, while another 22% (GA&C*) was indirect contribution of the platform in the form of games and experiments enabled by Google's own technologies. The 272 actual institutional partners only accounted for 34% of the featured content. This overwhelming presence of the platform itself – supported by its UK-based editorial team – as an actual and frequent content creator has further demonstrated its essential editorial function, as well as the level of granularity in terms of content creation on a daily basis.

Figure 16. A typical story layout, with title, description, and name of the creator.

Figure 17. Breakdown of TTP by content creator. N/A refers to projects with multiple contributors.

This, however, was not always the case. One interviewee from an institution that joined the original Art Project in 2012 shed some light on the reservation the platform had in terms of creating content on its own:

There was an art historian that was working with them around 2012 and 2013, and she was talking about the idea that they really didn't want to create content on their end because it would blur the line. They wanted to be an aggregate of content from museums around the world. If they started creating content on their own, then that might first of all set a precedent that museums would expect them to create content. Also, they're presenting themselves as this neutral third party that's just presenting things as a platform, and if the platform starts creating content, that gets messy.

This recollection directly referenced the platform metaphor as a mere neutral facilitator. It is unclear for how long the GA&C team, or at least some of its contractors with actual art historical expertise, tried to maintain the platform's aggregator identity, but as the TTP section has demonstrated, the line – if it ever existed at all – between content creator and neutral third-party aggregator has long been eviscerated.

In addition to the overwhelming presence of the platform itself, there has also been a clear regional preference, however unintentional, for content featured in the TTP section. Not including content created by GA&C's editorial team, Figure 18 shows the distribution of creators based on their country of origin. By far, institutions based in the U.S. have been most frequently featured (approximately 24%) as top picks, followed by those from the UK (11%), France (5%), Australia (5%), Russia (5%), Germany (4%), Nigeria (3%), Netherlands (2%), Japan (2%), Italy (2%), Mexico (2%), India (2%), and South Africa (2%). The other 25 countries each accounted for only 1% or less of the TTP section. When asked about the possible over-representation of U.S.-based institutions within TTP, the GA&C PM attributed that to the large number of these U.S. institutions on the platform to begin with:

I would say that reflects the partners on the platform. It's an interesting thing about US tax law, and it's very easy to set up a nonprofit in the US, which has tons and tons of tiny museums, like the Virginia Quilt Museum or the Owls Head Transportation Museum in Maine. [...] Once you're on the platform, then the editorial team will loop you onto the page. So yes, I would say that's reflective of the large number of US partners that we have.

Incidentally, the percentage of U.S.-based institutions on the platform (approximately 25%) is indeed close to their appearances in the TTP section. Nonetheless, rather than everyone simply being “looped onto the page” after joining the platform, about 90% of the partner institutions worldwide were never featured in this section.

More importantly, should the editorial team reflect (and therefore reinforce) such existing over-representation, or should it attempt to proactively recreate some balance in terms of regional representation? When asked this exact question, the PM responded:

I can't comment on their strategy, and they have their own goals. [...] The program managers from other countries work hard at getting more content on the platform, and we know that it's not reflective of the world to have more U.S. partners on the platform. It's also a lift to join the platform, it is work on the partner side of things. It's oftentimes smaller organizations, or maybe there're not as many museums around the world, but it's a question of the program managers trying to help and support and get as much on the platform as possible.

Finally, it might be helpful to examine the distribution by country over the entire 17-month data-collection period. In Figure 19, content created by the editorial team (GA&C) and games developed by Google (GA&C*) are added to the graph in order to better reflect the overall composition of the section. Not only does this longitudinal distribution attest to the persistence and centrality of the platform's editorial function over time, but the very creation of the TTP section, at least within the first 8 months, serves as a curatorial spotlight that showcases the platform's proprietary technologies more than the content provided by its institutional partners. It is also important to note that the eventual dwindling of GA&C* in the graph was by no means a sign of the end of the trend. Rather, it was exactly around that time – on June 30 of 2021, to be precise – when a dedicated “Play” tab was added to the navigation bar on the platform's homepage, thus obviating the promotion of playful experiences among its daily top picks. Indeed, whenever new games or interactive features were introduced by the platform, they would sometimes be featured in the TTP section again, if not being promoted at the top of the homepage with a full-width banner.

Figure 18. Breakdown of TTP by country. N/A refers to projects with multiple contributors.

Figure 19. TTP content distribution by country over time. See Appendix B for all countries featured.

The Platform as an Interface Regime

The previous two sections provided empirical evidence about the editorial and curatorial functions performed by the platform, especially how the program managers are actively involved in the processes of deciding the topics of collaborative projects with the input of institutional partners, as well as how the editorial team utilizes content contributed by institutional partners to create and promote content – stories, videos, and experiences – in one recurring section of the platform’s homepage. In addition to these content creation and curatorial processes, the presentation of cultural content on GA&C, especially individual items, is also conditioned by the design and functional elements of the platform’s interface architecture. I illustrate this process by comparing how one artwork – *The Milkmaid* (1660) by Dutch painter Johannes Vermeer – is displayed on three different websites: GA&C, Rijksmuseum, where the painting is located, and Europeana, an EU-supported digital cultural heritage platform (Figures 20a-c). Again, I use this seventeenth-century painting as an example because it has long been in the public domain and is therefore copyright-free. The two European hosting institutions also provide a counterpart to GA&C in terms of both the interface design and the operating philosophy, especially regarding open access, underlying the respective web environment.

← Google Arts & Culture

Home Explore Play Nearby Favorites 🔍 Sign in

ArtRemix PoemPostcard

Explore related content

RIJKS MUSEUM
Rijksmuseum
Amsterdam, Netherlands

The milkmaid
Johannes Vermeer Around 1660

♡ 🔗 📄

Intent on her task, the kitchen maid pours milk from a jug. The composition radiates a quiet calm, the only movement being the flow of milk into the bowl. Its most exceptional feature is the rendering of light. The tiny dots representing the reflection of light - as in the bread rolls on the table - are typical of Vermeer's technique. This painting is a high point within Vermeer's oeuvre. Of the thirty or so works he produced, four are in the Rijksmuseum. From the collections of J. Dissius (Delft), L. P. de Neufville, H. Muilman, L. van Winter and J. Six (Amsterdam), among others. Purchased with the support of the Vereniging Rembrandt from the heirs of J.H. Six van Vromade, 1908.

Details

Title: The milkmaid
 Creator: Johannes Vermeer
 Creator Death Place: Delft, The Netherlands
 Creator Birth Place: Delft, The Netherlands
 Date Created: Around 1660
 Style: Northern Netherlands School
 Provenance: Purchased from the heirs of Jonkheer P.H. Six van Vromade, Amsterdam, 1908, with support of the Vereniging Rembrandt
 Physical Dimensions: w410 x h455 mm
 Original Title: Het melkmeisje
 Type: Painting

Figure 20a. The Milkmaid on Google Arts & Culture.

The painting 'The Milkmaid' by Johannes Vermeer depicts a woman in a yellow and blue dress pouring milk from a red earthenware jug into a bowl on a table. The table is covered with a blue cloth and holds a basket of bread and other items. The scene is set in a simple, brightly lit room.

i **x** **31,985**

The Milkmaid, Johannes Vermeer, c. 1660
oil on canvas, h 45.5cm x w 41cm [More details](#)

A maidservant pours milk, entirely absorbed in her work. Except for the stream of milk, everything else is still. Vermeer took this simple everyday activity and made it the subject of an impressive painting – the woman stands like a statue in the brightly lit room. Vermeer also had an eye for how light by means of hundreds of colourful dots plays over the surface of objects.

[On display in Gallery of Honour](#) [Visit via the The best of the Rijksmuseum tour](#)

[Visit via the Highlights Gallery of Honour tour](#)

 [Download image](#)

 [Listen to audio fragment \(from the multimedia tour\)](#)

Figure 20b. The Milkmaid on Rijksmuseum.

HOME COLLECTIONS STORIES SHARE YOUR DATA LOG IN / JOIN

1 of 1 • p. 1

Public Domain

 SHARE
[DOWNLOAD](#)

The Milkmaid

A maidservant pours milk, entirely absorbed in her work. Except for the stream of milk, everything else is still. Vermeer took this simple everyday activity and made it the subject of an impressive painting – the woman stands like a statue in the brightly lit room. Vermeer also had an eye for how light by means of hundreds of colourful dots plays over the surface of objects.

This item is provided and maintained by Rijksmuseum

[View on the providing institution's website](#)

Good to know
All metadata

Publisher	Rijksmuseum
Subject	http://iconclass.org/41C222 ; http://iconclass.org/47I22311 ; http://iconclass.org/41C6413 ; http://iconclass.org/41C621 ; http://iconclass.org/41B23 ; http://iconclass.org/41A773
Type of item	painting ; Art of painting
Medium	Purchased with the support of the Vereniging Rembrandt

DISCOVER RELATED COLLECTIONS

 Canvas
 Art of painting

Figure 20c. The Milkmaid on Europeana.

The three web interfaces share some common functions and design elements, such as an image at a central position with the possibility to zoom in, basic information about the artwork with a short narrative introduction, metadata fields about technical details of the artwork and its collecting institution, the option to interact with the image in some ways, and the links to related content hosted on the platform. The presence of web elements like names and labels (i.e., cognitive affordances) and their visibility and legibility (i.e., sensory affordances) facilitate the user's information processing and meaning making processes when they see and interact with the web interface, which allows the user to perform some action (i.e., physical affordances) in order to ultimately fulfill certain goal (i.e., functional affordances), regardless of whether that use is intended by the interface designer or not (Hartson, 2003). That intended use, as Stanfill (2015) argued, both reflects and reinforces social logics and cultural norms built into the design of the web interface.

What, then, is the intended use of the three web interfaces and in what ways, if any, are their embedded logics and norms different from each other? One difference resides in the types of interaction with the image the platform affords users. While all three websites allow the users to view, zoom in, add to favorites, and share the image on social media, the download option is available on the museum website and Europeana but is conspicuously missing on GA&C. For the Rijksmuseum, users with a Rijksstudio account can make a print of a detailed view of the image, download and use the image to create their own product, or order a poster of the work (Figure 21). The downloaded image is in JPEG format with an average resolution of 4,500 by 4,500 pixels. The possibility to download an image is indicated by the download button and the Rijksstudio's scissors icon, both placed at visibly prominent parts of the page that users could easily perceive and understand. Without using phrases such as "copy-right free" or "public domain," the museum simply describes these objects as "digitally accessible, free of charge." Regardless, the option to download an image and the museum's prominent messages to encourage public reuse demonstrates none other than the kind of "read/write" or remix culture championed by scholars such as Lessig and Gauntlett. Thus, the intended use of the website highlights the promotion of creative reuse by the public, which is aligned with the museum's well-established reputation for and commitment to open data and open access (Pekel, 2014).

Figure 21. The download option provided by Rijksmuseum.

The Europeana website also includes a download option – although the image file is about half the resolution of that offered by the Rijksmuseum – along with a Public Domain Mark that explains what users can do with the image (Figure 22). This mark is also linked to Creative Commons (a nonprofit organization providing open licenses and legal tools for creators to share their works with the public), which provides a detailed explanation of the Public Domain Mark and what the public can do with images marked as such. In addition to this formal, if not legalistic, annotation regarding the reuse of the image, the Europeana interface does not suggest or encourage any particular ways of creative reuse in the way the Rijksmuseum does. Therefore, the intended use suggested by this interface design is one that allows for creative reuse, but does so not only to promote user engagement and open access but also to comply with and advocate data standards and rights management practices for the cultural sector, something that is aligned with the mission and established reputation of Europeana as an organization (Capurro & Plets, 2020; Thylstrup, 2019).

Figure 22. The download option provided by Europeana.

By comparison, what does the absence of content downloadability on GA&C reveal about the platform’s intended use and embedded norms? Following the prolonged lawsuits in the early 2010s from publishers and authors about the Google Books project, it is not unreasonable to speculate that the interface was designed to minimize the risk of copyright infringement. As one interviewee who has worked with the GA&C platform at several partner institutions commented:

At that time, the Google Art Project was only accepting works that were out of copyright, even though we had the permission from the rights holders of more contemporary works. I think they were still trying to prove out the platform itself and had decided what areas to not get bogged down in. I think one of those was rights management. [...] They probably learned their lesson from the Google Books project.

Whether or not it was indeed related to the legal quagmire of Google Books, this particular design choice was nonetheless conceived of by Google as a rights protection mechanism. This was outlined in the “Content Hosting Services” section of one particular version of the partner agreement:

2.7 Content Protection. Google will not offer any features designed to enable Users to download Platform Content from the Platform.²⁵

²⁵ An earlier version of the agreement specified that “Google will not offer any features designed to enable Users to download the 3D Models, Cultural Assets, or Gigapixel Images from the Platform.” This language was later changed to “Platform Content” as defined at the beginning of the agreement.

The prohibition of downloading content as a protection measure of the platform was also confirmed by the PM, who also considered it a gesture of reassurance on the part of Google when they initially reached out to cultural institutions at a time when the sector at large was not quite receptive to the idea of presenting their collections online:

There're also image protections in place, so you can't download an image, as I'm sure you've noticed, and if you try to print a page, it prints blank. That was important to the museum partners. I don't think that we would have been able to convince people to put images online, especially 10-15 years ago, when people thought if you put images online, people won't want to come and see them in person! You can never replace an in-person visit to an institution, and that would never be our goal. I think people have stopped thinking that as much.

These content protection measures extend beyond the omission of a download button from the interface or the disabling of webpage printing. The commonly used right-click command (or similar mouse/keyboard operations) to show an extended menu of user actions is also disabled throughout the entire platform. In other words, the physical affordance of performing a right-click is disabled to prevent the fulfillment of functional affordances, such as saving, printing, and inspecting the page. What is allowed then is a narrower set of user actions that prioritizes, again in Lessig's and Gauntlett's terms, read-only over read-write and sit-back-and-be-told over making-and-doing culture. The intended use of the interface therefore prescribes and perpetuates an idealized User with a particular mode of cultural engagement. These are the embedded cultural norms that are reflected and reinforced through the design and implementation of the platform's interface architecture.

The conditioning effect of the interface, however, is not without tension and cracks. As the PM mentioned:

For example, the MET has a huge open access collection. We actually had to change our contract with them because they wanted a download button for that very reason. They encourage people to download these works. If you go to the MET's collection and click on an image, if it's an open access image, you will be able to download it. It's same with the Cleveland Museum of Art, another huge open access proponent, and you can download their images, too.

Incidentally, or rather necessarily, the MET and the Cleveland Museum of Art are currently the second and ninth largest contributors of the platform, with a total of 201,173 and 35,333 uploaded items, respectively. Partly because of their essential contribution to the platform and partly because of their institutional commitment to the principle of open access, these well-known institutional partners have the incentive, resources, and leverage to negotiate a customized partnership agreement so as to remain committed to the idea of open access no matter where their collections are being displayed. In other words, the two institutions' embedded norms of openness, as a rare exception, successfully challenged the interface-induced logic of passive consumption implemented by the GA&C platform (Figure 23).

Figure 23. The download option for public domain images contributed by The MET.

Given the requirement for institutional partners to only contribute copyright-free or copyright-cleared content, why does GA&C not provide a download option for all of the images in the public domain? When asked whether Google should also promote the kind of open culture and participatory ethos advocated by institutions such as the MET, the PM suggested that “it’s a question of scalability in the sense that we don’t have an automated or easy way of knowing what work is in the public domain and technically downloadable.” Setting aside the question of scalability, however, I argue that the GA&C page essentially differs from the two European pages in that it does not in fact present the same kind of reproduction image.

For example, clicking the download button next to *The Milkmaid* on Europeana will initiate the downloading of a digital object, namely, a 4.55 megabyte JPEG file measuring 2,261 by 2,548 pixels at 300 dpi created on December 12 of 2009 with Adobe Photoshop CS3 Windows. This,

undoubtedly, is a digitized image of the painting, with all its digital materialities documented in the file's metadata fields. What makes the "image" on display on GA&C qualitatively different is evidenced in the dynamic URL. Below is a sample URL for a zoomed-in view of *The Milkmaid*, broken down into multiple lines for better legibility:

```
https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/the-milkmaid-johannes-  
vermeer/9AHrwZ3Av6Zhjg?ms=  
%7B%22x%22%3A0.3781161870862447  
%2C%22y%22%3A0.5308660707116841  
%2C%22z%22%3A14  
%2C%22size%22%3A  
%7B%22width%22%3A0.06092789267747345  
%2C%22height%22%3A0.030204376921685656%7D%7D
```

As a user moves the cursor within the frame or zooms in and out, the dynamic URL will change accordingly. More precisely, it is the numeric values following **x**, **y**, **z**, **size**, **width**, and **height** that change based on the zoom level and focal position. In other words, the structure of the dynamic URL reveals not a digital object but some three-dimensional Euclidean space in which the position of a given point can be represented with coordinates (x, y, z). This, decidedly, is not a digitized image of the painting, but a spatialized rendering of the reproduction image, not unlike the zooming techniques used in Google Maps. No digital file is embedded into the interface as an "assemblage of objects," to use Ash's (2015) terms, so there is, in short, simply no image to download. While this may be an "unintentional" and technical side effect of the platform's image protection measures, what the interface ends up showing is not just the copyright-free content per se, but rather one of Google's many proprietary technologies that, perhaps ironically, remixes the content.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that this read-only mode of user engagement has not always been the case, and the initiative in fact encouraged and promoted user-generated content for more than four years until its rebranding into GA&C in 2016. While users can create and share personal galleries now, these are simply image thumbnails grouped together with no additional information allowed. In contrast, the original Art Project and later Cultural Institute websites (see Figure 6 and Figure 8) included a "User Galleries" section in the top navigation bar, which allowed the public to search and browse (supposedly) all user-created galleries. Not only were texts and

videos also allowed back then, essentially turning these user galleries into blogs (Figure 24), but the platform also encouraged users to “try on the role of curator by creating an exhibition” and provided a step-by-step tutorial on how to create these online exhibitions:

First you’ll need an engaging theme. It could be simple (Winter) or more complex and conceptual (Good and Evil). It could be historical (Napoleon), topical (The City) or spiritual (demons). Next you’ll need to determine the order in which the works of art will be displayed. The order might be chronological or according to sub-themes (Good and Evil in the City, Good and Evil in the Country).²⁶

Figure 24. A user-created gallery about the Chiaroscuro technique.

Unfortunately, the archived User Galleries page does not load properly when inspected using the Wayback Machine, so it is unclear how many galleries had been created before Google removed the section from the navigation bar in 2016 and later disabled the addition of texts and videos altogether. Still, searching “google.com/usergallery/” (the common path segment in the URLs of all user-created galleries) would still retrieve at least 26 of such exhibitions, with topics

²⁶ The About page of the Google Cultural Institute included a section on using the Art Project as an education tool. See <https://web.archive.org/web/20131212221032/http://www.google.com/culturalinstitute/about/artproject/education/diy>.

ranging from “Effects of Industrial Revolution to Paintings” and “Mythical Animals as Symbols in Chinese Art” to “Mexican War Daguerreotypes” and “Ukiyo-e in the Edo Period.” Although they are hosted on the GA&C site, searching the title on the platform would yield no matching results. It is unclear why Google discontinued the promotion of such user-generated content or why it even had to disable the addition of interpretative texts in the user gallery format, but the mere existence of a previously open and participatory forum for users to create and share content suggests that the platform must have made a deliberate decision to pivot to the current more restrictive mode of user engagement. In retrospect, the old user gallery looks almost like the prototypical story format later introduced for partner institutions to use. Did GA&C simply “beta test” the tool with user-generated content before formally rolling out the storytelling feature?

Summary

This chapter addresses the ways in which content presentation on Google Arts & Culture is conditioned both directly by the curatorial and editorial functions of the GA&C team and indirectly through the limited affordances of the platform’s interface architecture. On a macro level, the GA&C team’s director and program managers play a consistently central role in deciding the topics for upcoming projects, while its editorial team has been both curating and creating content on a daily basis, promoting content from only a small portion of the institutional partners worldwide while prioritizing the platform’s own interactive experiences whenever needed. On a micro level, the interface design of the individual item page affords a narrow set of user actions. Although originally implemented as a content protection measure and gesture of reassurance to minimize the risk of copyright infringement, the lack of a download option even for images in the public domain (except for two large institutions), ends up prescribing and perpetuating a passive mode of user engagement that falls short of the promises of a participatory remix culture.

Nonetheless, the ability for some institutions to renegotiate the partner agreement and add a download option means not simply the addition of some web elements, but rather an active attempt to circumvent the platform’s proprietary technologies used for displaying images and directly encourage users to engage with their collection. It signals, in other words, a deliberate resistance against the platform’s interface architecture and by extension its governance mechanisms due to the institution’s deeply held belief in and commitment to the principle of open

access. This is just a snippet of a larger picture about how cultural institutions use the platform and adopt, negotiate, or resist its various tools in practice. I discuss these questions with greater detail in the next chapter.

Chapter 6: Unveiling Platform Use: Platform Governance Meets Institutional Practices

In this chapter, I demonstrate how institutional partners use the Google Arts & Culture platform on the ground and address the issue of platform governance (RQ3). As cultural institutions established the partnership with GA&C and adopted its various boundary resources, some of them have adapted their own institutional practices in the same process. Based on the interviews with cultural institutions and the GA&C Program Manager (PM) as well as the analysis of the platform's various governance documents (i.e., partner agreements, terms of service, and content guidelines), I demonstrate the multiple, contingent, and contested nature of platform governance (Katzenbach & Ulbricht, 2019) and foreground the interplay between GA&C's governance mechanisms and the resulting institutional practices (Poell et al., 2019) that range from adoption, negotiation, and resistance.

As noted in the Methods chapter, I conducted 20 semi-structured interviews with staff members from 23 cultural institutions. After analyzing the transcripts, I focused on three broad categories based on the interviewees' personal accounts:

- **Background:** information about the institution, including collections, digital strategies, as well as missions and values (e.g., open access) that are important to its operations, especially in the digital space.
- **Partnership:** the process of establishing the partnership, including the institution's perceived benefits and potential concerns about the initiative, internal decisions before joining the platform, as well as communications with the GA&C team.
- **Platform Use:** the actual use of the platform's tools and features by the institution (e.g., object selection and content creation) as well as the issues that have emerged – technical or political, on the part of the platform or the institution itself – in the process of adopting the platform's various boundary resources.

In the following sections, I present and analyze findings of the interviews based on these categories, with a particular focus on the establishment of the partnership and the use of the platform. By shedding light on how institutional partners responded differently to the opportunities and challenges presented by the GA&C, this chapter highlights why some cultural

institutions decided to participate while others rejected the idea of working with Google, how the platform's governance mechanisms – from interface design to infrastructural services – have facilitated or, more often than not, limited its adoption on a broader scale, and how the partner institutions' internal working dynamics have played an important role in the process.

Why Cultural Institutions Joined Google

The interviewees' initial reactions to the GA&C initiative or in some cases the Art Project were a combination of excitement, intrigue, and to a lesser extent, skepticism. Many interviewees remembered feeling excited about a then rising technology company taking interest in the dissemination of arts and culture at a time when the idea of the digital itself was not necessarily embraced by everyone in the museum community. Others referenced previous attempts – either unsuccessful or limited in scope and reach (e.g., ARTstor or Bridgeman Images) – to create a unified catalogue that is cross-collection and cross-institution. Still others considered the initiative an opportunity, especially for smaller institutions, to share the spotlight usually reserved for world-renowned museums. On the other hand, the skepticism was mainly centered on the long-term viability of the initiative, rather than the mere fact that it was run by a private technology company.

Regardless of Google's reputation within the cultural sector in the early 2010s, the initial reactions of the interviewees did highlight some of the perceived benefits of the partnership with GA&C: the creation of a 1) *unified portal* supported by a 2) *well-resourced and then reputable* technology company that would expand the 3) *reach* of the institution's collections – including accessibility and discoverability – and enrich the 4) *engagement* with audiences through education and entertainment. Not only were these four aspects frequently mentioned by the interviewees, but they also echoed the kind of technological vision that traces back to the ideal of the virtual museum.

In terms of resources offered by the initiative, many interviewees identified specific tools or features of the platform (i.e., boundary resources) that they hoped to use, such as the storytelling and design tools (as opposed to building their own web pages), the ability to embed GA&C content onto the institutional websites, and the navigable indoor spaces created using Street View technologies. In terms of reach and engagement, several interviewees emphasized

that they hoped that the platform would help them reach new and younger audiences who may not be among the typical museum-going demographics. One staff member from the J. Paul Getty Museum explained:

A lot of the reason why we're on Google is the accessibility portion of things and reaching a newer audience, who're interested in art but don't necessarily know a ton about it. We're making it less scholarly and easier to read and digest. The approach we take, and what we hope to write for Google, is about an early high school level. If I get a copy deck back and there's a word that I can't understand, we need to change the word.

Similarly, one staff member from the Georgia O'Keeffe Museum noted:

I think for scholarly use, a researcher is going to use our online collection platform and not this platform. I think we want elementary, middle, and high school students to engage. Maybe this is a window into O'Keeffe as an artist or they will visit the museum someday because they make a fun activity in their classroom.

Overall, the perceived benefits of the partnership with the GA&C initiative boiled down to a certain level of *alignment* – strategic or expedient – between what the platform had to offer and what the institution needed at a particular point in time. Strategically, what the platform had to offer was often in line with the institutional missions or digital strategies of a particular partner. A former staff member of the MET emphasized Google's reputation in the digital and technology space:

I think we also felt that this was really a good opportunity to showcase the kind of work the museum *should* be doing in regard to the digital space. Regardless of whether or not it was going to have any dramatic impact to us, it didn't really cost us anything to do, except our own time and effort. Google, like the MET, carried with it the reputation as a major player in the technology space, so there was an alignment there. [...] If it hadn't been Google, if it had been some fly-by-night organization, we probably never would have done it, but the name carried a lot of weight.

Other institutions aligned their mission with the digital platform as a potential outreach opportunity. For instance, a staff member from the Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute explained:

Our strategic priorities are related to science and technology: innovate and build, explore and protect, but we also have a third strategic priority that is focused on outreach: inspire

and engage. [Google Arts & Culture] very squarely fell within that category, so we really approached it as an opportunity to extend our reach and try out a new platform.

For institutions that had yet to develop a robust digital strategy, the platform often served as a sandbox for them to experiment with new ways of content creation and even shaped how internal functions were structured. As one staff member from the Georgia O’Keeffe Museum recalled:

I think it really started as a marketing tool, but that also fit with our museum in that we didn’t really have an area for digital strategy. We got the initial thing done but then it didn’t go anywhere. When I came on board and we started publishing more collection information, we realized that it was out of date. That’s when I worked with Marketing to pull it over to Digital Experience.

On the content level, this strategic alignment sometimes meant addressing specific needs of a particular project, as one staff member from the Royal Ontario Museum explained:

Google Arts & Culture doesn’t do everything that we want it to do, but it does enough of what we wanted to do that we think it’ll be a good fit, so we did. When we did this online exhibit, it was something that only existed on Google and had a particular purpose for a particular story that we wanted to tell. I think from all those senses, it was a success. It wasn’t about driving traffic to our website, but we wanted to, from a curatorial perspective, tell a story in a very particular way, in a way that we couldn’t do in real life, but that was facilitated by the Google platform.

In addition to these strategic considerations, sometimes the alignment between the platform and institution was a matter of expediency or (un)fortunate coincidence, thanks in part to the COVID-19 pandemic. As a former staff member from the MET described:

I think [Google’s] timing was fortunate because it happened very soon after the formation of this digital department within the museum. When the inquiry came in, internally there were people saying, “we have this new digital department, maybe this is something that we should actually take a look at.”

For some institutions, the platform’s invitation coincided with the launch of media and marketing campaigns or building renovation and shutdown. For instance, a staff member from the Harvard Art Museums recalled:

We were physically closed for a couple of years because the museum was under construction. We really needed to start a campaign to remind people that Harvard has a museum that has a notable art collection, and a new museum building will be opening in a

year and a half. Part of the internal conversation and decisions revolved around the question of where we want to invest our energy for marketing purposes. On the curatorial side, what's going to make us look good, what's going to draw people in, what is the noteworthy stuff we really want to show off? Those two things weighed heavily in our decision-making process.

For many institutions that joined the platform but had not devoted many resources into uploading or creating content, the pandemic provided an external impetus for them to take stock of their digital toolkit. As a staff member from the Getty Museum recalled:

In 2019, [Google] approached us, talking about using the platform more, but nothing ever really happened with it. It was when the pandemic hit that we thought, "oh, we have this dissemination tool that reaches a lot more people than we reach alone. We should probably attempt to use this somehow." It was dormant for a couple of years before we even really started doing anything.

The Harvard Art Museums shared a similar story about one particular exhibition:

We did put up the four stories there because it's an online version of a physical exhibition that we mounted just before Covid and the shutdown. [...] Our exhibition designer did a lot of work on the physical environment for the show and wanted to make sure that it didn't get lost in our history, so he really pushed to make these stories as a digital version of the exhibit, and he did it! [...] He designed the exhibition, he did the work on this virtual exhibition, and he was very keen on using this story feature for future exhibitions, but it unfortunately didn't stick, and other people weren't interested enough to warrant investing the time.

So, why did cultural institutions decide to work with the GA&C platform? Despite the unique situations in each organization, the comments above indicated a shared need among the cultural institutions for infrastructural resources to establish or strengthen their presence in the digital space through the creation of a unified catalogue in order to expand their reach beyond the physical space and enrich the engagement with broader audiences. While this need signaled an ideal (i.e., the promises of the virtual museum) that the larger community has always aspired to achieve, in reality it was the alignment – strategic or expedient – between what the institution needed and what the platform had to offer that motivated the institutions to actually start using the platform. As was the experience with the Harvard Art Museums, this alignment was often so contingent on institutional factors that, for most of the institutions interviewed, it turned out to be a temporary arrangement that "unfortunately didn't stick." In the following sections, I discuss

some of these contextual factors that prevented the adoption and (continued) use of the platform for some cultural institutions.

The Ones that Got Away: Where Platform Boundaries End

As I discussed in Chapter 4, the GA&C team internally distinguishes between long-tail partners and project partners. The former typically makes an application to join the platform and uses it as part of the institution's overall digital strategy, whereas the latter often establishes its presence on the platform by being invited to contribute to a particular project initiated by the GA&C team. Interviewees from 10 different institutions recalled that Google first reached out to their institution to initiate the partnership. Some of them joined the platform at an early stage when special projects were not available (e.g., National Gallery of Art, Harvard Art Museums, and Philadelphia Museum of Art), whereas others recalled being contacted because of a specific project (e.g., Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute, Münchner Stadtmuseum, and Harry Ransom Center). Five institutions mentioned that they reached out to Google to initiate the partnership. These proactive efforts usually occurred in the early years of the Art Project with individual staff members who were familiar with the museum technology community and had been keeping a close eye on the initiative's early development. One staff member from the Walters Art Museum recalled:

There was a lot of talk in places like the Museum Computer Network about the [Art Project] when it happened. Our team took a real interest in that because we had already put a substantial online collection together, and we were beginning to get curious about how to make it portable to other platforms.

Another interviewee who was working for the Denver Art Museum around 2011 recalled:

It was still invite-only even in the second round if I recall correctly. We were not part of that invite at first, and then I reached out. [...] I think we made the pitch very hard because Denver had a very significant native arts collection, and there were no other organizations at that point present in the project that represented those kinds of collection and objects to any significant degree, so we had a really good contribution to make. To their credit, Google immediately said, "yes, definitely, let's talk!"

Overall, however, many interviewees were not part of the decision making process, or even with the organization at all, when their institution joined the platform, so the institutional memory was fragmented and patchy at best as to how their partnership truly unfolded.

Two institutions that did provide a detailed recount of their communication and negotiation processes eventually decided not to join the platform. I use these two institutions – The Mesoamerica Center and Harry Ransom Center, both affiliated with the University of Texas at Austin – as well as their “failed” partnerships with GA&C as two edge cases to demonstrate some of the contextual factors that prevented the adoption of the platform and, by extension, the operating limitations of the platform’s governance mechanisms.

The Mesoamerica Center: The Promise That Was Not

The Mesoamerica Center was drawn to the Art Project with one specific feature in mind: 3D scanning. According to the assistant director (AD), they approached the Dallas Museum of Art (DMA), which had worked with the Google team to create 3D images for several objects from South America, hoping to establish a partnership with Google to create 3D images for their own collections. The AD reached out to the Google team in late 2015. As they recalled:

That’s the whole reason I got involved with Google Cultural Institute at the time. Here, we had maybe the lab with the tech capacity to scan, but we didn’t have the resources or staff to do all the scanning, turn the scans into 3D objects, post them somewhere with enough server size, and all of that kind of stuff. I thought, if they did it for the DMA, maybe they’d do it for us. Even if it was just a sample or set it up so that we could then keep going.

However, this request for technical support with 3D images was never really fulfilled. As the AD continued:

I think my big frustration in the end was that there were a lot of emails back and forth, and it was right at the transition from Google Cultural Institute and the World of Art, or whatever they were called, to Arts & Culture. In that transition, they kept handing me over to another person. [...] I have one person literally saying, “I am now the person to communicate with, so and so is doing something else, and I’m here to help you.” And then, I would get another person and then I would get another person. All in the scope of less than a year, I was handed off to four different people, with different titles every time. It seemed that every time they weren’t really answering my questions.

That was exactly the phase of reorganization and transition for Google. In the process of doing that, I think they reduced what they were giving to cultural entities on their end. In other words, all the tech knowhow of coming to a place to scan objects and sending a physical person to do that was probably eliminated, and all they provided was a platform, or what they called the “dashboard,” a publishing interface. It ultimately ended up seeming like I would have to photograph or scan everything on my end. That was the whole reason I wanted Google to do it. I didn’t need them to really provide this interface. I felt like if they digitize things, then in exchange I’ll put them on their interface and make them publicly accessible.

The experience of the Mesoamerica Center, especially the communication process it underwent to establish the partnership, highlighted several issues that other institutions similarly encountered. First, the AD was well aware of the tradeoff involved in such a partnership with private companies. The Center was specifically seeking support in the technological knowhow, digital infrastructure, and human capacities around the creation and presentation of 3D images. In return, it was willing to share the images on the platform. This realization, or anticipation, of a tradeoff was clearly articulated by many other interviewees as well. The problem in the case of the Center was that the exact terms of the partnership were not clear to the AD until the chair of the department, to which the Center belongs, signed the partner agreement.

That led to the second issue. As the AD found out only after the department had signed the agreement, the amount of support Google was able to provide fell short of what the Center had expected, or, if one were to take GA&C’s mission statement at face value, what the platform has always promised. The AD speculated on the correlation between the Art Project’s transition to Arts & Culture in 2016 and the drastic reduction, if not elimination, of some services the platform had originally provided or promised for earlier partners. It might be impossible to confirm the causality between everything that was happening around the transition period in 2016, but the limitation on the part of the Arts & Culture team to provide digitization services on a systematic and consistent scale was nonetheless confirmed by the PM:

We do digitize, but again it’s a question of bandwidth, because we’re a small team with limited resources. Honestly, at the end of the day, I would love it if we could digitize every institution that came to us, and this is where I think the misconception comes in, that we have all of Google’s budget on hand to send photographers and scanners, which we don’t.

The third issue, likely related to the small GA&C team, was the lack of effective or consistent communication to facilitate the maintenance of partnerships with cultural institutions. Again, the PM revealed that the U.S. team consists of only one full-time employee and three contractors as coordinators charged with managing the day-to-day communications with the partners. These coordinators would have been the ones who were interfacing with the Center. As the AD recalled:

Looking back now, when you look at these emails [from Google], they read like as if you were having a conversation with a bot. They sound very much like that. I got to the point where I questioned if I was really interacting with the person that was assigned to our collection, or if it was just whoever was signing off on emails that were automatically generated or something that felt not very personalized.

The frustration with staff turnover on the part of GA&C and the resulting lack of effective communication was not an isolated issue. As another interviewee recalled:

I worked with someone at Google to get them connected to [our API] and to make sure that we had mapped that data correctly. Then, that guy just left the project, which is what happens with Google all the time! In the course of less than two years, we went through six different contacts for our account before we even got the partnership live! It's been crazy! All of a sudden, we just get a random email from someone saying, "How are things going?" And I thought, "Who are you? What happened to [name]? Who's this person?" There was no account management, no handoff, and no customer service in terms of it being a partnership you might have with other types of organizations!

Other interviewees, while not feeling as frustrated, also mentioned similar situations where their dedicated contact person from the GA&C team was replaced with a generic email address, especially since the beginning of the pandemic.

In the end, due to the lack of resources, both internally and from Google, needed to 3D scan the collection, the Mesoamerica Center never launched its landing page on GA&C. Nonetheless, the partner agreement had already been signed and even has an auto-renewal clause. Since a notice of non-renewal was never provided by either side, the Center, despite having no visible presence on the platform, is technically still a partner institution and has therefore been receiving partner updates regularly.

Harry Ransom Center: Conditioned Visibility

If the experience of The Mesoamerica Center exemplified some of the limitations of what the platform had to offer for a long-tail partner, then the Harry Ransom Center (HRC) was sucked into a month-long logistical whirlpool as an unwilling project partner. Best known for its collection of literary manuscripts, HRC is a university-affiliated museum and archive that also holds, among other things, three paintings by artist Frida Kahlo. In the fall of 2017, HRC's marketing and communications team received a cold call from GA&C with a request for participation in an upcoming retrospective project about the Frida Kahlo. In a group interview with several HRC staff members, interviewee #1 recalled:

We get requests all the time for high-resolution digital images of our collection. [...] It's the sort of thing we do all the time: the request is in, a person or organization gets the permissions from the intellectual property owner, we provide copies of images, and they move forward. It seemed at first as if this was one of those requests, which was why it was a little frustrating that it morphed into this other kind of conversation. It felt a little bit like a bait and switch.

They wanted us to participate in this multi-institutional Frida Kahlo project, but they said, "As a condition of your participation, you have to submit 50 works of art and create a portal on the Google Arts & Culture platform." That was the sticking point for us. We were not prepared to select 50 objects, describe them, digitize them, and make them accessible to Google on their platform.

Interviewee #2 provided more context for the request:

We were happy to contribute the images of our three Frida Kahlo works to this larger project, but the condition of that participation was that we had to create this larger presence on Google Arts & Culture, and we had to do it within less than a month. It was a very, very short turnaround time that they were requesting, and given all of the internal priorities we had, that just didn't align. [...] As far as institutional priorities are concerned, it was a priority for them that didn't align in the same way as a priority for us.

Echoing the misalignment of institutional priorities, interviewee #1 added:

I also tried to emphasize in my conversations with the Coordinator at Google that our institutional priorities are not aligned with their work. The institutional services that we provide are very much in alignment with their goal of publishing artwork on the Internet. We can make those images available in a day, not an issue, but to devote staff time, energy, and real funds to a project that is not driven by campus needs, not driven by

researcher needs, it just didn't make sense. We would be happy to treat them like any other customer seeking access to our images, but nobody else says I'd like three, but give me 50, or I won't take the three! It's just a ludicrous business proposition!

In addition to the scope of participation, the terms of collaboration were another issue for HRC. As interviewee #2 recalled:

We had difficulty with our standard agreements or even getting them to complete our notification of intent to publish documents, which they refused to do because they already had in place some overarching agreement with the University of Texas. They said, "well, there's already an agreement with you, so you don't need to sign anything." I believe they did eventually show us the agreement. It was clear that it was with the university at large, and we fell under that governance, but we didn't participate in that documentation process at all.

The internal email records shared by HRC staff members showed several rounds of communications with the GA&C representatives about how to include the three paintings without HRC fully participating on the platform. In the end, HRC insisted that they would only share the three images and said it would otherwise not participate in the project at all. Google eventually accepted that offer, included the images in the project, and created a landing page for HRC nonetheless.²⁷ However, among the list of 31 institutions credited for the project, HRC was not one of them. Moreover, searching for "Harry Ransom Center" on the platform would yield no matching results, and users have to first locate the project or one of the three paintings to even arrive at HRC's landing page. When asked about HRC's conditioned visibility, so to speak, on the platform, the GA&C PM said they were not sure why the search results are the way they are, but attributed that to the maintenance of consistent user experience across the platform:

Logistically, in order to have works on the platform, they have to be connected to a partner. Because we are not the experts and we do not have the cultural know-how – it's our partners that have that – the works can't be floating on the platform without being connected to an organization. In order to have that, they need to have a partner page. But if you have a partner page with only three images, it just looks not very engaging or robust. It's not exactly good user experience.

²⁷ See <https://artsandculture.google.com/partner/harry-ransom-center>.

Issues Experienced by Partner Institutions

If the experience of the Mesoamerica Center revealed the lack of resources on the part of GA&C to provide some of the services expected by institutional partners, then the experience of HRC highlighted the lack of resources on the part of the institution, and due to the limited resources, the ways in which the platform's intended use is in conflict with the institution's internal priorities. Importantly, this conflict was by no means limited to those institutions that decided not to collaborate with Google. Interviewees from existing partner institutions also highlighted the following four broad categories of issues when using the platform.

Resources and Priorities

Overall, limited resources and competing internal priorities emerged as the two most commonly mentioned themes by the interviewees, followed by the lack of effective communication discussed above. In some cases, the institution's digital strategy, including the use of external platforms, was only temporarily prioritized during the pandemic, and the limited resources were later diverted back to the creation of in-person experiences and other competing initiatives. For some, individual staff members who initially advocated the use of the platform left the organization, and their successors were much less enthusiastic about the collaboration. For others, those who still championed the use of the platform simply did not rise high enough within the organizational hierarchy to make the call and muster the necessary resources to continue the collaboration (a point I return to in a later section). For some institutions, the entire partnership with Google was just an experiment for them to become inspired on how to improve their own digital strategies and infrastructures. In any case, what these scenarios have in common is the contingent nature of the alignment between the platform and the institution, which, due to various contextual factors, greatly diminished or discontinued the use of the platform over time.

One rare exception worth mentioning is the Georgia O'Keeffe Museum. Like many institutions, the museum does not have enough resources to consistently contribute new content to the platform. After discussing their difficulties with the GA&C team, the museum secured short-term funding from Google for a dedicated editorial and production assistant position whose responsibilities include creating content for a retrospective project about artist Georgia O'Keeffe. The interviewees were not entirely sure, as they claimed, how the museum managed to secure

this type of direct financial support from Google, but it involved museum management communicating its needs with higher-ups within the GA&C team. This is the only case of direct funding I identified from the interviews, and it is unclear how prevalent this kind of practice truly is when it comes to special projects in general.

Motive and Commercialization

In addition to limited resources, competing internal priorities, and the absence of effective communications, the interviewees also identified other issues, ranging from the speculatively ideological to the intricately logistical. Towards the end of the interview, I asked if there is one question that the interviewees would want to ask the GA&C team. The top response was always about motive, perhaps best summarized by one interviewee:

Why? Why do you still exist? What are you here to do? Not what marketing asks you to say what you're doing, but what are you actually doing? What purpose within the Google corporation does this serve? It's been over 12 years, but we've never really had an answer to that question.

Without clear communications about the intent of the platform beyond what the mission statement proclaims, and in part due to the current lack of trust in private technology companies in general, many interviewees instead speculated on what the initiative means for Google. As one interviewee commented:

I think there's always the question, "what do they want, why do they want this, what's in it for them?" When you're at a nonprofit, you always wonder, "why does this big, multi-billion dollar company want to partner with us?" Honestly, through various partnerships, especially with bigger institutions, we've found that it gives them a little bit of clout to have these larger, trusted, well-known arts institutions and other nonprofits. When they're on there, they can get more of the smaller ones or other people who might be a little bit more hesitant.

Some were much more explicit about the exploitative nature of the entire initiative. As one interviewee argued:

Back then, we were a lot less sophisticated about what that relationship was or would turn into. Now I look at it, Google is basically using us for art washing in the extreme. All these huge tech companies, Google chief among them, have all of these initiatives that are about public benefits, corporations, or 501(c)(3)s, where they can demonstrate benefit to

the community. In return, you focus on those things and don't notice the others. For Google, this was a very public-first path at that. How evil can we be? Look at all this great museum stuff that we did! You trust museums, right?

Others echoed the sentiment of distrust and, without using the term "Googlization," emphasized the larger role played by the company in the online ecosystem:

Google has completely ruined online advertisements. They've completely ruined online search. They've done incredible amount of damage and actively participated in the gentrification of the Internet. Why would I trust them with cultural heritage too?

This deep-seated distrust of Google, however, has not always been the case. It is important to historicize the origin of the platform and the drastically different perception of the company in the early 2010s. As one interviewee who worked with GA&C at multiple institutions recalled:

I would say in those days, we still had a lot of lingering techno utopianism left over from Kevin Kelly and Stewart Brand. That aesthetic still informed a lot of decisions we made, particularly around Google, which at that time was seen as the more honorable alternative to Microsoft. It seems hilarious in retrospect, but at the time that was the dominating framework. I think we still tended to take things that those companies – and Google in particular – would say pretty much at face value.

Despite the criticism, what was clearly missing from the conversations was the reference to the collection of data as a motive for the company to train and profit from its own proprietary technologies, as many scholars have theorized within the frameworks of platformization and datafication. When asked about the use of their collection (meta)data by Google beyond the platform, only one interviewee explicitly noted the issues of datafication and commercialization:

They're not charging people, but they're training their AI. They are generating revenue that will remain within the company at a time when arts and culture is massively underfunded, under attack all the time from neocon censorship fetishists. They're not going to charge people to come, but of course they're making money off of this when they sell AI products. They are indirectly making money off of this.

For most institutions, however, the main concern with commercialization was to minimize the risk of copyright infringement and to remain committed to open culture:

The topic of conversation internally revolves around copyright and licensing. The good thing with the Google platform at the time we joined was that it all started with a

conversation with folks from the platform, so we were very specific and intentional about what we're going to contribute. For us, that basically means contributing only things that we know are free of copyright and licensing issues.

My primary concern is that it's Google. Depending on the language in the contract, you're never quite sure what they're going to do with your data and how they're going to use it. We went through a long back and forth revising our contract to ensure that it was very clear about who owned the data that was posted there and what control Google had over it.

Several other institutions shared similar internal deliberation and decision-making processes, especially regarding the terms and conditions outlined in the partner contract. It was also because of such internal deliberations that most interviewees were fully aware of the tradeoffs and potential risks involved in sharing collection images and data, not just with Google, but anywhere online.

When further asked about the use of their collection data for AI training purposes, particularly against the backdrop of the Hollywood writers and actors strike in 2023 and the broader social debate over the use of generative AI, the interviewees expressed a mix of non-concern and resignation. On the one hand, they were not concerned about the use of their data for training purposes because that use case is already covered in the contract, though not specifically related to AI training. In the case of public domain images, several interviewees even strongly defended, regardless of their personal convictions, the rights of Google, or anyone else for that matter, to use the images and data as they fit. On the other hand, the sense of non-concern was in part due to the inevitable fact, as many interviewees emphasized, that Google has been scraping the Internet, including images published on their institutional websites, to train their technologies for decades. As one interviewee summarized:

[We don't have] full autonomy over how things appear. We are at the discretion of Google in terms of how things appear. That's something that we've realized as we've worked on it more. [...] At the end of the day, it serves the purpose of reaching more people and making our collections more findable. Most of the stuff that's on the platform is public domain and open content. This is all stuff that people could go onto our website and take and do whatever they want anyhow. People could take our entire collection, put it into some sort of datasets, and still do AI with it, and there's nothing we can do about that regardless.

In other words, for reasons both within and beyond their control, most institutions considered the datafication and potential commercialization of their collection simply as part of “the cost of doing business” with Google and having a presence in the digital space in general. For many institutions, this consideration was weighted against, and eventually outweighed by, the perceived benefits of the collaboration.

Content Creation

While the issues of motive and commercialization may be abstract and sometimes ideological in nature, logistical and practical matters also surfaced in terms of how the platform and its various features are designed and implemented. For partner institutions, these problems often centered around uploading images and creating stories on the platform.

Item Uploading. As a first step after establishing the partnership, an institution needs to decide how many and which items to upload to the platform. The interviewees shared three different approaches to accomplishing this task. First, the team in charge of the institution’s GA&C account would identify an existing subset of collection highlights based on either a ready-made catalogue or what is already available on its institutional website. This process was usually done in consultation with the curatorial team and also took into account whether the images meet the platform’s technical requirements (e.g., dimensions and resolutions). This process was also where copyright was frequently mentioned. As one interviewee noted:

I think the biggest concern that we had initially was, and this is why that initial group that we sent was largely public domain works, that the contracts with Google were flipped as far as rights went. Compared to other contracts we worked with third party distributors, where those platforms like Bridgman and ARTstor worked with all of the rights holders for putting content and making content available through them, Google flipped it and the contributing partners were responsible for rights clearance and rights analysis. That puts more work on the contributing organizations.

Second, some institutions chose specific items based on the stories they, or another institution, were working on, as images have to be first published on the platform before they can be located in the storytelling tool (Figure 25). On an item level, institutions can decide whether other partners can use their images for content creation, and several interviewees shared

experiences of asking, or being asked by, another institution to upload particular items for cross-collection storytelling. For instance, the interviewee from the Getty Museum recalled:

We had an exhibit on some Assyrian reliefs, and all of them were from the British Museum, but none of them were online. It was quite a long process to get them to add the images to their collection, so it would show up as the British Museum, because they weren't on there already. There's been other cases with University of Arizona Museum of Art for the de Kooning story that we did. The object is in their collection. We approached them saying we wanted to do this story and asked whether they had any interest in being on the platform. Ultimately, they approved of us loading it onto our platform, with the note that it's courtesy on the part of their collection, because they just don't have enough staff to maintain it.

Figure 25. The GA&C story editor interface.

Finally, several institutions mentioned that they were more than happy to share all the public domain images from their collections with the platform. This process, however, was often impeded by the lack of proper data standards and the data migration processes. Some interviewees complained about the platform's complete disregard of data standards and vocabularies used by the museum community at large. As one of them noted:

[Another issue] was the way data itself was organized. They just set it up in a way that really seemed free for all. [...] Seeing what they had put together, it's clear now that they were coming from a non-tabular, non-relational, graph database of a philosophy, and shoehorning our stuff into that was very difficult. They didn't look at CDWA. They didn't look at CCO.²⁸ None of the established cultural heritage data standards for sharing that many other aggregators had worked on for decades! It was just, "this is what we want, give it to us on our terms," which characterizes a lot of what they have done with the whole thing! For our data to fit into their schema, it was the difficulty of being a square peg in a round hole.

Another interviewee cited the lack of proper metadata standards to challenge GA&C's self-claimed mission of preservation:

Google Arts & Culture is out claiming that they're doing preservation but nothing that they are doing meets any of the baseline standards for preservation. Look at Library of Congress. Look at Europeana. There are a bunch of things that define what some of these requirements are. [...] What they are doing is not preservation because there's no commitment to the longevity of the data, and there is no data transparency about how the data was collected, how the data was processed. The data is only available in proprietary formats through a proprietary front end. They do not meet any preservation standards!

The result of being a square peg in a round hole sometimes meant that institutions had to simplify, normalize, or "massage" their data into the format stipulated by the platform, which was outlined in a spreadsheet template. Several interviewees described this process as laborious, clunky, and even primitive, but the interviewee from the Walters Art Museum provided a different perspective:

Not following major metadata standards, that is interesting, but I think their perspective was different. They want to make it simple for both a small community library and the MET, so they needed to find that lowest common denominator. I understand why they took that simpler approach, and from a community outreach perspective, I even agree with it. Maybe the museums on their own side should have the most robust datasets anyway. We are, after all, the primary source.

Regardless of the reason, many institutions did end up uploading fewer items than they otherwise would have, not least because metadata of such manually uploaded items will not be synchronized with the institution's own database. GA&C does provide a "Large Scale Data

²⁸ Both CDWA (Categories for the Description of Works of Art) and CCO (Cataloguing Cultural Objects) are data standards for the description of art, architecture, and other cultural works.

Program,” which started in December of 2019, as a bespoke technical service for institutions with more than 1,000 items to share. Presumably acting as an API, it promises to automate metadata preparation and file uploading, synchronize collection information, and provide better integration with Google Search.²⁹ Still, only one interviewee mentioned this service and said that they “never got to the point where theirs could connect to ours in the meaningful way.” Others recalled similar efforts to connect their APIs to the platform, but the process was frustratingly slow and often hindered by staff turnover within Google.

Story Creation. Interviewees from partner institutions that joined the platform in its early days recalled no conversation about the storytelling feature, although one of them mentioned that their institution had to sign a non-disclosure agreement with Google about “some features that had yet to go public.” Regardless, as another interviewee noted in their communication with Google, during the platform’s transition from the Art Project to Arts & Culture around 2016, there was also a shift in focus from showcasing individual objects to content creation in the form of storytelling. As is shown in Figure 3, the average number of stories created by all U.S.-based institutions is 5.6, with 50% of them creating somewhere between one to six stories. In fact, the largest contributor of the platform in terms of items uploaded – LIFE Photo Collection with 4,402,304 items – does not have any story on its landing page at all, presumably because it joined the platform before the story feature became available.

Regarding content creation strategies, especially in deciding the topic of the story, the interviewees mentioned three different scenarios. First, some institutions joined the platform as project partners, which often meant that there was already a loosely defined topic for them to work around. As I mentioned in Chapter 4, the GA&C team would also regularly reach out to partner institutions about new features and upcoming projects as a call for participation. Some of these calls were about broad and recurring topics such as heritage months and sent to all U.S.-based partners, while others were more specific, such as single-artist retrospectives, and were often handled by Coordinators who would reach out to select institutions with particular collections related to the project topic. Not only is this an important part of the platform’s editorial

²⁹ See <https://support.google.com/culturalinstitute/partners/answer/9584243>.

functions, but it also results in an inequality between the amount of attention and resources different institutions receive. As the interviewee from the National Gallery of Art noted:

I feel like they treat museums differently, which is a little tough to know, and I hate to see that. I suspect that the smaller museums maybe don't have the kind of collection that Google thinks is going to drive traffic.

Smaller institutions were well aware of the difference as well. As one interviewee recalled:

When we launched the partnership, Google said they might feature our content in some future projects, so we tagged them in all kinds of posts and sent them stuff, but nothing ever happened. As a small organization, that would be huge, so that was a little bit of a disappointment.

Second, several interviewees mentioned that they took advantage of the platform to create entirely new content that otherwise was not available anywhere else, including the one museum that received direct funding from Google for one of its editorial positions. These use cases, however, were highly contingent on extenuating circumstances (e.g., closure due to the pandemic or building renovation) or individual staff members (or sometimes interns) who were enthusiastic about the platform. As a result, this resource-intensive strategy has not been a sustainable option for many institutions.

For most institutions, repurposing existing content, either from their own website or based on a physical exhibition, was by far the most commonly adopted content strategy. For some, repurposing was considered a "low risk" option considering the little amount of additional research and curatorial work it required:

We did not create much new content for the platform. We have four stories on the platform, and two of those were entirely repurposed from existing website content. Nothing new was written. It was the exact same text, the exact same images, the exact same embedded videos that we've just repurposed for that platform. That was certainly very low risk.

For others, it was a matter of allocating limited resources among competing priorities:

It quickly became clear that these stories were a lot of work for minimal return, compared to the work that we were already putting together around exhibitions. We could have repurposed what we were already doing for exhibitions, whether that was our own website, marketing materials, in-gallery interpretation, or maybe if we had a small

publication or something, and we could repurpose them. But it really was such a specific format that Google put together that we basically had to make a new thing.

The issue of format was also mentioned by other interviewees. One institution said they “loved the spirit of experimentation” with Google:

But unfortunately, their platforms are just not very sophisticated, which is so weird! This is mainly for artwork publishing, but they don’t allow you to say where you’re not going to crop. In 2020, it was really forcing our content into certain kinds of layouts, and a lot of those layouts go against our internal standards [...] by which these artworks can be published. It was not meeting those standards in a very basic way, like overprinting or cropping, which we can’t control and are different based on screen size. That’s one of the reasons we did not go more deeply, and we actually ended up building our own platform for publishing.

Similarly, another institution highlighted how the constraints of the storytelling format, from an interface design perspective, frustrated the content creation process, especially when different teams within the institution had to collaborate on the story:

I got distracted and everyone got distracted with the interface: Do we want this on the left or the right? Do we want this text to be big or small? Is it a composing environment? Is it a design tool? It’s trying to do all of these things to the detriment of each and to all of the others. It was a bit distracting as a tool to use. I like to focus the project on composing first and then on designing, but that was tricky to do. It’s like designing the publication while you’re writing it, which is not what they’re used to, for good reason. That’s not what you probably should do, because otherwise you just get in this loop and you find yourself writing for the design. That’s not authorship. It’s backwards in some ways.

Internal Dynamics

The issues outlined in the previous sections highlight different points of tension between the platform and the institution, from the establishment of the partnership to the use of the platform on the ground. Another important aspect – and I argue this is what GA&C has not paid sufficient attention to – concerns the internal dynamics within the partner institutions. From choosing which items to share to deciding what stories to create, there were always additional layers of translation, communication, and negotiation between the digital team in charge of managing the platform and the curatorial team, which typically had to sign on with most content decisions for the continued use of external platforms. As a result, partner institutions sometimes

inherited a patchy institutional memory about digital initiatives in general, struggled with internal communication and collaboration regarding the use of external platforms, and often lacked the data analytics needed to justify continued investment in using GA&C.

Institutional Memory. The first issue regarding internal dynamics is the lack of robust institutional memory of how the partnership unfolded or developed. The GA&C platform, for some reason, does not show when an institution initially joined the initiative, and most interviewees, unless they had a copy of the partnership agreement at hand, could not even recall in which year their organization started collaborating with Google. A very common response to this question was: “No? I’m not sure anyone does, really! I’m sure someone has a definitive date, but even my boss can’t remember that. It’s always, ‘oh, a couple years ago.’”

Staff turnover, along with the lack of proper transition, was the main reason behind such patchy memories. A new staff member in the digital team might not be as interested in the use of the platform as their predecessor, who usually did not have the opportunity to share with the organization as to strategically why and practically how to use the platform. As one interviewee recalled, right before leaving their job:

In my last few hours, it was pretty much transferring all the passwords over, and that’s it! There was no chance of having a discussion about what our intent is behind these various projects, so most of those things that I was working on probably just stopped right at that point.

In some extreme cases, despite the best efforts of individual staff members, even the login credentials could be lost in the transition process:

I left all of the credentials to my department head, and I left very thorough project documentation. But when someone picked up that documentation and tried to take over, they were asking me, “[name] can’t find the credentials, do you remember them?” And I thought, “are you kidding me?” As long as it isn’t prioritized and made a part of someone’s responsibility, it is really easy for these incredibly detailed needs to slip through the cracks!

Despite the criticism about communications and staff turnover on the part of Google, the lack of institutional memory has prompted some interviewees to critically reflect on their own organizational practices:

I think staff turnover at Google is a convenient scapegoat, but I also think that staff turnover at the museum is a big problem too, because these are long projects, and the sustainability option has to be built into the responsibility for a position, and not the interests and motivations of an individual person.

Indeed, the role played by individual staff members who were enthusiastic about the platform was a recurring theme among the interviews. Whether it was contacting Google to establish the partnership, working on API integration to automate metadata migration, or creating new content on a regular basis, individual staff members in the institution's digital, media, web, or information technology teams were an indispensable contributor to the platform's successful and sustained adoption. Without building these platform-oriented responsibilities into a permanent role, however, using the platform as a genuine part of the institution's digital strategy would be too contingent to be sustainable.

Internal Communication. Beyond preserving the institutional memory and maintaining a consistent platform strategy, another important aspect of the partner institutions' internal dynamics was the communication, collaboration, and occasional frustration between the digital team and the curatorial team. First of all, there seemed to be a lingering difference in philosophy about everything digital to begin with. When discussing some AI-based new features on the platform, one interviewee said, "Well, I am not a curator, let's put it that way, so I have a much broader tolerance for stuff like this than other folks would." Similarly, another said, "I could see the curators freaking out in a bad way about all this! If you're speaking with them, they would be extremely upset and would want to take everything down!"

Not only do these comments demonstrate a clear disparity between the digital staff and the curatorial staff regarding digital technologies, but they also signal, according to some of the interviewees, a misunderstanding of the platform's intended use and target audience on the part of their curatorial colleagues. As one interviewee from their institution's digital media production team mentioned:

The curator really thought Google Arts & Culture was a platform for scholarly research and wanted to preserve those handwritten photo captions verbatim. We tried to explain that that's not how it works. [...] They're always thinking about it in terms of it being an exhibition and a resource for scholars. They will always come to us with 20 to 30 images, and that's where my team comes in, saying, "no, no, no, we need to do way fewer than

that!” We always try to ask: What’s going to make the best story? What are the smallest number of images that we can tell the story in?

In some cases, the misunderstanding made it difficult for curators to adapt to the story as a short-form medium:

Some of the hesitancy we still get is, for instance, the character count, which is 280 characters per slide. For a scholar, that is not a lot. That is pulling teeth to get them to write that succinctly. We’ve had pushback from them before, “this is what I want to write,” and we had to go back and say, “I understand that, but this is not the right space for that. This is who it’s for. This is what we’re talking about, we need to make it digestible.” It’s been like a training process: some people just get it, “okay, short, sweet to the point, here’s what we’re writing,” but some people want it to be a spot for scholarly essays, and we have to tell them, “that is not it, not here.”

This process was echoed by other institutions as well:

Our curators found that very frustrating to work with because of all of the length requirements. The web is not their native platform. They write long books, they write exhibition labels that have four paragraphs on them, and they came at this thing, thinking this is a digital exhibition tool, but it’s not. It’s a lot more like a blogging platform, and it is a short form medium. I understand that as a web developer, but a scholar really struggles with that, and I think some compromise would be in order there.

For some interviewees, the curators’ misunderstanding of the platform was symptomatic of their broader insufficient familiarity with digital technologies in general:

Our difficulty was the relationship with curators. [...] They wanted control over everything! They wanted to zoom in on these things, and I had to tell them, “we can’t because the image isn’t big enough or because Google doesn’t have that,” basically helping them understand what they can and cannot do. It’s frustrating for someone outside of the technology sphere to say, “Google can do anything! Why am I being presented with this barrier?” As a middleman, this was really frustrating! [...] The curators set their entire life studying three different kinds of fibers in use in a tiny town on the other side of the world. You know what I mean? They’re very specific in their knowledge, but it does not include websites, and it does not include databases.

What, then, did the partners do to address the curator’s misunderstanding? Some of the interviewees shared their efforts to communicate and negotiate with the curatorial team. As one of them explained:

It's really about trying to socialize with the curators, explaining how this will look, attention spans, web usage, all of the things that they don't know about but that our team knows about, and to really set limits on that. That's what we're always fighting against, that people always want to put in more than there is reasonably room for.

Similarly, another interviewee offered a detailed account of how they worked with curators to integrate the platform into their work:

It's taken some education, training, or just informational encouragement to get our curators and senior staff more comfortable with the platform. [...] It was a matter of working with them, showing them the benefits of being able to zoom in on an image, really emphasizing that it is object-focused because it is really about looking at the objects in a way that [is different from] our website.

Then, it was a matter of going to them and saying: Is there anything that you would like to talk about in gallery but haven't been able to? Is there something that you've wanted to write a blog post about, but haven't been able to? Or did you find something cool in the collection that's really neat, but you're not really sure where to talk about it? Basically, it was just working with them through a bunch of different angles to see what's possible on the platform.

Once we started building [stories], we then showed them the stats we had. A particularly good one early on was our new acquisitions, one for 2019 that we pulled together and published. That was featured early in the pandemic on a promo they did for International Museum Day, and it was a top banner, and it got tons of views! We said to them: look at the reach your content could be having by contributing to the platform and utilizing this partnership and their willingness to include and promote our content!

In other words, the successful adoption of the platform as a content creation tool depends in large part on a constructive internal working relationship, especially one in which the digital team can help the curatorial team to understand the intended use and potential benefits of the platform and to overcome the technical challenges of storytelling due to specific affordances of the platform.

Analytics and Impact. Unfortunately, effective cross-team communication has not been the experience for most institutions, not least because many of them were not keeping track of the data analytics provided by the platform. In other words, the impact of the partnership with Google and the institution's presence on the platform has not always been assessed or even taken into account to justify the platform's continued use as part of the institution's overall digital strategy. Thanks to one interviewee who generously shared their data, it is clear that the data

analytics provided by GA&C include two monthly spreadsheets, which institutions can download from the platform backend:

- **Page Views:** the number of times (and the average time spent) an institution's various pages (including the landing page, items, and stories) have been viewed, as well as the country, platform (web or mobile, Android or iOS), and traffic source (Google, direct from the platform, or other) of these views.
- **Viewers:** the country, platform, traffic source, and daily views sum of each viewer.

First, many interviewees expressed disappointment and frustration with the type and scope of data provided. As one interviewee commented:

Why doesn't Google Arts & Culture have a decent analytics panel? I have to download raw data and run it through this process and it's really opaque. I just don't understand why they don't have that, and it's something that I've expressed frustration with. I think every participant that I've worked with has also said the same thing. [...]

I find it really hard to believe that they are making decisions and essentially initiating content without any analytics. Do they survey their visitors? Granted, we have become much more customer focused in the past few years than before, but we don't make a decision without getting data. We test everything. It's Google, how could they not be? How can there not be some kind of analytics that they're not sharing with us?

Apparently, the current data analytics is a downgrade from a previous version. As one interviewee recalled, having worked with the platform since the very beginning:

I haven't looked at this for a while, so I could be wrong in what I'm stating. But in the original version of the Art Project, you could install your own Google Linux Property ID, but they dispensed with that feature many years ago in favor of just giving you the CSV download files, which gave you much less data about what was going on the platform.

Other interviewees shared a similar sentiment of frustration with the data, except those in a data-focused role, who occasionally joked about being "used to having bad data!" Often, the interviewees would compare GA&C with the company's other products such as Google Analytics (and sometimes YouTube), which provided the "gold standard" of web analytics and is arguably at the core of Google's entire business model.

All but two institutions interviewed said they had not tracked the data for months, if not years, with two smaller institutions not even realizing the analytics were available. Those that do

pay attention to the metrics have had a hard time using the data to justify the use of the platform to the rest of the institution:

I wish Google was more transparent and I could see how many visitors were looking at these stories. Without measurement, I can't advocate to my boss and say, look how many people saw this story, we should absolutely be putting more resources into this. We're just operating blind, just assuming that a lot of people are coming there. If I could show a lot of traffic, that would help me make my case.

Similarly, another interviewee shared:

We look at it and we keep track of the size of that audience, but it's not even one that I report as part of my overall metrics. I'm ready to answer questions about it if they ever come up in our meetings. I think the metrics that I would be more interested in is following users from that platform to ours. The hope maybe is that on the Google platform we're creating some curiosity about the artwork, and then they would go to the primary source for the latest, greatest, and more information.

Despite the ideal pathway of drawing users from the platform to the institution's own website, without informative data analytics to understand the use of the collections by the audiences or, in the case of smaller institutions, the resources or bandwidth to keep track of the data in the first place, the impact of the collaboration with Google was never truly addressed by the partner institutions. As a result, the institution's digital team often found it difficult to convince their curatorial colleagues to devote time and resources required to meaningfully use the platform as part of the digital strategy.

Summary

In this chapter, I focused on the issue of platform governance and how it has reshaped organizational practices on the ground as cultural institutions partnered with GA&C, adopted its tools and features, and altered, for better or worse, their internal dynamics in the same process. As the interviewees recalled the unfolding of their partnership with Google, I have shown that most partner institutions, despite having mixed feelings about GA&C being an initiative led by a private company, had hoped for the creation of a unified catalogue with technological and logistical support from Google that would help them reach and engage with a broader audience base in the digital space. While this may be an aspiration shared by the community at large, it

often took a critical alignment between the platform and the institution to kickstart the partnership in reality, whether it was part of the institution's long-term digital strategy or simply a measure of expediency because of extenuating circumstances.

Despite the shared vision, mutual benefits, and the genuine goodwill of individuals from both the GA&C team and the partner institutions, the alignment and the partnership it sustained ended up being temporary and experimental at best due to a variety of issues. The perceived disparity between what the platform seemed to promise and the amount of support institutions actually received, along with the lack of effective communication due to limited human capacity on the part of the GA&C team and the resulting lack of clarity about Google's true motives, made the partnership much less enticing, if not downright impractical, especially for institutions with limited resources or competing priorities.

Nonetheless, several interviewees expressed appreciation for Google's efforts and shared positive experiences working with the GA&C team. This included offering feedback on making story texts more accessible and engaging for younger audiences, respecting the authoritative voice of partner institutions in content creation, and connecting with Google developers about new features and technical issues. However, the interviews did not reveal a discernible pattern of which institutions had more success with the platform. Although internal resources were necessary, they were not sufficient on their own. Continued use of the platform seemed to depend more on a constructive internal dynamic within partner institutions, where the digital team could effectively communicate and collaborate with the curatorial staff to utilize the platform in alignment with their institutional missions.

In terms of platform governance, technical and logistical issues abounded, ranging from interface (e.g., constraining formats) to infrastructure (e.g., lacking data standards), which hindered the platform's use and integration into the institutions' digital strategy to a fuller extent, if they had one to begin with. The partner institutions, in the meantime, were not without vulnerabilities, from internal staff turnover within the digital team that at times created a patchy institutional memory to the tension with and misunderstanding on the part of curatorial staff about the intended use and demonstrated effectiveness of the platform. Despite the occasional positive feedback, the collaboration with Google for most institutions ended up being a daring

venture of experimentation in the digital space, an emergent measure of convenience during the global pandemic, or a legacy archive that is no longer being actively maintained. The use of the platform, in other words, “unfortunately didn’t stick.”

Chapter 7: Conclusion

While I have always been intrigued by the Google Arts & Culture platform, the decision to pursue this research project did not materialize until the global pandemic became a daunting reality in early 2020. Far from a tangential personal anecdote, this historical (in)opportune-ness not only encapsulates much of the platform's origin, expansion, and current state, but also mirrors how cultural institutions have interacted with and adapted to the initiative over the past 13 years.

The Art Project started at a time when most of the museum community was not ready to establish a presence in the digital space. Google's initial invitation coincided with some of the sector's early experiments with the web and organizational restructuring happening within larger institutions that established the prototypical digital team. Fast forward to 2020, and cultural institutions around the world were forced to migrate their operation to the digital space without necessarily being ready in terms of technical infrastructure or human expertise. Some of them resorted to Google while others revived an existing, if not dormant, partnership to experiment with new formats of online storytelling and engagement. This is the social and institutional background against which Google plays a part, for better or worse, in the platformization of the cultural sector.

This is also the story that I have set out to tell throughout this dissertation, one about the platformization of the cultural sector, about the adoption of and resistance against one of Google's lesser-known platform products, and about the interplay between governance mechanisms of the platform and internal practices of its institutional partners. In this concluding chapter, I situate the key findings of the study vis-à-vis the research questions, discuss the theoretical relevance and practical implications of these findings, and address the limitations of the study while suggesting directions for future research.

Synthesis of Key Findings

How did Google's digital cultural heritage initiative evolve from the Art Project into Arts & Culture over the past 13 years? Using archival analysis to reconstruct a nuanced platform timeline, I demonstrated the confluence of two simultaneous trends. On the one hand, the initially separated art, history, and heritage projects managed by the Google Cultural Institute were later consolidated into one unified brand of GA&C, as different types of cultural institutions converged

onto the platform, transforming itself into one ever-expanding networked memory institution. On the other hand, the initiative gradually diverged, particularly on the app, from facilitating and empowering cultural institutions to attracting and engaging with audiences through increasingly gamified content without consulting partners on which features should be developed initially or adequately communicating afterwards how such content might align with their needs. Despite the trend of digital convergence and the presence of the wide array of topics, the platform still shows a clear and lingering preference, as perceived by partner institutions, for still images commonly found in art museums and cultural heritage sites. However, for all the disparity between its mission statement and actual evolution, as well as the strategic ambiguity about its motive and primary users, GA&C has nonetheless provided cultural institutions with a growing set of tools for storytelling, discoverability, and engagement, which have proven to be a useful option for some partners to expand their presence in the digital space.

After partner institutions signed up for the platform, uploaded items, and created stories, what happened to these contributions? How are they being presented on the platform? Based on content analysis of the highly curated section “Today’s top picks” and the interview with the GA&C Program Manager, I revealed the essential curatorial and editorial functions fulfilled by the GA&C team in deciding the topics of thematic projects and maintaining a regularly updated section of featured content, with some authored by the platform’s editorial team and others serving to promote its new features. Based on discursive interface analysis of the platform’s interface design, I also highlighted the narrow set of user actions afforded by the platform, which, despite the objection from some institutions, perpetuates a passive mode of user engagement that falls short of the promises of a truly participatory culture. Both the macro process of cultural canonization and the micro process of technical circumscription have a conditioning effect on how content is being presented on the platform, prioritizing select content from only a few institutions and prescribing a passive mode of user engagement that is enclosed in the platform’s proprietary technologies. Contrary to the platform metaphor, GA&C is far from being a neutral facilitator that simply helps cultural institutions fulfil their mission online.

How, at the other side of the equation, did cultural institutions respond to the invitation from Google? Why did some institutions decide to join the initiative while others passed on the

offer? And how was the use of the platform influenced by its various governance mechanisms? Based on in-depth interviews with individuals from 23 institutions, I showed that the partners had hoped for the creation of an aggregate portal with technological support from the technology sector that would help them establish and expand their presence in the digital space. In reality, the alignment between the platform and the institution was either a response to the institution's digital strategy or an expediency due to extenuating circumstances. Several interviewees shared overall positive experience with the platform, but despite the genuine efforts of individuals from both GA&C and the partner institutions, the alignment ended up being contingent and experimental because of a variety of issues, including limited resources on both sides, the lack of effective communication from Google to manage the growing partnerships, staff turnover on both sides resulting in a patchy institutional memory regarding digital initiatives, competing internal priorities within the partner institutions especially after the pandemic, and internal power dynamics between the digital team and curatorial staff that may not be conducive to sustained communication and collaboration required to fully take advantage of the platform.

So, what exactly is GA&C? Based on findings presented in this dissertation, I argue that it is an under-resourced and misconceived initiative within Google that provides cultural institutions with an image repository and storytelling tools, but it communicates primarily yet inadequately with the partner institutions' digital team, which often lacks the infrastructural capacity or hierarchical power to prioritize the collaboration and allocate necessary resources to fully utilize the platform. For GA&C, carrying the name of Google was a double-edged sword that, while grabbing attention, also created a persistent misconception that the platform had the company's infinite resources at its disposal. The absence of resources in turn limited what the platform can offer to partner institutions, reducing it to essentially an online publishing platform, while efforts to digitize collections and improve analytics have largely been stalled. Moreover, GA&C's limited staff capacity and resulting lack of effective communication significantly hampered its efforts to maintain the growing number of partnerships it forged over time. For institutional partners, the use of external platforms was usually assigned, if not relegated, to the digital, technology, media, or IT department, if they even had one to begin with. While the digital team required curatorial input to decide what and how to contribute to the platform, it typically could not set internal priorities or

allocate sufficient resources to utilize the platform meaningfully and sustainably. The few success stories were exceptions rather than the rule, relying heavily on the digital team proactively communicating and collaborating with curatorial staff about the platform's intended use and potential benefits for the institution.

Rethinking Participation, Privatization, and Platformization

What do these findings mean for the broader conceptual issues raised in the literature review, such as the ideal of the virtual museum, the enclosure of the cultural commons, and the permeation of platform governance? From a practical perspective, what lessons could Google or similar initiatives learn from the 13 years of experience? After all, GA&C is by no means the only platform dedicated to arts and culture. Whether it is the supranational portal Europeana, national projects in countries such as the UK (e.g., Art UK), Denmark (e.g., Dansk Kulturarv), or Germany (e.g., museum-digital), emerging initiatives such as Curationist, or single-institution websites that increasingly function as an open platform, the same tensions surrounding issues of participation, privatization, and platformization will likely emerge and need to be addressed for these platforms to remain relevant in the long run.

Whose Participation?

Except for the two museums that renegotiated the contract with Google to add an option for users to download public domain images, GA&C, with its reliance on proprietary technologies and limited user affordances, does not accommodate the kind of user-oriented creative reuse envisioned by the participatory culture. However, for a sector that still relies heavily on curatorial expertise and professional interpretation, the questions remain: Is it really Google's responsibility to engage users beyond the read-only and sit-back-and-be-told culture? Do users really want to create their own remix or would they rather, especially younger generations, simply scroll through arts and culture the same way they interact with almost everything else online? In other words, without fully taking into account the exploitative nature of using platforms as digital labor, or the agency and autonomy of individual users to decide their preferred mode of engagement, was the notion of a remix-based participatory culture an aspirational aberration of the 2000s?

At a time when getting high enough view counts is already a commendable performance indicator for many cultural institutions, would they realistically expect users to generate creative content as well? As one interviewee put it, if a high school student learned about an artist with some AI gimmicks on GA&C, “Who are we to say that is not meaningful engagement? Is it really our place to say one engagement is preferred over another?” Moreover, the ideal virtual museum, whether envisioned by avant-gardists in the 1920s or experimented by museum practitioners in the 1990s, was always experimental, interactive, spectacularized, and sometimes gamified, but audience participation in the sense of creating content was rarely part of the idea. GA&C already functions as a brochure museum, content museum, and learning museum, but are we supposed to impose the mandate of the participatory museum on the platform as well, when the sector at large has yet to figure out a sustainable formula for encouraging user contributions?

That does not mean, however, that there is no place for a community-driven approach on a digital platform that encourages collaborative participation by individual experts or professional organizations. For instance, Europeana runs an annual Digital Storytelling Festival that invites cultural heritage professionals, educators, and students – instead of individual end users – to tell stories about arts and culture and cultivate their storytelling skills.³⁰ Taking a different approach, Curationist, an open access initiative launched in 2023, has created residency programs such as Curationist Fellows and Critics of Color.³¹ These opportunities seek to support writers, artists, researchers, and cultural professionals to collaborate and co-create editorial features related both to their expertise and collections on the platform. While not shying away from their own editorial function, both initiatives manage to embrace a community-driven approach that encourages the participation by domain experts – again, not individual users – with diverse voices and fosters a more inclusive environment for cultural co-creation. Could GA&C adopt a similar approach? It is perhaps unlikely in the short term, given the limited resources of the team. More importantly, it would also require a more collaborative mindset and communicative approach, something GA&C has not consistently displayed when working with cultural institutions.

³⁰ See <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/digital-storytelling-festival>.

³¹ See <https://www.curationist.org/about>.

The Irrelevance of Algorithms?

One of the recurring arguments throughout this dissertation is the essential editorial and curatorial functions fulfilled by the GA&C team through its special projects and daily features. While taking a more collaborative approach, platforms such as Europeana and Curationist also play an important editorial role. If anything, these alternative platforms have been very transparent about their own editorial interventions, assigning content authorship to specific internal staff members or external collaborators. In contrast, little information is available about GA&C's editorial team. The stories they created all come with an anonymous byline of "By Google Arts & Culture" and the platform itself, as the PM claimed, "tried to keep it neutral and educational." Regardless of the adopted approach or the underlying philosophy, what such platform-led content editorialization presents is a direct challenge to the mythologized platform metaphor that it is merely a neutral facilitator that helps users create and share their own content.

Meanwhile, these human-centered editorial interventions also provide a counterpoint to what Gillespie (2014) called the *algorithmic logic*, which depends on machine-driven procedural choices to automate some aspects of human judgment. In fact, these interventions perfectly instantiate the old *editorial logic* algorithms are supposed to replace, one that "depends on the subjective choices of experts, who are themselves made and authorized through institutional processes of training and certification, or validated by the public through the mechanisms of the market" (p. 192). Indeed, from reviewing partnership applications, selecting project topics, and curating daily top picks, to the operation of the cultural sector itself, such "institutional processes" and "subjective choices" mostly characterize the content-related decision-making on GA&C, in which, as the PM confirmed, algorithms did not play any significant role, at least for now. There is no denying the disruptive impacts that algorithmic sorting has on restructuring the allocation of social resources in general and conditioning content visibility on platforms in particular. However, for specialized platforms in arts and culture that value institutional authority and interpretative expertise, the editorial logic remains robust, and perhaps it should. The question for GA&C, or any other platform, is how to establish trust and maintain transparency with both individual users and institutional partners while fulfilling their necessary editorial responsibilities.

The Googlization of Arts and Culture?

The issues of trust and transparency, or lack thereof according to the feedback of many institutional partners, circle back to the basic premise of this dissertation that Google's expansion into arts and culture risks eroding the cultural heritage commons as the display and dissemination of digital cultural heritage become increasingly platform-dependent. If the second enclosure is about the adoption of legal, managerial, and technological strategies for corporations to control and commodify public information (Boyle, 2003), and if the rise of networked memory institutions is about the privatization of traditional memory institutions as they increasingly adopt proprietary practices (Pessach, 2008), did these happen on GA&C? Is the arts and culture sector irrevocably Googlized?

On the one hand, the fact that most institutions had to digitize their own collection and the decision for Google to circumvent sector-wise data standards made it very difficult for partners to adopt Google's infrastructural services and replace their own content management system. In many cases, partner institutions had to normalize their datasets to accommodate the sharing of images and their metadata with the platform. On the other hand, the platform's interface regime is unforgivingly standardized and proprietary, to which partner institutions simply had to adapt their own internal practices. That said, some institutions already cracked open the otherwise seamless interface design by insisting on the addition of a download option in pursuit of open access, while others, having experimented with what Google had to offer, decided to build a bespoke platform or launch their own initiatives, sometimes inspired by Google's technologies. Overall, when the use of the platform cannot even be strategically sustained, the incursion and displacement by Google's proprietary technologies within traditional memory institutions was hardly ever a real concern.

Still, cultural institutions worldwide have contributed enormous quantities of high-quality and hitherto unexploited images and metadata through GA&C in the past 13 years. While it may be impossible to definitively prove how Google profited from these free contributions – whether by improving other products such as Search and YouTube, training proprietary algorithms and generative AI models, or simply, as the interviewees said, gathering clout and art washing – the fact that Google says in the platform FAQ that it will not “directly monetize the content” is enough of a confession that indicates the economic value of the platform for the company at large.

Moreover, the interviewees were fully aware of, if not slightly resigned to, how their collections have been used and abused by for-profit entities in general once they publish content online. Regarding the use of collection images to train generative AI models without credits or fair compensation, the most common sentiment among the interviewees was, unfortunately, that “anyone can do that anyway.” In the end, GA&C perhaps did not privatize cultural institutions in the same way, or to the same extent, contemplated by many critical scholars, but the datafication of arts and culture, or a narrower version of Googlization, may already be the reality through the inevitable process of platformization.

Lessons for Cultural Institutions

What lessons could cultural institutions, whether or not they work with GA&C, learn from the issues discussed throughout the dissertation? After all, the overarching narrative I hope to recount is as much about the platformization of the cultural sector as about the digital capacity of cultural institutions as they work with external platforms to fulfill their institutional missions. From the creation of a long-term digital strategy to the development of a collaborative internal working environment, how should the cultural sector at large better prepare itself? In collaboration with the American Alliance of Museums, the Knight Foundation (2020) commissioned a study of 480 museums of different sizes and types across the U.S., with survey data collected before the global pandemic, to understand the “digital readiness and innovation maturity” of the museum sector. The study identified several issues that prove relevant to the findings of this dissertation, including limited digital staffing, still emergent digital strategies, and siloed digital projects where outcomes are barely tracked and audience insights poorly integrated (see also Merritt, 2021).

Indeed, the issues discussed in Chapter 6 resonate with the Knight Foundation study and highlight the importance of cultivating an institution’s digital readiness. Many interviewees in the dissertation were part of dedicated digital teams, but those from smaller organizations often handled multiple roles, making digital initiatives just one of their many responsibilities. As a result, these initiatives were often not prioritized and depended on the enthusiasm or commitment of individual staff members, rather than being embedded within the responsibilities of a predefined position. In terms of digital strategies, only four interviewees articulated a coherent, long-term vision for their institution in the digital space, whereas others simply equated digital strategies

with whatever the digital team is tasked with on a regular basis. Similarly, the lack of collaboration or communication between the digital team and the curatorial staff reflected the siloed nature of many digital projects. In one extreme case, an interviewee had never heard of GA&C until another team from the organization presented the final result of their published stories on the platform. Finally, the lack of useful analytics from GA&C or the lack of efforts on the part of cultural institutions to integrate available data into decision-making processes also tracks with the findings of the Knight Foundation study.

The cultural sector alone may not be able to solve all these problems, and despite the trend of digital convergence on GA&C, non-museum cultural institutions from other countries may also face unique challenges not discussed in this dissertation. Nonetheless, the concept of digital readiness, however defined in practice, still provides a useful guiding framework for cultural institutions to take stock of available resources, assess their current level of digital capacity, and identify areas of improvement that most urgently need to be addressed. To that end, the Knight Foundation study includes a matrix of “digital innovation attributes” – strategy, people, practices, audience, partnerships – that can help cultural institutions assess their own level of technical and organizational readiness. This is perhaps the one piece of advice I would like to offer to cultural institutions at the end of the dissertation. Whether it is GA&C, another platform company, or other unforeseeable waves of disruption unleashed by the rampant (ab)use of generative AI, the cultivation of digital readiness throughout the organization will always be an essential aspect of building institutional robustness while endeavoring to fulfill their mission in the radically changing digital world.

Beyond This Dissertation

In this dissertation, I employed various methods to examine the archived history, content presentation, and institutional use of the Google Arts & Culture platform. While the findings shed new light on the process of platformization as it unfolds in the cultural sector, it is important to note its limitations and suggest possible directions for future research. First, while platforms increasingly exhibit the characteristics of multi-sided markets, this study only focuses on two sides: platform provider and institutional users. The only reference to end users is the way in which the platform’s limited affordances prescribe a passive mode of user engagement. While

that is a normative statement about the platform's intended use, how it has been used in reality by different user demographics remains unclear. This is in part due to the lack of use data shared by the platform, a point of complaint by many institutional partners as well. Therefore, future research might situate the platform in specific contexts, provide detailed case studies of its use among certain groups (e.g., students or educators) or, from a user experience design perspective, follow the walkthrough method and understand how individual users navigate the platform interface, especially with the newly designed mobile app.

Second, while content analysis of the Today's top picks section revealed a clear pattern of the platform prioritizing certain institutions or certain types of content, the analysis was largely content agnostic, gathering information on whose stories were frequently featured yet not taking into account what those stories were really about. Did institutional partners favor deep dives into certain artists or artworks while those created by GA&C tend to be light-hearted art trivia? As one interviewee distinguished between content creation (by the GA&C team) and knowledge creation (by domain experts), this dissertation never addresses this distinction on a granular level. It is possible to manually analyze each top pick and compile the results, but it might be advantageous for future research to utilize computational methods (e.g., with a machine learning classifier) to dissect the data more systematically and efficiently.

Third, while the interviewee with the GA&C PM provided much needed information about the internal working of the GA&C team, it was limited to the account of one individual that was not with the initiative from the very beginning and is only part of its U.S. operation. Access to more members from the GA&C team, especially those managing other regions or from other functional groups, may help paint a more complete picture of the team's overall decision-making processes. Similarly, most of the interviews with institutional partners involved staff members of the digital, media, or technology team. As internal dynamics prove to be an important factor of the platform's adoption, what would have been the responses of, for example, curators, educators, registrars, or institutional management? Future research therefore could expand the pool of interviewees and seek to identify potentially different perspectives within the cultural institutions.

Finally, while this dissertation examines platformization as a broader social phenomenon, many external factors and stakeholders are not taken into account. For example, the pursuit of

open access on the part of cultural institutions may, as it happens, challenge the platform as a form of infrastructural walled garden, but this is an institution-wide decision that would involve stakeholders beyond the everyday work of the digital team or curators. Also, the cultural policy and political environment of a particular country may affect the amounts of resources cultural institutions receive to develop their digital capacity. Would Google manage the partnerships differently, for example, in European countries where GA&C is not the only platform available? Or is the neoliberal tendency, complicated by rising nationalist rhetoric worldwide, overriding the traditional state support model, thereby delegating an even larger role to the private sector in the near future? Finally, as generative AI disrupts every social sector as we speak, how would the regulation of AI, or lack thereof, shape the future direction of the platform? This dissertation examines the issue of regulation *by* platforms, but what about regulation *of* platforms? These questions invite researchers to consider stakeholders and factors beyond the immediate scope of this study and help understand platformization and its intricate interaction with diverse social, institutional, and regulatory dynamics.

Appendix A: Interview Questions

Background

1. Can you introduce your organization and your position in it?
2. Does your organization have a dedicated digital team or a long-term digital strategy?
3. How did your organization first hear about GA&C? What was your first impression?
4. What motivated you to join the platform? What concerns did you have?
5. What was the application process like? How long did it take?

Use of the Platform

1. Which services and tools has your organization used so far?
2. Are there any restrictions on how you can use the digitized copies?
3. How does your organization decide which content to publish on the platform? Have you ever taken down any content from the platform?
4. How much do you know about the users of the platform?
5. Have you collaborated with other institutions through GA&C?

Organizational Changes

1. To what extent is GA&C integrated into your organization's overall digital strategy?
2. What have been the benefits of using the platform, for your organization and audiences?
3. What have been the challenges of using the platform? How have you addressed them?
4. How have you measured the impact of using the platform? Based on what metrics?

Conclusion

1. In retrospect, what has the collaboration with Google meant for your organization?
2. If you can ask the GA&C team one question or make one comment, what would that be?
3. Is there anything else you would like to share?

Appendix B: TTP Distribution by Country (08/2020 – 12/2021)

Country (including GA&C)	Frequency	Percentage
GA&C	955	38.43%
GA&C*	534	21.49%
United States	236	9.50%
N/A	200	8.05%
United Kingdom	112	4.51%
France	51	2.05%
Australia	51	2.05%
Russia	47	1.89%
Germany	40	1.61%
Nigeria	26	1.05%
Netherlands	22	0.89%
Japan	21	0.85%
Italy	21	0.85%
Mexico	21	0.85%
India	16	0.64%
South Africa	15	0.60%
Belgium	13	0.52%
Spain	11	0.44%
China	11	0.44%
Vietnam	10	0.40%
Kenya	10	0.40%
South Korea	9	0.36%
Austria	8	0.32%
Brazil	7	0.28%
Israel	5	0.20%
Peru	5	0.20%
Argentina	3	0.12%
Indonesia	3	0.12%
Poland	3	0.12%
Slovenia	3	0.12%
United Arab Emirates	1	0.04%
Norway	3	0.12%
Canada	2	0.08%
Colombia	2	0.08%
Portugal	2	0.08%
Czech Republic	1	0.04%
Hong Kong	1	0.04%
Puerto Rico	1	0.04%
Ukraine	1	0.04%
Singapore	1	0.04%
Switzerland	1	0.04%
Total	2485	100%

References

- Adamczyk, P. (2012, October 30). More Art Project online for you to explore. *Google*.
<https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/more-art-project-online-for-you-to/>
- Anderson, M. L. (1999). Museums of the Future: The Impact of Technology on Museum Practices. *Daedalus*, 128(3), 129–129.
- Andreessen, M. (2007, September 16). *The three kinds of platforms you meet on the Internet*. Pmarchive. https://fictivekin.github.io/pmarchive-jekyll/pmarchive-jekyll/three_kinds_of_platforms_you_meet_on_the_internet
- Andrejevic, M. (2007). Surveillance in the Digital Enclosure. *The Communication Review*, 10(4), 295–317. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714420701715365>
- Andrews, J., & Schweibenz, W. (1998). A new medium for old masters: The Kress Study Collection Virtual Museum Project. *Art Documentation*, 17(1), 19–27.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/adx.17.1.27948930>
- Arditi, D. (2021). *Streaming culture: Subscription platforms and the unending consumption of culture*. Emerald Publishing Limited.
- ArtBabble. (n.d.). *ArtBabble no longer babbles on*. ArtBabble. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from <https://artbabble.org/partner>
- Ash, J. (2015). *The interface envelope: Gaming, technology, power*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Baldwin, C. Y., & Woodard, C. J. (2009). The architecture of platforms: A unified view. In A. Gawer (Ed.), *Platforms, markets, and innovation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Baltussen, L. B., Oomen, J., Brinkerink, M., Zeinstra, M., & Timmermans, N. (2013, April). *Open Culture Data: Opening GLAM Data Bottom-up*. Museums and the Web 2013, Portland. <https://mw2013.museumsandtheweb.com/paper/open-culture-data-opening-glam-data-bottom-up/>
- Barry, A. (1998). On interactivity: Consumers, citizens and culture. In S. Macdonald (Ed.), *The politics of display: Museums, science, culture* (pp. 85–102). Routledge.
- Battro, A. M. (2010). From Malraux's Imaginary Museum to the Virtual Museum. In R. Parry (Ed.), *Museums in a Digital Age* (pp. 136–147). Routledge.
- Bautista, S. S. (2014). *Museums in the digital age: Changing meanings of place, community and culture*. AltaMira Press.
- Bearman, D., & Trant, J. (2018). Museum web sites and digital collections. In J. D. McDonald & M. Levine-Clark (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of library and information science, fourth edition* (pp. 3222–3232). CRC Press.
- Benjamin, W. (2019). The work of art in the age of mechanical reproduction. In H. Arendt (Ed.) H. Zohn (Trans.), *Illuminations: Essays and reflections* (pp. 166–195). Mariner Books.

- Benkler, Y. (2006). *The wealth of networks: How social production transforms markets and freedom*. Yale University Press.
- Bennett, T. (1990). The political rationality of the museum. *Continuum*, 3(1), 35–55.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10304319009388148>
- Berwick, C. (2011, April 1). Up Close and Personal with Google Art Project. *Art in America*, 99(4), 23–24.
- Blaschke, M. (2012, May 31). Explore historic sites with the World Wonders Project. *Google*.
<https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/explore-historic-sites-with-world/>
- Bogost, I., & Montfort, N. (2009, December). Platform Studies: Frequently Questioned Answers. *Proceedings of the Digital Arts and Culture Conference*. Digital Arts and Culture, Irvine, CA. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/01r0k9br>
- Bollier, D., & Helfrich, S. (Eds.). (2012). *The wealth of the commons: A world beyond market and state*. Levellers Press.
- boyd, danah, & Crawford, K. (2012). Critical Questions for Big Data. *Information, Communication & Society*, 15(5), 662–679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2012.678878>
- Boyle, J. (2003). The Second Enclosure Movement and the Construction of the Public Domain. *Law and Contemporary Problems*, 66(33), 33–74.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315095400-3>
- Boyle, J. (2008). *The public domain: Enclosing the commons of the mind*. Yale University Press.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE.
- Britannica. (2017, March 27). *Virtual museum*. Encyclopaedia Britannica.
<https://www.britannica.com/topic/virtual-museum>
- Bruns, A. (2008). *Blogs, Wikipedia, Second life, and Beyond: From production to produsage*. Peter Lang.
- Bucher, T., & Helmond, A. (2018). The Affordances of Social Media Platforms. In J. Burgess, A. Marwick, & T. Poell (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of social media* (pp. 233–253). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473984066>
- Cachia, A. (2014). Disability, Curating, and the Educational Turn: The Contemporary Condition of Access in the Museum. *ONCURATING.Org*, 24, 51–66.
- Caines, M. (2013, December 3). Arts head: Amit Sood, director, Google Cultural Institute. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/culture-professionals-network/culture-professionals-blog/2013/dec/03/amit-sood-google-cultural-institute-art-project>
- Cao, T. L. (2024). Rethinking openness: A social constructivist approach to the promises of the new museology. *Internet Histories*, 8(1–2), 114–135.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/24701475.2023.2244341>

- Capurro, C., & Plets, G. (2020). Europeana, EDM, and the Europeanisation of Cultural Heritage Institutions. *Digital Culture & Society*, 6(2), 163–190. <https://doi.org/10.14361/dcs-2020-0209>
- Castells, M. (2009). *Communication power*. Oxford University Press.
- Chen, A. (2018, January 26). The Google Arts & Culture App and the Rise of the “Coded Gaze.” *The New Yorker*. <https://www.newyorker.com/tech/annals-of-technology/the-google-arts-and-culture-app-and-the-rise-of-the-coded-gaze-doppelganger>
- Cherbo, J. M., Vogel, H. L., & Wyszomirski, M. J. (2008). Toward an Arts and Creative Sector. In J. M. Cherbo, R. A. Stewart, & M. J. Wyszomirski (Eds.), *Understanding the arts and creative sector in the United States* (pp. 9–27). Rutgers University Press.
- Christen, K. (2012). Does information really want to be free? Indigenous knowledge systems and the question of openness. *International Journal of Communication*, 6, 2870–2893.
- Cook, T. (2013). Evidence, memory, identity, and community: Four shifting archival paradigms. *Archival Science*, 13(2), 95–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-012-9180-7>
- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2015). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Sage.
- Cousineau, L. S., Oakes, H., & Johnson, C. W. (2019). Appnography: Modifying Ethnography for App-Based Culture. In D. C. Parry, C. W. Johnson, & S. Fullagar (Eds.), *Digital Dilemmas: Transforming Gender Identities and Power Relations in Everyday Life* (pp. 95–117). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95300-7_5
- Davis, D. (1995). The Work of Art in the Age of Digital Reproduction (An Evolving Thesis: 1991–1995). *Leonardo*, 28(5), 381–386. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1576221>
- Davis, J. L., & Chouinard, J. B. (2016). Theorizing affordances: From request to refuse. *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*, 36(4), 241–248. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0270467617714944>
- Drotner, K., Dziekan, V., Parry, R., & Schrøder, K. C. (2019). Media, mediatisation and museums: A new ensemble. In K. Drotner, V. Dziekan, R. Parry, & K. C. Schrøder (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of museums, media and communication* (pp. 1–12). Routledge.
- Duino, J. (2018, January 15). *Google’s Arts & Culture app can compare your selfie to famous pieces of art*. 9to5Google. <https://9to5google.com/2018/01/15/google-arts-and-culture-application-compare-selfie-art/>
- Dulong de Rosnay, M., & Stalder, F. (2020). Digital commons. *Internet Policy Review*, 9(4), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.14763/2020.4.1530>
- Dziekan, V., & Proctor, N. (2019). From elsewhere to everywhere: Evolving the distributed museum into the pervasive museum. In K. Drotner, V. Dziekan, R. Parry, & K. C. Schrøder (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of museums, media and communication* (pp. 177–192). Routledge.

- Edwards, L. (2015). *European Cultural Commons: Supporting the new Europeana Strategy 2015-2020*. Europeana.
https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Projects/Project_list/Europeana_Version3/Milestones/Ev3%20MS20%20Cultural%20Commons%20White%20Paper.pdf
- Evans, S. K., Pearce, K. E., Vitak, J., & Treem, J. W. (2017). Explicating Affordances: A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Affordances in Communication Research. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 22(1), 35–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcc4.12180>
- Galloway, A. R. (2012). *The interface effect*. Polity Press.
- Gaskin, S. (2020, March 30). *Google Arts & Culture Booms as Art World Moves Online*. Ocula Magazine. <https://ocula.com/magazine/art-news/interest-in-google-arts-culture-skyrockets-as/>
- Gauntlett, D. (2011). *Making is connecting: The social meaning of creativity, from DIY and knitting to YouTube and Web 2.0*. Polity Press.
- Geismar, H. (2018). *Museum object lessons for the digital age*. UCL Press.
- Ghazawneh, A., & Henfridsson, O. (2013). Balancing platform control and external contribution in third-party development: The boundary resources model. *Information Systems Journal*, 23(2), 173–192. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2575.2012.00406.x>
- Giaccardi, E. (Ed.). (2012). *Heritage and social media: Understanding heritage in a participatory culture*. Routledge.
- Gibson, J. J. (1986). *The ecological approach to visual perception*. Psychology Press.
- Gillespie, T. (2010). The politics of ‘platforms.’ *New Media & Society*, 12(3), 347–364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444809342738>
- Gillespie, T. (2014). The Relevance of Algorithms. In T. Gillespie, P. J. Boczkowski, & K. A. Foot (Eds.), *Media Technologies: Essays on Communication, Materiality and Society* (pp. 167–193). MIT Press.
- Gillespie, T. (2017, August 24). *The platform metaphor, revisited*. Culture Digitally. <http://culturedigitally.org/2017/08/platform-metaphor/>
- Gillespie, T. (2018). *Custodians of the internet: Platforms, content moderation, and the hidden decisions that shape social media*. Yale University Press.
- Google. (2014, January 15). *Experiments with Google*. Experiments with Google. <https://experiments.withgoogle.com/>
- Google. (2015a, March 25). *Frequently asked questions*. Google Arts & Culture Platform Help. https://support.google.com/culturalinstitute/partners/answer/6002688?hl=en&ref_topic=4387717
- Google. (2015b, November 30). *Google Arts & Culture*. Google Play. <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.google.android.apps.cultural&hl=en>

- Google. (2018, March 31). *Content guidelines*. Google Arts & Culture Platform Help. <https://support.google.com/culturalinstitute/partners/answer/6190689#zippy=%2Creporting-potential-issues%2Ccommercialisation>
- Google. (2020, April 24). *About Google Arts & Culture*. Google Arts & Culture. <https://about.artsandculture.google.com/>
- Google Books. (2012, December 25). *Google Books History (archived)*. Google Books. <https://web.archive.org/web/20121225193810/https://books.google.com/googlebooks/about/history.html>
- Hardin, G. (1968). The Tragedy of the Commons. *Science*, 162(3859), 1243–1248.
- Hartson, R. (2003). Cognitive, physical, sensory, and functional affordances in interaction design. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 22(5), 315–338. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290310001592587>
- Hein, H. (1993). Institutional blessing: The museum as canon-maker. *The Monist*, 76(4), 556–573.
- Helmond, A. (2015). The Platformization of the Web: Making Web Data Platform Ready. *Social Media + Society*, 1(2), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305115603080>
- Hesmondhalgh, D., Nisbett, M., Oakley, K., & Lee, D. (2015). Were New Labour’s cultural policies neo-liberal? *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 21(1), 97–114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2013.879126>
- Hesmondhalgh, D., & Pratt, A. C. (2005). Cultural industries and cultural policy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 11(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630500067598>
- Hess, C., & Ostrom, E. (Eds.). (2007). *Understanding knowledge as a commons: From theory to practice*. MIT Press.
- Hughes, T. P. (2012). The evolution of large technological systems. In W. E. Bijker, T. P. Hughes, & T. J. Pinch (Eds.), *The social construction of technological systems: New directions in the sociology and history of technology* (pp. 45–76). MIT Press.
- Huhtamo, E. (2010). On the origins of the virtual museum. In R. Parry (Ed.), *Museums in a digital age* (pp. 121–135). Routledge.
- Hvenegaard Rasmussen, C., Rydbeck, K., & Larsen, H. (Eds.). (2022). *Libraries, archives, and museums in transition: Changes, challenges, and convergence in a Scandinavian perspective*. Routledge.
- Jamieson, R. (2009, April 14). ArtBabble: The YouTube of the arts. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2009/apr/14/artbabble>
- Jeanneney, J.-N. (2007). *Google and the myth of universal knowledge: A view from Europe* (T. L. Fagan, Trans.). University of Chicago Press.
- Jenkins, H. (2006). *Fans, bloggers, and gamers: Exploring participatory culture*. New York University Press.

- Jenkins, H. (2009). *Confronting the challenges of participatory culture: Media education for the 21st century*. The MIT Press.
- Johnson, C. W., Cousineau, L. S., Filice, E., & Parry, D. C. (2023). Methodology in Motion: Reflections on Using Appnography for the Study of Dating Apps. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 29(10), 1052–1063. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10778004231163166>
- Katzenbach, C., & Ulbricht, L. (2019). Algorithmic governance. *Internet Policy Review*, 8(4).
- Kelly, K. (2013). *Images of works of art in museum collections: The experience of open access, a study of 11 museums* (pp. 1–35). Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR). <https://www.clir.org/pubs/reports/pub157/>
- Kidd, J. (2014). *Museums in the new mediascape: Transmedia, participation, ethics*. Ashgate.
- Kizhner, I., Terras, M., Romyantsev, M., Khokhlova, V., Demeshkova, E., Rudov, I., & Afanasieva, J. (2020). Digital cultural colonialism: Measuring bias in aggregated digitized content held in Google Arts and Culture. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 36(3). <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqaa055>
- Klein, H. K., & Kleinman, D. L. (2002). The social construction of technology: Structural considerations. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 27(1), 28–52. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016224390202700102>
- Kline, R., & Pinch, T. (1996). Users as agents of technological change: The social construction of the automobile in the rural United States. *Technology and Culture*, 37(4), 763–795. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3107097>
- Klingemann, M., & Doury, S. (2016, November 14). *X Degrees of Separation*. Experiments with Google. <https://experiments.withgoogle.com/x-degrees-of-separation>
- Knight Foundation. (2020). *Digital Readiness and Innovation in Museums: A Baseline National Survey* (p. 25). Knight Foundation. <https://knightfoundation.org/reports/digital-readiness-and-innovation-in-museums/>
- Kobyakova, L. (2020, May 18). *Stay “connected to culture” on International Museum Day*. Google. <https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/stay-connected-culture-international-museum-day/>
- Laws, A. S. (2015). *Museum Websites and Social Media: Issues of Participation, Sustainability, Trust and Diversity*. Berghahn Books.
- Lessig, L. (1999). *Code and Other Laws of Cyberspace*. Basic Books. <https://lessig.org/images/resources/1999-Code.pdf>
- Lessig, L. (2001). *The future of ideas: The fate of the commons in a connected world*. Random House.
- Lessig, L. (2006). *Code and other laws of cyberspace: Version 2.0*. Basic Books.
- Lessig, L. (2008). *Remix: Making art and commerce thrive in the hybrid economy*. Penguin Press.
- Levy, S. (2011). *In the plex: How Google thinks, works, and shapes our lives*. Simon & Schuster.

- Light, B., Burgess, J., & Duguay, S. (2018). The walkthrough method: An approach to the study of apps. *New Media & Society*, 20(3), 881–900. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816675438>
- Malraux, A. (1974). *The voices of silence* (S. Gilbert, Trans.). Princeton University Press.
- Manovich, L. (2002). *The language of new media* (1st MIT Press paperback edition). MIT Press.
- Marcum, D. B., & Schonfeld, R. C. (2021). *Along came Google: A history of library digitization*. Princeton University Press.
- Marty, P. F. (2007). Museum Websites and Museum Visitors: Before and After the Museum Visit. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 22(4), 337–360. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09647770701757708>
- Marty, P. F. (2014). Digital Convergence and the Information Profession in Cultural Heritage Organizations: Reconciling Internal and External Demands. *Library Trends*, 62(3), 613–627. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lib.2014.0007>
- Marty, P. F. (2018). Museum informatics. In J. D. McDonald & M. Levine-Clark (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of library and information science, fourth edition* (pp. 3176–3184). CRC Press.
- Marty, P. F., & Kim, C. U. (2020). Trending MCN: Fifty Years of Museum Computing Conferences and Community. *Curator: The Museum Journal*, 63(2), 193–215. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cura.12355>
- Mayer-Schönberger, V., & Cukier, K. (2013). *Big data: A revolution that will transform how we live, work, and think*. John Murray.
- McGuigan, J. (2005). Neo-Liberalism, Culture and Policy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 11(3), 229–241. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630500411168>
- McIntyre, D. P., & Srinivasan, A. (2017). Networks, platforms, and strategy: Emerging views and next steps. *Strategic Management Journal*, 38(1), 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2596>
- Mejias, U. A., & Couldry, N. (2019). Datafication. *Internet Policy Review*, 8(4).
- Merritt, E. (2021, June 14). *Digital Readiness and Pandemic Adaptations*. American Alliance of Museums. <https://www.aam-us.org/2021/06/14/digital-readiness-and-pandemic-adaptations-2/>
- Miller, T., & Yúdice, G. (2002). *Cultural policy*. Sage.
- Moholy-Nagy, L. (1969). *Painting, photography, film* (J. Seligman, Trans.). Lund Humphries.
- MoMA. (n.d.). *MoMA Learning*. MoMA Learning. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from https://www.moma.org/learn/moma_learning/
- Mulcahy, K. (2006). Cultural Policy: Definitions and Theoretical Approaches. *The Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society*, 35(4), 319–330. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JAML.35.4.319-330>

- Müller, K. (2002). Museums and Virtuality. *Curator: The Museum Journal*, 45(1), 21–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2151-6952.2002.tb00047.x>
- Navarrete, T. (2014). *A history of digitization: Dutch museums*. University of Amsterdam.
- Nieborg, D. B., & Poell, T. (2018). The platformization of cultural production: Theorizing the contingent cultural commodity. *New Media & Society*, 20(11), 4275–4292.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818769694>
- Norman, D. A. (1988). *The psychology of everyday things*. Basic Books.
- Office of the Attorney General. (2018, September 17). *Overview of the Public Information Act*. Office of the Attorney General. <https://www.texasattorneygeneral.gov/open-government/members-public/overview-public-information-act>
- O'Reilly, T. (2005, October 1). *Web 2.0: Compact Definition?* O'Reilly Radar.
<http://radar.oreilly.com/archives/2005/10/web-20-compact-definition.html>
- Osborn, D. (2016, July 19). The new Google Arts & Culture, on exhibit now. *Google*.
<https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/the-new-google-arts-culture-on-exhibit/>
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press.
- Page, B. (2011, March 23). New York judge rules against Google books settlement. *The Guardian*.
<https://www.theguardian.com/books/2011/mar/23/google-books-settlement-ruling>
- Page, L., & Brin, S. (2004). *2004 Founders' IPO Letter*. Alphabet Investor Relations.
<https://abc.xyz/investor/founders-letters/2004-ipo-letter/>
- Parry, R. (2007). *Recoding the museum: Digital heritage and the technologies of change*. Routledge.
- Parry, R. (2013). The End of the Beginning: Normativity in the Postdigital Museum. *Museum Worlds*, 1(1), 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.3167/armw.2013.010103>]
- Peacock, D. (2007). The Information Revolution in Museums. In P. F. Marty & K. Jones (Eds.), *Museum Informatics: People, Information, and Technology in Museums* (pp. 59–76). Routledge.
- Pekel, J. (2014). *Democratising the Rijksmuseum: Why did the Rijksmuseum make available their highest quality material without restrictions, and what are the results?* (pp. 1–15). Europeana Foundation. <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/democratising-the-rijksmuseum>
- Péllissier, M. (2021). *Cultural commons in the digital ecosystem*. ISTE.
- Perkowitz, S. (2016, March 5). *The Internet Before the Internet: Paul Otlet's Mundaneum*. JSTOR Daily. <https://daily.jstor.org/internet-before-internet-paul-otlet/>
- Perrigo, M. (2023, January 15). *The Google Arts and Culture app has a new icon, and it's anything but classy*. Chrome Unboxed. <https://chromeunboxed.com/the-google-arts-and-culture-app-has-a-new-icon-and-its-anything-but-classy/>

- Persse, J. (2016, September 19). An Ending ... and an Exciting New Chapter. *Inside/Out: A MoMA/MoMA PS1 Blog*. https://www.moma.org/explore/inside_out/2016/09/19/an-ending-and-an-exciting-new-chapter/
- Pessach, G. (2008). [Networked] memory institutions: Social remembering, privatization and its discontents. *Cardozo Arts & Entertainment Law Journal*, 26(1), 71–149.
- Petrelli, D., Dulake, N., Marshall, M., Kockelkorn, H., & Pisetti, A. (2016, April). *Do it together: The effect of curators, designers, and technologists sharing the making of new interactive visitors' experiences*. MW2016: Museums and the Web 2016, Los Angeles. <https://mw2016.museumsandtheweb.com/paper/do-it-together-the-effect-of-curators-designers-and-technologists-sharing-the-making-of-new-interactive-visitors-experiences/index.html>
- Pfanner, E. (2011, November 20). Quietly, Google Puts History Online. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2011/11/21/technology/quietly-google-puts-history-online.html>
- Pietroni, E. (2019). Experience Design, Virtual Reality and Media Hybridization for the Digital Communication Inside Museums. *Applied System Innovation*, 2(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/asi2040035>
- Pinch, T. J., & Bijker, W. E. (2012). The social construction of facts and artifacts: Or how the sociology of science and the sociology of technology might benefit each other. In W. E. Bijker, T. P. Hughes, & T. J. Pinch (Eds.), *The social construction of technological systems: New directions in the sociology and history of technology* (pp. 11–44). MIT Press.
- Plantin, J.-C., Lagoze, C., Edwards, P. N., & Sandvig, C. (2018). Infrastructure studies meet platform studies in the age of Google and Facebook. *New Media & Society*, 20(1), 293–310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816661553>
- Plantin, J.-C., & Punathambekar, A. (2019). Digital media infrastructures: Pipes, platforms, and politics. *Media, Culture & Society*, 41(2), 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443718818376>
- Poell, T., Nieborg, D. B., & Duffy, B. E. (2022). *Platforms and cultural production*. Polity.
- Poell, T., Nieborg, D., & van Dijck, J. (2019). Platformisation. *Internet Policy Review*, 8(4).
- Rayward, W. B. (1998). Electronic information and the functional integration of libraries, museums, and archives. In E. Higgs (Ed.), *History and electronic artefacts* (pp. 207–226). Clarendon Press.
- Riessman, C. K. (2008). *Narrative methods for the human sciences*. SAGE Publications. <http://catdir.loc.gov/catdir/enhancements/fy0829/2007037953-t.html>
- Robinson, H. (2018). Curating convergence: Interpreting museum objects in integrated collecting institutions. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 24(4), 520–538. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2016.1218859>

- Rochet, J.-C., & Tirole, J. (2003). Platform Competition in Two-sided Markets. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 1(4), 990–1029.
- Rodríguez-Ortega, N. (2018). Canon, value, and cultural heritage: New processes of assigning value in the postdigital realm. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, 2(2), 25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti2020025>
- Rogers, R. (2013). *Digital methods*. The MIT Press.
- Rogers, R. (2019). *Doing digital methods*. SAGE Publications.
- Roued-Cunliffe, H., Valtýsson, B., & Colbjørnsen, T. (2022). Digital Communication in LAMs. In C. Hvenegaard Rasmussen, K. Rydbeck, & H. Larsen (Eds.), *Libraries, archives, and museums in transition: Changes, challenges, and convergence in a Scandinavian perspective* (pp. 130–143). Routledge.
- Rubinstein, B. (1992). The micro gallery at the national gallery of London. *Archives and Museum Informatics*, 6(2), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02770344>
- Russo, A. (2012). The rise of the ‘media museum’: Creating interactive cultural experiences through social media. In E. Giaccardi (Ed.), *Heritage and social media: Understanding heritage in a participatory culture* (pp. 145–157). Routledge.
- Sarkis, M. (1993). Interactivity Means Interpassivity. *Media Information Australia*, 69(1), 13–16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X9306900104>
- Schiller, D. (2007). *How to think about information*. University of Illinois Press.
- Schweibenz, W. (2004). The development of virtual museums. *ICOM News*, 3, 3.
- Schweibenz, W. (2018). The work of art in the age of digital reproduction. *Museum International*, 70(1–2), 8–21. <https://doi.org/10.1111/muse.12189>
- Schweibenz, W. (2019). The virtual museum: An overview of its origins, concepts, and terminology. *The Museum Review*, 4(1).
- Shepherd, J. (2024, January 24). *Art Selfie is back, this time with generative AI*. Google. <https://blog.google/outreach-initiatives/arts-culture/art-selfie-is-back-this-time-with-generative-ai/>
- Shu, C. (2018). *Why inclusion in the Google Arts & Culture selfie feature matters*. TechCrunch. <https://social.techcrunch.com/2018/01/21/why-inclusion-in-the-google-arts-culture-selfie-feature-matters/>
- Simon, N. (2010). *The participatory museum*. Museum 2.0.
- Somers, J. (2017, April 20). *Torching the Modern-Day Library of Alexandria*. The Atlantic. <https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2017/04/the-tragedy-of-google-books/523320/>
- Sood, A. (2011, February 1). Explore museums and great works of art in the Google Art Project. *Official Google Blog*. <https://googleblog.blogspot.com/2011/02/explore-museums-and-great-works-of-art.html>

- Sood, A. (2012, April 3). Going global in search of great art. *Official Google Blog*.
<https://googleblog.blogspot.com/2012/04/going-global-in-search-of-great-art.html>
- Sooke, A. (2011, February 1). The problem with Google's Art Project. *The Telegraph*.
<https://www.telegraph.co.uk/culture/art/art-news/8296251/The-problem-with-Google-Art-Project.html>
- Srnicek, N. (2017). *Platform capitalism*. Polity.
- Stam, D. C. (1993). The informed muse: The implications of 'the new museology' for museum practice. *Museum Management and Curatorship*, 12(3), 267–283.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09647779309515365>
- Stanfill, M. (2015). The interface as discourse: The production of norms through web design. *New Media & Society*, 17(7), 1059–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444814520873>
- Star, S. L., & Griesemer, J. R. (1989). Institutional Ecology, "Translations" and Boundary Objects: Amateurs and Professionals in Berkeley's Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, 1907-39. *Social Studies of Science*, 19(3), 387–420.
- Stromberg, J. (2012, April 5). *The Portrait Gallery and American Art Get the Google Art Project Treatment*. Smithsonian Magazine. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smithsonian-institution/the-portrait-gallery-and-american-art-get-the-google-art-project-treatment-172069463/>
- Tan, C. (2018). *Regulating content on social media: Copyright, terms of service and technological features*. UCL Press.
- Tansley, R. (2014, December 10). Bringing the museum to your mobile. *Google Europe Blog*.
<https://europe.googleblog.com/2014/12/bringing-museum-to-your-mobile.html>
- TED. (2016, June 29). *Every piece of art you've ever wanted to see—Up close and searchable | Amit Sood*. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CjB6DQGalU0>
- Thylstrup, N. B. (2019). *The politics of mass digitization*. The MIT Press.
- Vaidhyanathan, S. (2011). *The Googlization of everything (and why we should worry)*. University of California Press.
- Valtýsson, B. (2020a). *Digital cultural politics: From policy to practice*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Valtýsson, B. (2020b). Diving into the archive: Google Cultural Institute and the cultural politics of participation. In B. Eriksson, C. Stage, & B. Valtýsson (Eds.), *Cultures of Participation: Arts, Digital Media and Cultural Institutions* (pp. 220–235). Routledge.
- Valtýsson, B. (2022). Museums in the age of platform giants: Disconnected policies and practices. *International Journal of Cultural Studies*, 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/13678779221079649>
- van Dijck, J. (2013). *The culture of connectivity: A critical history of social media*. Oxford University Press.

- van Dijck, J. (2014). Datafication, dataism and dataveillance: Big Data between scientific paradigm and ideology. *Surveillance & Society*, 12(2), 197–208. <https://doi.org/10.24908/ss.v12i2.4776>
- van Dijck, J., Poell, T., & Waal, M. de. (2018). *The platform society: Public values in a connective world*. Oxford University Press.
- Vergo, P. (1989). Introduction. In P. Vergo (Ed.), *The new museology* (pp. 1–5). Reaktion Books.
- Warman, M. (2011, February 1). World's greatest art galleries now on Google Street View. *The Telegraph*. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/technology/google/8295487/Worlds-greatest-art-galleries-now-on-Google-Street-View.html>
- Weil, S. E. (1999). From being about something to being for somebody: The ongoing transformation of the American museum. *Daedalus*, 128(3), 229–258.
- Williams, D. (2010). A Brief History of Museum Computerization. In R. Parry (Ed.), *Museums in a Digital Age* (pp. 15–21). Routledge.
- Willsher, K. (2013, December 10). Google Cultural Institute's Paris opening snubbed by French minister. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/dec/10/google-cultural-institute-france-minister-snub>
- Wilson-Barnao, C. (2017). How algorithmic cultural recommendation influence the marketing of cultural collections. *Consumption Markets & Culture*, 20(6), 559–574. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10253866.2017.1331910>
- Witcomb, A. (2006). Interactivity: Thinking Beyond. In S. Macdonald (Ed.), *A companion to museum studies* (pp. 353–361). Blackwell.
- Wordie, J. R. (1983). The Chronology of English Enclosure, 1500-1914. *The Economic History Review*, 36(4), 483–505. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2597236>
- Wyszomirski, M. (2004). From Public Support for the Arts to Cultural Policy. *Review of Policy Research*, 21(4), 469–484. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-1338.2004.00089.x>
- Ziska, D. (1999, March 24). *The National Gallery of Art's Micro Gallery is now available on CD-ROM*. National Gallery of Art. <https://web.archive.org/web/20080531083129/http://www.nga.gov/press/1999/cdrompr.shtm>
- Zuboff, S. (2019). *Age of surveillance capitalism: The fight for a human future at the new frontier of power*. PublicAffairs.